

Values and Cleavages in European Political Cultures in the Past Decade: Cleavages within Countries Supplementary Material version as of July 20, 2024

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1 Introduction

This supplementary material collects some additional information about the methods used in a talk given in the Political Culture Lecture Series of the ECPR Standing Group on Political Culture. It contains all the tables and figures for individual countries on which the interpretations and conclusions of the talk are based.

1.1 Additional information about the Cobb algorithm

The underlying idea of Cobb's approach was to find a function of the form

$$f(x, y; \theta) = \exp\{ \theta_{00} + \theta_{10}x + \theta_{20}x^2 + \dots + \theta_{n0}x^n + \theta_{01}y + \theta_{11}xy + \dots + \theta_{n-1,1}x^{n-1}y + \dots + \dots + \theta_{ij}x^i y^j + \dots + \theta_{0n}y^n \} \quad (1)$$

with n even, $i + j \leq n$, $i, j \geq 0$, $\theta_{n0}, \theta_{0n} < 0$, and $\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} f(x, y; \theta) dy dx = 1$

which is the ansatz for two dimensions (Cobb's ansatz for one dimension is even simpler, and for higher dimensions the number of parameters to be estimated grows overexponentially).

This Cobb algorithm [?, ?, ?, ?] in two dimensions tries to provide a unified view at the two-dimensional distributions of pairs of factors derived from the many item batteries of the EVS. It replaces the simple scattergram — misleading as it is because it does not visualise the case weights necessary to guarantee that the overall sample is more or less representative for the population of the countries analysed in the EVS — and also the attempts to visualise these weights with sometricks to make different weights visible. In some cases, unidimensional density functions are used instead, in most cases also up to the fourth degree of the polynomial, in some cases up to the sixth.

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Fig. 1 Comparison of density plots for factors F1 and F5 describing trust and satisfaction in political institutions and attitudes towards immigrants, respectively, for respondents from all waves and countries without missing data in the items listed in Table ??

The leftmost diagram in Figure ?? is a simple scattergram of the two factors F1 and F5 describing trust and satisfaction in political institutions and attitudes towards immigrants, respectively, for respondents from all waves and countries without missing data in the items listed in Table ??, without representing the weights of the cases; the second diagram represents the weights of

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the cases by adding additional dots around the dot with exact coordinates — these are normally distributed around the exact dot with a standard deviation of 0.5, the number of extra dots being proportional to the weight of the represented case. The third diagram also adds additional dots around the exact place distributing the weight of the case on a square around the exact place, with decreasing percentages of the weight in greater distance from the center and represents the local density of these dots with the same colours as in the fourth and final diagram. The fourth diagram, finally, shows the exact solution of the Cobb algorithm. The unhatched magenta region is the region where at least some respondents can be found,

These diagrams should be read and interpreted as follows: The center of the coordinate system (not necessarily the center of the diagram, as many distributions have long tails on one side and short ones on the other!) represents a respondent whose attitudes in question match exactly the mean of all respondents in all countries and all waves, hence this is the anchor of the scales used; the farther from the center a point is the more different from this overall mean is the attitude of a respondent who is represented by this point (if there are any, individual respondents are only visible in the leftmost diagram in Figure ??). Densities are marked with colours in the two diagrams to the right in this figure, red marking the highest density, magenta marking a density of nearly zero (magenta hatched marks a reason where definitely no real respondents are represented). The maximum density is marked with its height, and the contour lines give additional information about the form of the density function. In some cases, several density maxima can be seen both with the help of the contour lines and of the coloration. All attempts at visualising the true empirical density distribution are always approximative, as the simple scattergram does not take account of the different representative weights of the individual respondents, the attempt at blowing the individual respondents up to a group of similar virtual respondents is certainly questionable; the same applies to the third diagram in Figure ??, and the Cobb algorithm can only make sure that the approximated density function has the same or very similar moments as the empirical distribution.

Each of the diagrams shown below gives an idea of what this frequency density function looks like: one-dimensional distributions are shown with their histograms and with the density functions estimated with the one-dimensional Cobb algorithm, two dimensional distributions (only in the Supplementary Material) are represented with contour lines and colours which depict the values of the respective functions, moreover the two-dimensional diagrams are underlaid with scattergrams where the scattergrams also reflect the weights of the EVS cases. These diagrams can be used both to follow up the development within one country over five waves (or at least the waves when the respective country was included in the study or the questions were asked in this country in the respective wave) and to compare countries with each other.

The analysis of answers to the EVS questionnaire suffers from the fact that some groups of variables — among them those mentioned in Table 3 of the main paper about important qualities children should have — are only binary variables such that these eleven variables have at most $2^{11} = 2048$ combinations (excluding the cases with missing answers). 1725 of these occur, but the 80 most frequent combination make up 50 percent of all weighted cases with no missing answers (and only these are included in the factor analysis); their frequencies are between 2.549 and 0.297 per cent — such that the distribution of the derived factors F31 through F34 is far from continuous. The factor analysis converts the eleven binary observable variables into a smaller number of latent variables whose moments (taken pairwise, and up to order 6) are approximations to the respective moments of the eleven observed variables. As such, their distributions are more easily depictable than those of the original observed variables. A comparison (in Figure ??) between a simple and a weighted scattergram of the first two factors F31 and F32 with a smoothed density plot and the calculated density according to equation ?? shows the way from the observable distribution to more easily interpretable graphic images. For some item groups the analysis of factors extracted from this kind of observables remains difficult, and its results remain a little questionable. But for most item groups the situation is much better, but as the group of binary items (“what children should learn”) is the one which is available over all waves and nearly all countries and as it tells a lot about people’s cultural backgrounds it seemed attractive enough to include them in this chapter in spite of the shortcomings of the scale construction.

1.2 Data used

The data used in the talk stem from the European Social Survey [?] including data of rounds 1 to 11, as downloaded July 8, 2024, with a total of 512,745 cases. Not all variable groups could be used as not all were used in all countries and in all waves. The variables used are the following:

1.2.1 European Social Survey

The individual variables used for constructing the scales can be found in subsection ?. All are either eleven-point scales measured from 0 to 10 or six-point scales from 1 to 6

- Trust in and satisfaction with institutions and attitudes towards immigrants

- Trust in the legal system, the police, politicians ...: 0=no trust at all, 10=complete trust
- Satisfaction with democracy, government ...: 0=extremely dissatisfied, 10=extremely satisfied
- Immigration bad (0)/good (10) for country's economy, country's cultural life undermined (0)/enriched (10) by immigrants
- Value orientations (1: very much like me, 6: not like me at all)
 - Hedonist values
 - Altruist values
 - Traditional values
 - Materialist values
- Satisfaction with life as a whole (0: extremely dissatisfied)
 - Satisfaction with economy and life as a whole
 - Satisfaction with public services: health system and education system

These factors covering about one half of the total variance of all items, see below Table ??.

Beside these items, a variable showing the educational status of respondents is used, and, of course, also information about the ESS wave (up to wave 11 for some countries, as this one was made available in late June 2024) and the region where respondents lived.

Exact data about when the interviews were carried out in each country are only available for waves 1, 2, 10 and 11.

1.2.2 Other Data

To add information about where the ESS respondents lived and what could be found out about the regions where they lived, EUROSTAT's DEGURBA data [?] were used supplying information about the DEGURBA classification of all NUTS3 areas of the European Union and some associated countries. As the ESS does not contain information about the NUTS3 region where an interview took place but, depending on country and year, only about NUTS2 regions, the DEGURBA information had to be averaged (weighted with the population size of the NUTS3 regions) and then classified such that class 1 contains NUTS-2 regions with an average below 1.739578 and class 3 contains NUTS-2 regions with an average above 2.027970. These data were added to the ESS data file and used for further analyses.

ESS does not provide regional data for the first four waves. The definition of regions in the DEGURBA database changed in several countries over time, such that only for waves 10 and 11 sufficient regional data both in ESS and DEGURBA are available for comparing between highly urbanised, mixed and rural regions. But as regional data are available for some countries in waves 4 through 11, these were also used. For some countries, ESS provides only a very coarse-grained regionalisation of respondents — for Germany, for example, only the federal states were used such that only two groups could be built with Berlin, Hamburg and Bremen as one highly urbanised group and all other 13 federal states as mixed; for Switzerland only the NUTS-2 level is given which divides the country into seven regions three of which are (according to the weighted averaging algorithm) urban (Zürich, Nordwestschweiz and Région lémanique) while the other four are mixed (Ticino, Ostschweiz, Zentralschweiz and Espace Mittelland).

Beside the degree of urbanisation of the regions where the respondents lived, the average purchasing power of their region was attached to the respondent data. Again, regions were classified into three equal groups, the poorest regions with up to 84.9 per cent of the purchasing power of the whole country, the richest with more than 103.9 percent. Unlike the case of the urbanisation, the effect of the ESS regionalisation of respondents did not leave empty groups in Germany, but in Switzerland none of the seven regions had an average purchasing power below the 87 per cent threshold.

A third regional variable assigned to the respondents is the population density of the region where they were interviewed: The first group had a density below 118.86 inhabitants per square km, the last group had a density above 267.42 inhabitants per square km,.

1.3 Factor analyses

The factor analysis whose results are presented in Table ?? uses all ESS items scaled from 0 to 10 (and some scaled from 1 to 6) and all 319564,125 (weighted) respondents with no missing values in these variables. The seven factors represent about 50 per cent of the total variance of these variables. Table ?? shows the coefficients of the VARIMAX rotated solution (at the same time correlations between factors and items) as far as they exceed the absolute value of 0.15. The items were only available for about 60 per cent of the cases.¹

Table 1 Rotated Component Matrix of the Factor Analysis

Variable	Item text	Trust F1	Satisfaction F2	Altruism F3	Traditionalism F4	Materialism F5	Pro-Immigrants F6	Hedonism F7
F1	Trust	1	0	0	0	0	0	0
trstep	Trust in the European Parliament	0.809					0.200	
trstplt	Trust in politicians	0.806	0.311					
trstprt	Trust in political parties	0.804	0.280					
trstprl	Trust in country's parliament	0.752	0.346					
trstun	Trust in the United Nations	0.755					0.198	
trstlgl	Trust in the legal system	0.674	0.340					
trstplc	Trust in the police	0.550	0.361			0.204		
F2	Satisfaction	0	1	0	0	0	0	0
stfeco	How satisfied with present state of economy in country	0.308	0.720					
stfdem	How satisfied with the way democracy works in country	0.465	0.624					
stfhlth	State of health services in country nowadays	0.243	0.622					
stfgov	How satisfied with the national government	0.460	0.615			-0.151		-0.203
stflife	How satisfied with life as a whole		0.611	-0.174				
stfedu	State of education in country nowadays	0.252	0.599	0.159	-0.164			
F3	Altruism	0	0	1	0	0	0	0
iphpppl	Important to help people and care for others well-being			0.656	0.247			
iplylfr	Important to be loyal to friends and devote to people close			0.650	0.217			
impenv	Important to care for nature and environment			0.603	0.246			
ipudrst	Important to understand different people			0.590	0.203		-0.189	
impfree	Important to make own decisions and be free			0.543		0.277		0.184
ipeqopt	Important that people are treated equally and have equal opportunities			0.542	0.178		-0.172	
ipertiv	Important to think new ideas and being creative			0.502	-0.152	0.291		0.224
F4	Traditionalism	0	0	0	1	0	0	0
ipbhprp	Important to behave properly				0.719			
ipfrule	Important to do what is told and follow rules				0.651	0.183		
impsafe	Important to live in secure and safe surroundings			0.222	0.588	0.177		
imptrad	Important to follow traditions and customs			0.166	0.551	0.152		
ipmodst	Important to be humble and modest, not draw attention			0.231	0.538	-0.366		
ipstrgv	Important that government is strong and ensures safety			0.303	0.532	0.165	0.151	
F5	Materialism	0	0	0	0	1	0	0
ipsuces	Important to be successful and that people recognize achievements				0.187	0.700		0.253
imprich	Important to be rich, have money and expensive things			-0.167		0.667		0.241
ipshabt	Important to show abilities and be admired				0.189	0.628		0.269
iprspt	Important to get respect from others				0.401	0.577		
F6	Pro-Immigrants	0	0	0	0	0	1	0
imwbent	Immigrants make country worse or better place to live	0.187	0.153				0.853	
imueclt	Country's cultural life undermined or enriched by immigrants	0.175					0.841	
imbgeco	Immigration bad or good for country's economy	0.162	0.177				0.816	
F7	Hedonism	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
impfun	Important to seek fun and things that give pleasure							0.763
ipgdtim	Important to have a good time			0.179				0.680
ipadvnt	Important to seek adventures and have an exciting life					0.339		0.657
impdiff	Important to try new and different things in life			0.298		0.214		0.593
	explained variance	4.615	3.072	2.953	2.784	2.439	2.378	2.288
	explained variance %	12.472	8.302	7.980	7.524	6.591	6.421	6.184

¹ Starting from pairwise correlations, this would have yielded about 90 per cent of the cases, but then factor scores could not have been calculated.

2 Results from the European Social Survey: Distributions of the Trust and Immigration Factors in Selected European Countries and Different Degrees of Urbanisation

The first two characters of the region code denote the country, the next two characters denote the ESS wave. The degree of urbanisation is coded in the last character of the region code (1: highly urbanised, 2: mixed, 3: rural). Data were taken from [?] where they are available at the NUTS-3 level. To adapt the data to the regions coded in the ESS, the DEGURBA levels of these regions were averaged (weighted with the regional population) and the regions were classified into groups of equal size (weighted average < 1.90342, between 1.90342 and 2.28253 and > 2.23253).

The diagrams show the two-dimensional distribution of the two factors. The horizontal axis is the Trust factor, the vertical axis is the Immigration factor. Hence the upper right quadrant shows respondents with trust and with sympathy towards immigrants above the average (calculated over all countries and waves).

“CPT” means critical point type; this is usually the maximum of the two-dimensional distribution, sometimes, if there are several local maxima, the saddle between the two maxima; sometimes even a local minimum could be identified. x_m and y_m are the coordinates of maxima or addles of the bimodal distributions. $f(x_m, y_m)$ is the value of the distribution function at such a point.

Table rows starting with P contain the significance level of the mean differences (in columns $\mu(x)$ and $\mu(y)$) and the significance yielded by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test between the one-dimensional distributions in urbanisation classes 1 and 3 (in columns mode(x) and mode(y)). If the significance level is below 0.05, the entry is marked in yellow. The numbers of respondents (weighted countrywise) interviewed within the respective region groups can be found in the middle of these rows.

Table 2: Parameters of two-dimensional distributions of Trust and Immigration factors — Degree of Uerbanisation

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Albania								
AL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
AL06U1	385	0.073	0.765	1.050	1.030	0.099		
AL06U1	385						max	0.243 1.073 0.146
AL06U2	72	0.510	1.065	1.089	0.875	0.273		
AL06U2	72						max	0.471 1.601 0.208
AL06U3	415	0.325	0.711	1.137	1.147	-0.136		
AL06U3	415						max	0.467 1.217 0.113
AL06U	871							
AL06U Sig.		0.002	0.134				0.203	0.019

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Austria									
AT07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
AT07U1	318	0.134	0.271	1.189	0.969	-0.012			
AT07U1	318					max	-0.129	0.415	0.140
AT07U3	1155	-0.089	-0.329	1.104	0.917	0.133			
AT07U3	1155					max	-0.020	-0.167	0.166
AT07U	1473								
AT07U Sig.		0.002	0.082				0.016	0.087	
AT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
AT08U1	379	0.217	-0.022	1.172	1.108	-0.102			
AT08U1	379					max	-0.041	0.262	0.110
AT08U3	1303	-0.018	-0.474	1.034	0.968	0.215			
AT08U3	1303					sad	2.105	-3.311	0.001
AT08U3	1303					max	-0.057	-0.428	0.167
AT08U	1681								
AT08U Sig.		<0.0005	0.001				0.001	0.005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

AT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
AT09U1	537	0.234	0.213	1.032	1.019	0.095		
AT09U1	537						max	0.798 0.758 0.169
AT09U3	1540	0.154	-0.384	0.977	1.042	0.067		
AT09U3	1540						max	0.295 -0.278 0.151
AT09U	2077							
AT09U Sig.		<0.0005	0.397					<0.0005 0.090

AT11	2023-06-13–2023-12-03							
AT11U1		0.200	0.064	1.043	0.903	0.091		
AT11U1							max	0.431 0.222 0.195
AT11U1							sad	-2.535 2.174 0.003
AT11U3		0.104	-0.126	1.062	0.950	0.148		
AT11U3							sad	3.106 -2.364 0.001
AT11U3							max	0.091 -0.087 0.174
AT11U								
AT11U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					0.013 <0.0005

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Belgium								
BE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
BE05U1	618	0.033	-0.134	0.977	0.805	0.046		
BE05U1	618						max	0.397
BE05U1	618						sad	-2.694
BE05U2	679	-0.032	-0.091	0.968	0.794	0.113		
BE05U2	679						max	0.369
BE05U2	679						sad	-2.671
BE05U3	170	0.230	-0.021	0.929	0.724	0.118		
BE05U3	170						max	0.590
								0.249
								0.303
	BE05U1							
	BE05U2							
	BE05U3							
BE05U	1467							
BE05U Sig.		0.052	0.165					0.049
BE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
BE06U1	654	0.235	-0.057	0.981	0.816	0.111		
BE06U1	654						max	0.637
BE06U1	654						sad	-2.508
BE06U2	808	0.147	-0.133	0.932	0.777	0.087		
BE06U2	808						max	0.619
BE06U3	182	0.087	-0.233	1.043	0.783	0.167		
BE06U3	182						sad	1.945
BE06U3	182						max	0.551
BE06U3	182						sad	-2.304
								1.726
								0.002
	BE06U1							
	BE06U2							
	BE06U3							
BE06U	1645							
BE06U Sig.		0.109	0.641					0.342

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
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BE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
BE07U1	627	0.126	-0.064	1.026	0.860	0.165		
BE07U1	627						max	0.607 0.308 0.224
BE07U2	756	0.126	-0.187	1.008	0.786	0.134		
BE07U2	756						sad	0.577 -3.829 0.001
BE07U2	756						max	0.667 0.035 0.270
BE07U3	175	-0.053	-0.177	0.966	0.936	0.104		
BE07U3	175						max	0.487 0.181 0.208
BE07U	1558							
BE07U Sig.		0.026	0.012				0.335	0.002
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BE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
BE08U1	618	0.123	0.127	0.967	0.816	0.023		
BE08U1	618						max	0.650 0.274 0.294
BE08U2	746	0.064	-0.082	0.995	0.803	0.114		
BE08U2	746						max	0.674 0.173 0.265
BE08U3	220	-0.169	0.034	0.965	0.813	0.113		
BE08U3	220						max	0.328 0.144 0.248
BE08U	1585							
BE08U Sig.		<0.0005	0.135				0.005	0.012

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

BE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
BE09U1	639	0.198	0.168	0.905	0.804	0.009			
BE09U1	639					sad	0.258	-3.119	0.002
BE09U1	639					max	0.569	0.278	0.311
BE09U2	722	0.159	0.012	0.924	0.792	0.208			
BE09U2	722					max	0.647	0.215	0.287
BE09U3	164	-0.022	0.251	0.942	0.801	-0.019			
BE09U3	164					sad	1.012	-2.777	0.001
BE09U3	164					max	0.725	0.499	0.298

BE09U	1525								
BE09U Sig.		0.003	0.318				0.821	0.221	

BE10	2021-10-28–2022-09-02								
BE10U1	458	0.046	0.258	1.017	0.860	0.121			
BE10U1	458					max	0.656	0.513	0.211
BE10U2	532	0.143	0.185	0.994	0.719	0.055			
BE10U2	532					max	0.661	0.386	0.324
BE10U3	128	0.144	0.256	0.895	0.763	0.113			
BE10U3	128					max	0.712	0.185	0.254

BE10U	1117								
BE10U Sig.		0.293	0.832				0.183	0.631	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Bulgaria								
BG05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
BG05U1	568	-0.433	0.635	0.990	1.031	-0.151		
BG05U1	568						max	-0.609 0.621 0.145
BG05U2	515	-0.288	0.518	1.129	1.014	-0.142		
BG05U2	515						sad	-2.005 -2.877 0.003
BG05U2	515						max	-0.271 0.640 0.161
BG05U3	235	0.099	0.677	1.039	0.962	-0.238		
BG05U3	235						max	-0.187 0.805 0.177
BG05U	1318							
BG05U Sig.		0.040	0.567					0.157 0.421
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BG06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
BG06U1	499	-0.354	0.301	0.977	0.883	-0.246		
BG06U1	499						max	-0.236 0.120 0.209
BG06U1	499						sad	0.094 3.638 0.002
BG06U2	533	-0.442	0.551	1.172	1.140	-0.111		
BG06U2	533						max	-0.700 0.570 0.124
BG06U3	220	-0.511	0.632	0.953	1.025	0.026		
BG06U3	220						max	-0.171 0.934 0.139
BG06U	1251							
BG06U Sig.		0.155	<0.0005					0.092 <0.0005

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		

BG09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
BG09U1	406	-0.662	-0.101	0.924	0.974	-0.239				
BG09U1	406					max	-0.878	0.270	0.169	
BG09U2	429	-0.492	-0.150	1.124	1.070	-0.049				
BG09U2	429					max	-0.864	-0.505	0.141	
BG09U3	189	-0.289	0.108	1.272	1.372	-0.006				
BG09U3	189					max	1.571	1.474	0.049	
BG09U3	189					max	-1.185	-1.262	0.114	
BG09U3	189					sad	0.279	1.063	0.041	

BG09U	1024									
BG09U Sig.		0.005	0.040				0.001	0.006		

BG10	2021-06-28–2021-09-30									
BG10U1	643	-0.574	0.062	1.041	1.231	0.012				
BG10U1	643					max	-1.003	-0.289	0.118	
BG10U2	1086	-0.453	0.204	0.998	1.041	-0.143				
BG10U2	1086					max	-0.540	0.343	0.128	
BG10U3	409	-0.193	0.259	0.994	0.922	0.104				
BG10U3	409					sad	1.529	-2.700	0.002	
BG10U3	409					max	-0.280	0.432	0.184	

BG10U	2138									
BG10U Sig.		<0.0005	0.006				<0.0005	0.001		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Switzerland									
CH05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
CH05U1	195	0.316	0.117	0.870	0.772	-0.128			
CH05U1	195					max	0.582	0.281	0.271
CH05U2	523	0.330	0.121	0.913	0.852	-0.082			
CH05U2	523					max	0.600	0.241	0.249
CH05U3	414	0.184	0.007	0.894	0.792	-0.110			
CH05U3	414					max	0.481	0.090	0.253
CH05U	1133								
CH05U Sig.		0.037	0.082				0.474	0.276	
CH06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
CH06U1	180	0.291	0.042	0.854	0.757	0.117			
CH06U1	180					max	0.703	0.128	0.269
CH06U2	555	0.379	-0.025	0.827	0.819	-0.025			
CH06U2	555					max	0.717	0.097	0.261
CH06U3	433	0.331	-0.006	0.845	0.771	-0.080			
CH06U3	433					sad	0.137	-3.477	0.001
CH06U3	433					max	0.646	0.063	0.307
CH06U	1168								
CH06U Sig.		0.773	0.097				0.694	0.469	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N		$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

CH07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
CH07U1	196	0.381	0.074	0.788	0.749	0.030				
CH07U1	196						max	0.620	0.204	0.289
CH07U2	570	0.329	-0.004	0.840	0.815	-0.028				
CH07U2	570						max	0.530	0.094	0.272
CH07U3	455	0.333	<0.0005	0.852	0.764	0.004				
CH07U3	455						max	0.607	0.095	0.297
		CH07U1			CH07U2			CH07U3		
CH07U	1222									
CH07U Sig.		0.143	0.298					0.236	0.200	

CH08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31									
CH08U1	191	0.458	0.054	0.783	0.841	0.006				
CH08U1	191						max	0.608	0.202	0.269
CH08U2	579	0.315	-0.003	0.912	0.856	-0.053				
CH08U2	579						max	0.646	0.162	0.232
CH08U2	579						sad	-2.114	2.622	0.002
CH08U3	444	0.355	-0.132	0.843	0.789	0.070				
CH08U3	444						max	0.502	0.021	0.283
CH08U3	444						min	-3.874	-0.280	0.000
		CH08U1			CH08U2			CH08U3		
CH08U	1214									
CH08U Sig.		0.143	0.011					0.230	0.050	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
CH09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
CH09U1	200	0.325	0.012	0.861	0.840	-0.097				
CH09U1	200						max	0.660	0.154	0.260
CH09U2	512	0.426	0.011	0.852	0.766	0.074				
CH09U2	512						max	0.716	0.072	0.282
CH09U3	396	0.417	0.012	0.869	0.780	-0.060				
CH09U3	396						max	0.584	0.077	0.298
CH09U3	396						sad	-3.223	-0.132	0.002
CH09U3	396						sad	-1.316	2.985	0.001
CH09U	1108									
CH09U Sig.		0.513	0.184					0.427	0.304	
CH10	2021-05-05–2022-05-02									
CH10U1	190	0.409	0.096	0.949	0.881	-0.142				
CH10U1	190						max	0.862	0.342	0.225
CH10U2	565	0.519	0.209	0.858	0.799	0.030				
CH10U2	565						max	0.756	0.362	0.298
CH10U3	437	0.395	0.060	0.834	0.720	0.124				
CH10U3	437						sad	-0.094	-3.139	0.001
CH10U3	437						max	0.773	0.174	0.333
CH10U	1192									
CH10U Sig.		0.059	0.009					0.504	0.301	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
CH11	2023-03-11–2024-01-31								
CH11U1	154	0.487	0.175	0.831	0.718	0.089			
CH11U1	154					max	0.894	0.542	0.355
CH11U2	479	0.514	0.181	0.818	0.749	0.058			
CH11U2	479					max	0.780	0.245	0.311
CH11U3	407	0.409	0.040	0.813	0.801	0.138			
CH11U3	407					max	0.871	0.182	0.280

CH11U1

CH11U2

CH11U3

CH11U 1040

CH11U Sig.

0.161 0.017

0.148 0.027

Cyprus

CY05 2010-01-01–2011-12-31

CY05U1 728 0.087 -0.572 1.092 0.939 -0.195

CY05U1 728

max 0.237 -0.873 0.171

CY05U1

CY05U 728

CY05U Sig.

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

CY06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
CY06U1	846	-0.280	-0.819	1.094	0.949	-0.072		
CY06U1	846						max	-0.619 -1.242 0.154
CY06U	846							
CY06U	Sig.							

CY09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
CY09U1	656	-0.182	-0.254	0.889	0.886	-0.109		
CY09U1	656						max	-0.011 -0.180 0.190
CY09U	656							
CY09U	Sig.							

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
CZ05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
CZ05U1	231	-0.156	-0.326	0.995	0.875	-0.216			
CZ05U1	231					max	-0.724	0.014	0.159
CZ05U2	394	-0.213	-0.159	1.064	0.935	-0.136			
CZ05U2	394					max	-0.443	-0.146	0.170
CZ05U3	1271	-0.252	-0.306	1.003	0.888	-0.066			
CZ05U3	1271					max	-0.506	-0.362	0.199

CZ05U	1896							
CZ05U Sig.		0.378	0.012				0.038	0.482

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
CZ06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
CZ06U1	200	0.152	-0.303	1.104	0.952	-0.260			
CZ06U1	200					max	-0.676	0.112	0.179
CZ06U2	263	-0.418	-0.196	1.164	0.902	-0.300			
CZ06U2	263					sad	-1.533	-3.566	0.001
CZ06U2	263					max	-1.099	-0.134	0.224
CZ06U2	263					min	-0.539	3.693	0.000
CZ06U2	263					sad	-2.531	3.724	0.001
CZ06U3	926	-0.398	-0.224	1.102	0.955	-0.152			
CZ06U3	926					max	-0.659	-0.177	0.165

CZ06U	1389							
CZ06U Sig.		<0.0005	0.457				<0.0005	0.548

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

CZ07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
CZ07U1	158	0.121	-0.632	1.229	0.885	-0.252			
CZ07U1	158						max	1.102 -0.723 0.215	
CZ07U1	158						sad	-1.961 -2.562 0.015	
CZ07U1	158						sad	-0.392 -0.389 0.132	
CZ07U1	158						max	-1.099 -0.338 0.142	
CZ07U2	320	-0.316	-0.406	1.010	0.810	-0.158			
CZ07U2	320						max	-0.054 -0.217 0.200	
CZ07U3	1003	-0.152	-0.491	1.070	0.790	-0.032			
CZ07U3	1003						max	-0.326 -0.432 0.219	
	CZ07U1			CZ07U2			CZ07U3		
CZ07U	1481								
CZ07U Sig.		<0.0005	0.015				0.001	0.041	

CZ08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
CZ08U1	239	-0.068	-0.747	1.097	0.915	0.018			
CZ08U1	239						max	-0.078 -0.877 0.151	
CZ08U2	387	0.029	-0.662	1.056	0.877	0.023			
CZ08U2	387						max	0.007 -0.575 0.166	
CZ08U3	1354	0.039	-0.549	1.062	0.845	0.011			
CZ08U3	1354						max	0.263 -0.398 0.179	
	CZ08U1			CZ08U2			CZ08U3		
CZ08U	1980								
CZ08U Sig.		0.362	0.001				0.182	0.005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

CZ09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
CZ09U1	232	-0.105	-0.582	1.023	0.984	0.274			
CZ09U1	232					max	-0.337	-0.961	0.174
CZ09U2	371	-0.155	-0.691	1.067	0.948	0.178			
CZ09U2	371					max	-0.384	-0.772	0.151
CZ09U3	1249	0.056	-0.526	1.148	0.882	0.086			
CZ09U3	1249					max	0.414	-0.184	0.166
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ09U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ09U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ09U3</p> </div> </div>									
CZ09U	1852								
CZ09U Sig.		0.002	0.009				0.010	0.002	

CZ10	2021-07-07–2021-09-26								
CZ10U1	271	0.050	-0.238	1.020	1.017	0.064			
CZ10U1	271					max	0.185	0.073	0.144
CZ10U2	356	0.264	-0.306	1.051	0.868	0.053			
CZ10U2	356					max	0.870	0.040	0.183
CZ10U3	1306	0.306	-0.352	1.212	1.013	0.187			
CZ10U3	1306					max	1.158	0.308	0.152
CZ10U3	1306					max	-1.014	-1.250	0.085
CZ10U3	1306					sad	-0.501	-0.811	0.083
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ10U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ10U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ10U3</p> </div> </div>									
CZ10U	1932								
CZ10U Sig.		0.116	0.041				0.154	0.173	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Germany									
DE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
DE05U1	653	0.120	0.090	0.953	0.926	0.108			
DE05U1	653					max	0.177	0.278	0.194
DE05U2	1082	-0.112	0.002	0.889	0.846	0.031			
DE05U2	1082					max	-0.040	0.019	0.207
DE05U3	630	-0.088	-0.102	0.869	0.918	0.093			
DE05U3	630					max	0.015	0.038	0.194
			<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE05U1</p> </div> </div>						
DE05U	2364								
DE05U Sig.		0.043	0.065				0.002	0.240	
DE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
DE06U1	751	0.167	0.187	0.807	0.890	-0.002			
DE06U1	751					max	0.304	0.255	0.225
DE06U2	1150	0.001	0.115	0.886	0.805	0.088			
DE06U2	1150					sad	0.746	-3.407	0.001
DE06U2	1150					max	0.151	0.193	0.240
DE06U3	650	0.042	0.042	0.896	0.864	0.047			
DE06U3	650					max	0.213	0.139	0.229
			<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE06U1</p> </div> </div>						
DE06U	2551								
DE06U Sig.		<0.0005	0.006				0.001	<0.0005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

DE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
DE07U1	766	0.046	0.149	0.921	0.892	0.144			
DE07U1	766					max	0.394	0.419	0.200
DE07U2	1242	0.026	0.019	0.940	0.844	0.063			
DE07U2	1242					max	0.214	0.104	0.220
DE07U3	637	-0.012	-0.061	0.979	0.873	0.159			
DE07U3	637					max	0.372	0.164	0.208
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE07U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE07U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE07U3</p> </div> </div>									
DE07U	2646								
DE07U Sig.		0.512	<0.0005				0.566	<0.0005	

DE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
DE08U1	743	0.111	0.079	0.927	0.898	0.082			
DE08U1	743					max	0.559	0.313	0.200
DE08U1	743					sad	-2.398	2.245	0.005
DE08U2	1229	0.131	-0.063	0.905	0.858	0.121			
DE08U2	1229					max	0.430	0.066	0.208
DE08U3	613	0.047	-0.109	0.962	0.891	0.152			
DE08U3	613					max	0.345	0.123	0.196
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE08U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE08U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>DE08U3</p> </div> </div>									
DE08U	2585								
DE08U Sig.		0.813	0.228				0.516	0.006	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
DE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
DE09U1	604	0.224	0.112	0.939	0.936	0.181				
DE09U1	604					max	0.562	0.390	0.197	
DE09U2	961	0.061	0.056	0.929	0.910	0.149				
DE09U2	961					max	0.525	0.456	0.192	
DE09U3	517	0.018	-0.061	0.959	0.908	0.147				
DE09U3	517					max	0.425	0.121	0.176	
DE09U	2082									
DE09U Sig.		0.088	0.044				0.005	0.019		
DE11	2023-05-12–2023-12-17									
DE11U1	669	0.328	0.099	0.995	0.853	0.270				
DE11U1	669					max	0.810	0.373	0.231	
DE11U1	669					sad	-2.098	2.053	0.003	
DE11U2	1033	0.270	0.051	0.977	0.876	0.231				
DE11U2	1033					max	0.785	0.364	0.209	
DE11U2	1033					sad	-2.075	2.137	0.005	
DE11U3	468	0.210	-0.071	1.021	0.842	0.290				
DE11U3	468					max	0.644	0.128	0.217	
DE11U3	468					sad	-2.256	1.805	0.005	
DE11U	2169									
DE11U Sig.		0.118	0.018				0.730	<0.0005		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Denmark								
DK05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
DK05U1	386	0.528	0.266	0.866	0.899	-0.143		
DK05U1	386						max	0.944 0.393 0.237
DK05U3	896	0.539	-0.095	0.835	0.895	-0.007		
DK05U3	896						max	0.739 0.069 0.222
DK05U	1282							
DK05U Sig.		<0.0005	0.203					<0.0005 0.184
DK06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
DK06U1	414	0.683	0.331	0.862	0.863	0.016		
DK06U1	414						max	0.924 0.582 0.273
DK06U1	414						sad	-2.243 1.841 0.003
DK06U3	950	0.604	-0.078	0.828	0.933	0.142		
DK06U3	950						max	0.866 0.154 0.208
DK06U	1364							
DK06U Sig.		<0.0005	0.083					<0.0005 0.297

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

DK07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
DK07U1	412	0.592	0.109	0.935	0.913	-0.004			
DK07U1	412					sad	3.033	-2.657	0.001
DK07U1	412					max	0.854	0.403	0.235
DK07U1	412					sad	-2.252	2.008	0.003
DK07U3	889	0.425	-0.250	0.895	0.935	0.152			
DK07U3	889					max	0.860	0.076	0.192
DK07U	1301								
DK07U Sig.		<0.0005	0.919				<0.0005	0.939	

DK09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
DK09U1	393	0.644	-0.083	0.908	0.858	0.019			
DK09U1	393					sad	-1.661	-2.283	0.005
DK09U1	393					max	0.652	0.242	0.229
DK09U3	870	0.569	-0.035	0.840	0.927	0.027			
DK09U3	870					max	0.959	0.265	0.226
DK09U	1263								
DK09U Sig.		0.154	0.383				0.020	0.152	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Estonia								
EE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
EE05U1	449	0.295	-0.043	0.894	0.882	-0.148		
EE05U1	449						max	0.432 0.050 0.228
EE05U1	449						sad	-3.108 1.231 0.002
EE05U2	109	-0.071	0.182	1.083	0.920	-0.159		
EE05U2	109						max	0.711 0.048 0.120
EE05U2	109						sad	-0.265 -0.265 0.111
EE05U2	109						max	-0.865 -0.333 0.113
EE05U3	790	0.194	-0.248	0.948	0.786	-0.096		
EE05U3	790						max	0.337 -0.131 0.244
EE05U	1348							
EE05U Sig.		0.001	<0.0005				0.013	<0.0005
EE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
EE06U1	656	0.117	0.091	0.891	0.853	-0.174		
EE06U1	656						max	0.198 0.089 0.220
EE06U2	229	-0.072	0.322	1.113	0.985	-0.246		
EE06U2	229						max	-0.204 0.426 0.164
EE06U3	908	0.151	0.013	0.924	0.856	-0.098		
EE06U3	908						max	0.187 0.077 0.213
EE06U	1793							
EE06U Sig.		0.006	<0.0005				0.663	0.176

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		

EE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
EE07U1	743	0.046	0.044	0.952	0.840	-0.016				
EE07U1	743						min	0.307 -3.898 0.000		
EE07U1	743						max	0.306 0.141 0.235		
EE07U2	271	0.034	0.017	1.068	0.976	-0.054				
EE07U2	271						max	-0.203 0.317 0.154		
EE07U3	627	0.098	0.014	0.972	0.804	-0.064				
EE07U3	627						sad	1.281 -3.118 0.001		
EE07U3	627						max	0.279 0.088 0.245		

EE07U	1642									
EE07U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005		

EE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31									
EE08U1	797	0.301	-0.232	0.900	0.896	0.014				
EE08U1	797						max	0.419 -0.089 0.210		
EE08U2	149	-0.233	-0.375	1.052	0.955	-0.201				
EE08U2	149						max	-1.013 -0.295 0.161		
EE08U3	808	0.174	-0.231	0.934	0.860	0.127				
EE08U3	808						max	0.546 -0.134 0.221		

EE08U	1754									
EE08U Sig.		<0.0005	0.423				<0.0005	0.298		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

EE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
EE09U1	723	0.355	-0.087	0.963	0.839	-0.043		
EE09U1	723					sad	1.763	-3.465
EE09U1	723					max	0.589	0.010
EE09U2	154	-0.183	-0.440	1.033	1.014	0.029		
EE09U2	154					max	-0.249	-0.374
EE09U3	840	0.137	-0.283	0.950	0.819	0.162		
EE09U3	840					max	0.508	-0.108
EE09U	1717							
EE09U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005

EE10	2021-06-09–2021-12-31							
EE10U1	632	0.359	0.062	0.909	0.853	0.056		
EE10U1	632						sad	1.043
EE10U1	632						max	0.655
EE10U2	89	0.028	-0.342	1.168	1.080	0.084		
EE10U2	89						sad	-0.292
EE10U2	89						max	1.312
EE10U2	89						sad	-0.655
EE10U2	89						max	-1.248
EE10U3	647	0.116	-0.168	0.992	0.926	0.004		
EE10U3	647						max	0.432
EE10U	1368							
EE10U Sig.		<0.0005	0.113				<0.0005	0.346

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Spain										
ES05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
ES05U1	1212	-0.120	0.229	0.957	0.840	-0.047				
ES05U1	1212						max	0.197	0.415	0.222
ES05U2	228	-0.184	0.207	0.963	0.855	0.027				
ES05U2	228						max	0.043	0.360	0.229
ES05U2	228						sad	-2.489	2.896	0.004
ES05U3	120	-0.082	0.262	1.001	0.841	-0.156				
ES05U3	120						max	0.018	0.325	0.204
ES05U	1560									
ES05U Sig.		0.001	0.038					0.047	0.003	
ES06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
ES06U1	1286	-0.416	0.498	0.985	0.984	-0.096				
ES06U1	1286						max	-0.485	0.684	0.157
ES06U2	226	-0.430	0.475	0.926	0.957	-0.304				
ES06U2	226						max	-0.402	0.480	0.195
ES06U3	111	-0.154	0.377	0.944	1.003	-0.175				
ES06U3	111						sad	2.696	-2.551	0.002
ES06U3	111						max	0.097	0.921	0.168
ES06U	1623									
ES06U Sig.		0.022	0.454					0.068	0.462	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		

ES07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
ES07U1	1083	-0.225	0.366	1.003	0.957	-0.141				
ES07U1	1083					max	-0.240	0.500	0.169	
ES07U2	183	-0.377	0.338	1.053	0.923	-0.119				
ES07U2	183					max	-0.763	0.428	0.180	
ES07U3	88	-0.217	0.179	1.154	0.937	-0.204				
ES07U3	88					sad	-0.836	-2.960	0.004	
ES07U3	88					max	-0.847	0.326	0.193	
ES07U3	88					sad	0.124	3.976	0.001	

ES07U	1353									
ES07U Sig.		0.444	0.803				0.431	0.332		

ES08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31									
ES08U1	1128	-0.309	0.449	1.038	0.955	-0.066				
ES08U1	1128					max	-0.166	0.700	0.152	
ES08U2	199	-0.165	0.294	1.050	1.022	-0.289				
ES08U2	199					max	0.041	0.494	0.148	
ES08U3	82	-0.292	0.425	1.046	0.857	-0.001				
ES08U3	82					max	-0.833	0.763	0.153	

ES08U	1410									
ES08U Sig.		0.768	0.163				0.961	0.096		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
<hr/>										
ES09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
ES09U1	972	-0.212	0.525	1.021	0.923	-0.014				
ES09U1	972					max	-0.200	0.674	0.179	
ES09U2	165	-0.278	0.564	0.907	1.036	-0.092				
ES09U2	165					max	-0.077	1.072	0.167	
ES09U3	76	0.003	0.319	0.916	0.813	0.082				
ES09U3	76					max	0.769	0.051	0.293	
ES09U	1213									
ES09U Sig.		0.221	0.273				0.225	0.811		
<hr/>										
Finland										
FI05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
FI05U1	446	0.484	0.273	0.811	0.761	-0.023				
FI05U1	446					max	0.755	0.419	0.302	
FI05U2	438	0.433	0.175	0.833	0.701	0.042				
FI05U2	438					max	0.825	0.350	0.333	
FI05U3	468	0.488	0.094	0.851	0.732	0.036				
FI05U3	468					max	0.757	0.282	0.324	
FI05U	1352									
FI05U Sig.		0.022	0.175				0.011	0.624		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
FI06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
FI06U1	647	0.637	0.297	0.818	0.733	0.066				
FI06U1	647					sad	0.881	-2.813	0.001	
FI06U1	647					max	1.033	0.414	0.364	
FI06U2	588	0.483	0.141	0.835	0.715	0.117				
FI06U2	588					max	0.977	0.269	0.323	
FI06U3	823	0.478	0.109	0.824	0.715	0.083				
FI06U3	823					max	0.827	0.216	0.330	
		FI06U1			FI06U2			FI06U3		
FI06U	2058									
FI06U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005		
FI07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
FI07U1	632	0.551	0.319	0.870	0.821	0.095				
FI07U1	632						max	0.967	0.587	0.269
FI07U2	493	0.370	0.176	0.878	0.793	0.063				
FI07U2	493						min	0.835	-3.528	0.000
FI07U2	493						max	0.853	0.338	0.280
FI07U3	796	0.360	0.083	0.923	0.792	0.095				
FI07U3	796						max	0.840	0.262	0.271
		FI07U1			FI07U2			FI07U3		
FI07U	1922									
FI07U Sig.		0.593	0.595				0.796	0.150		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
FI08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
FI08U1	610	0.635	0.294	0.898	0.908	0.071			
FI08U1	610					max	1.065	0.504	0.261
FI08U2	464	0.549	0.141	0.908	0.753	0.121			
FI08U2	464					max	0.979	0.431	0.320
FI08U3	743	0.452	0.060	0.918	0.795	0.135			
FI08U3	743					max	0.978	0.243	0.287
FI08U	1817								
FI08U Sig.		0.004	0.638				<0.0005	0.309	
<hr/>									
FI09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
FI09U1	548	0.639	0.337	0.862	0.761	0.174			
FI09U1	548					max	1.118	0.581	0.413
FI09U2	439	0.535	0.142	0.855	0.798	0.199			
FI09U2	439					max	1.014	0.479	0.311
FI09U3	639	0.543	0.046	0.857	0.819	0.244			
FI09U3	639					max	1.031	0.390	0.298
FI09U	1626								
FI09U Sig.		0.005	0.507				<0.0005	0.511	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
FI10	2021-09-01–2022-01-14								
FI10U1	501	0.814	0.370	0.803	0.760	0.133			
FI10U1	501						max	1.285 0.707 0.385	
FI10U2	427	0.789	0.173	0.841	0.791	0.089			
FI10U2	427						max	1.276 0.312 0.331	
FI10U3	429	0.718	0.097	0.870	0.824	0.143			
FI10U3	429						sad	0.757 -4.104 0.000	
FI10U3	429						max	1.160 0.403 0.308	
FI10U3	429						sad	-2.480 1.173 0.003	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FI10U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FI10U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FI10U3</p> </div> </div>									
FI10U	1357								
FI10U Sig.		0.209	<0.0005				0.260	<0.0005	
FI11	2023-08-10–2024-01-25								
FI11U1	481	0.942	0.468	0.790	0.829	0.106			
FI11U1	481						max	1.226 0.819 0.333	
FI11U1	481						sad	-2.126 1.570 0.002	
FI11U2	438	0.768	0.361	0.802	0.794	0.175			
FI11U2	438						max	1.173 0.645 0.350	
FI11U3	515	0.746	0.265	0.814	0.810	0.206			
FI11U3	515						max	1.122 0.504 0.302	
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FI11U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FI11U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FI11U3</p> </div> </div>									
FI11U	1435								
FI11U Sig.		0.045	0.044				0.034	0.030	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
France									
FR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
FR05U1	426	0.068	-0.026	0.977	1.005	0.096			
FR05U1	426					max	0.271	0.226	0.158
FR05U1	426					sad	-2.064	2.698	0.005
FR05U2	305	0.002	-0.189	0.949	0.945	-0.064			
FR05U2	305					max	0.202	-0.172	0.188
FR05U3	883	0.042	-0.189	0.896	1.009	-0.026			
FR05U3	883					max	0.268	-0.102	0.157
FR05U	1614								
FR05U Sig.		0.035	0.327				0.019	0.107	
FR06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
FR06U1	491	0.106	0.187	0.970	0.916	-0.102			
FR06U1	491					max	0.559	0.330	0.186
FR06U2	391	0.001	-0.184	0.942	0.949	0.050			
FR06U2	391					max	0.262	-0.163	0.173
FR06U2	391					sad	-2.433	2.541	0.004
FR06U3	978	0.013	-0.256	0.886	0.956	0.154			
FR06U3	978					max	0.176	-0.136	0.185
FR06U	1860								
FR06U Sig.		0.132	<0.0005				0.017	<0.0005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

FR07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
FR07U1	456	0.017	0.190	0.970	1.033	0.026			
FR07U1	456					max	0.276	0.397	0.153
FR07U2	320	-0.072	-0.050	0.864	0.989	<0.0005			
FR07U2	320					max	0.153	0.241	0.169
FR07U3	951	-0.064	-0.138	0.919	0.963	0.103			
FR07U3	951					max	0.060	0.021	0.180
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FR07U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FR07U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FR07U3</p> </div> </div>									
FR07U	1726								
FR07U Sig.		0.261	<0.0005				0.001	<0.0005	

FR08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
FR08U1	440	-0.001	0.245	0.938	0.970	-0.004			
FR08U1	440					max	0.390	0.439	0.195
FR08U2	316	-0.026	-0.090	0.910	1.009	0.042			
FR08U2	316					max	0.615	0.180	0.185
FR08U3	1146	-0.158	-0.111	0.911	0.981	0.093			
FR08U3	1146					max	0.148	0.135	0.156
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FR08U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FR08U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>FR08U3</p> </div> </div>									
FR08U	1902								
FR08U Sig.		0.003	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Greece									
GR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
GR05U1	833	-0.640	-0.604	0.904	0.972	-0.079			
GR05U1	833					max	-1.067	-1.132	0.210
GR05U2	600	-0.767	-0.672	1.044	0.894	-0.152			
GR05U2	600					max	-1.331	-1.278	0.335
GR05U3	879	-0.633	-0.788	0.940	0.903	0.105			
GR05U3	879					max	-1.251	-1.371	0.254
GR05U	2312								
GR05U Sig.		0.438	0.103				0.009	0.399	
GR10	2021-11-21–2022-04-19								
GR10U1	867	0.284	-0.615	0.868	0.883	-0.172			
GR10U1	867					max	0.551	-0.582	0.181
GR10U2	600	0.162	-0.480	0.890	0.885	-0.099			
GR10U2	600					max	0.351	-0.248	0.185
GR10U3	896	0.326	-0.296	0.863	0.851	0.003			
GR10U3	896					sad	2.340	-2.760	0.004
GR10U3	896					sad	-1.769	-2.929	0.004
GR10U3	896					max	0.495	-0.162	0.250
GR10U	2363								
GR10U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
HR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
HR05U2	489	-0.868	0.374	0.913	1.037	-0.153			
HR05U2	489					max	-0.914	0.390	0.171
HR05U3	669	-0.675	0.045	1.055	1.020	-0.099			
HR05U3	669					max	-1.030	0.032	0.160
HR05U	1158								
HR05U Sig.		<0.0005	0.279						
HR09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
HR09U2	213	-0.829	0.004	0.982	1.144	-0.128			
HR09U2	213					max	-1.200	-0.280	0.118
HR09U3	259	-0.730	0.174	1.030	1.286	-0.151			
HR09U3	259					max	-1.233	-0.709	0.089
HR09U3	259					sad	-1.179	-0.328	0.089
HR09U3	259					max	-1.146	1.073	0.102
HR09U	472								
HR09U Sig.		0.004	0.424						

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
HR10	2021-05-05–2021-11-13									
HR10U1	221	-0.404	0.253	0.985	1.253	-0.170				
HR10U1	221						max	-0.534	0.928	0.110
HR10U2	312	-0.604	0.490	0.964	1.098	-0.103				
HR10U2	312						max	-0.258	0.706	0.124
HR10U3	790	-0.525	0.191	1.119	1.162	-0.158				
HR10U3	790						max	-0.848	0.327	0.109
		HR10U1			HR10U2			HR10U3		
HR10U	1322									
HR10U Sig.		0.442	0.049					0.463	0.026	
HR11	2023-06-24–2024-01-05									
HR11U1	274	-0.249	0.181	0.944	1.224	-0.200				
HR11U1	274						max	-0.301	0.608	0.102
HR11U2	321	-0.543	0.283	1.031	0.952	-0.021				
HR11U2	321						max	-0.683	0.517	0.170
HR11U3	714	-0.554	0.089	1.024	1.094	-0.095				
HR11U3	714						max	-0.715	0.036	0.128
		HR11U1			HR11U2			HR11U3		
HR11U	1309									
HR11U Sig.		<0.0005	0.222					<0.0005	0.394	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Hungary								
HU05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
HU05U2	124	0.075	-0.089	1.122	0.834	-0.073		
HU05U2	124						max	1.397 -0.096 0.152
HU05U2	124						sad	0.425 -0.009 0.133
HU05U2	124						max	-0.825 0.138 0.174
HU05U3	585	0.232	-0.322	1.053	0.876	-0.079		
HU05U3	585						max	0.188 -0.330 0.195
HU05U	709							
HU05U Sig.		0.740	0.895					
HU06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
HU06U2	203	0.119	-0.051	0.966	0.931	-0.167		
HU06U2	203						sad	1.949 -3.674 0.001
HU06U2	203						max	0.136 -0.063 0.181
HU06U2	203						sad	-1.253 3.575 0.002
HU06U3	761	0.033	-0.197	1.079	0.905	-0.208		
HU06U3	761						max	-0.172 -0.076 0.182
HU06U	964							
HU06U Sig.		0.025	0.408					

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

HU07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
HU07U2	171	0.025	-0.289	0.996	0.970	-0.176		
HU07U2	171						max	-0.521 -0.266 0.220
HU07U3	516	0.068	-0.311	1.026	0.875	-0.159		
HU07U3	516						sad	2.799 -3.236 0.002
HU07U3	516						min	0.740 -4.171 0.000
HU07U3	516						sad	-1.551 -3.363 0.001
HU07U3	516						max	0.054 -0.272 0.209
HU07U3	516						sad	1.508 2.913 0.001
HU07U3	516						min	-1.139 3.788 0.000

HU07U	687							
HU07U Sig.		0.387	0.769					

HU08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
HU08U2	86	0.375	-0.807	1.084	0.944	-0.218		
HU08U2	86						max	0.081 -0.736 0.141
HU08U3	578	0.117	-0.685	1.029	0.872	0.175		
HU08U3	578						max	0.218 -0.609 0.201

HU08U	664							
HU08U Sig.		0.031	0.231					

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

HU09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
HU09U1	219	0.653	-0.627	0.915	0.964	-0.252		
HU09U1	219						sad	3.865 -1.924 0.003
HU09U1	219						max	0.693 -0.392 0.223
HU09U1	219						sad	-2.027 -1.480 0.004
HU09U2	166	0.522	-0.289	0.817	0.926	-0.064		
HU09U2	166						sad	0.355 -4.981 0.000
HU09U2	166						max	0.652 -0.334 0.200
HU09U2	166						sad	0.038 3.392 0.004
HU09U3	831	0.567	-0.699	0.997	0.953	0.046		
HU09U3	831						max	0.932 -0.452 0.163

HU09U	1217							
HU09U Sig.		0.697	0.122				0.014	0.091

HU10	2021-06-10–2021-10-16							
HU10U1	284	0.657	-0.326	0.798	1.020	-0.269		
HU10U1	284						max	0.569 0.433 0.252
HU10U1	284						sad	-1.441 -1.993 0.006
HU10U2	245	0.654	-0.216	0.805	0.873	-0.262		
HU10U2	245						sad	1.573 -3.678 0.001
HU10U2	245						max	0.857 -0.240 0.262
HU10U2	245						sad	0.405 2.758 0.007
HU10U3	826	0.430	-0.545	0.976	0.948	-0.191		
HU10U3	826						max	0.685 -0.358 0.166

HU10U	1355							
HU10U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	0.003

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

HU11	2023-05-06–2023-11-07							
HU11U1	346	0.800	-0.384	0.863	1.355	-0.268		
HU11U1	346						max	0.826 0.413 0.110
HU11U2	259	0.442	-0.561	1.002	0.935	-0.167		
HU11U2	259						max	0.633 -0.576 0.178
HU11U2	259						sad	-2.309 -2.678 0.002
HU11U2	259						sad	2.350 2.436 0.001
HU11U3	1093	0.408	-0.634	0.985	1.045	-0.005		
HU11U3	1093						max	0.533 -0.520 0.137
HU11U	1699							
HU11U Sig.		<0.0005	0.001					<0.0005 <0.0005

Ireland								
IE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
IE09U1	495	0.236	0.794	1.042	0.901	0.016		
IE09U1	495						max	0.826 1.172 0.236
IE09U2	264	0.216	0.536	0.933	0.766	0.021		
IE09U2	264						max	0.762 0.816 0.255
IE09U3	984	0.209	0.391	1.001	0.921	0.017		
IE09U3	984						max	0.566 0.554 0.190
IE09U	1743							
IE09U Sig.		0.884	<0.0005					0.207 <0.0005

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
IE10	2021-11-23–2022-08-26								
IE10U1	408	0.244	0.888	1.110	0.885	0.100			
IE10U1	408					max	1.059	1.123	0.242
IE10U2	204	0.255	0.963	0.951	0.770	0.178			
IE10U2	204					max	0.928	1.211	0.300
IE10U3	734	0.391	0.563	1.096	0.886	-0.083			
IE10U3	734					max	1.007	0.711	0.227
IE10U	1346								
IE10U Sig.		0.054	<0.0005				0.039	<0.0005	
<hr/>									
IE11	2023-06-27–2024-01-03								
IE11U1	397	0.297	0.723	1.012	0.954	0.052			
IE11U1	397					max	0.644	1.273	0.243
IE11U2	165	0.414	0.482	0.954	0.878	-0.014			
IE11U2	165					max	0.907	0.754	0.224
IE11U3	1013	0.299	0.274	1.107	1.107	0.028			
IE11U3	1013					max	0.763	0.790	0.145
IE11U	1576								
IE11U Sig.		0.423	<0.0005				0.068	<0.0005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Italy								
IT06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
IT06U1	221	0.036	0.161	1.054	1.144	-0.038		
IT06U1	221						max	0.174 0.841 0.117
IT06U2	335	-0.306	0.195	1.020	1.053	0.063		
IT06U2	335						sad	2.652 -2.472 0.002
IT06U2	335						max	-0.349 0.383 0.133
IT06U3	147	-0.242	0.117	0.950	1.002	0.088		
IT06U3	147						max	0.144 0.368 0.169
IT06U3	147						sad	-3.696 1.550 0.003
IT06U	703							
IT06U Sig.		<0.0005	0.553					0.357 0.044
IT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
IT08U1	844	-0.288	-0.243	1.050	1.032	0.084		
IT08U1	844						max	-0.904 -0.792 0.143
IT08U2	845	-0.331	-0.266	0.964	1.020	0.132		
IT08U2	845						max	-0.766 -0.883 0.144
IT08U3	291	-0.375	-0.230	1.098	1.078	0.132		
IT08U3	291						max	0.524 0.157 0.084
IT08U3	291						sad	0.089 -0.094 0.082
IT08U3	291						max	-1.412 -1.195 0.178
IT08U	1979							
IT08U Sig.		0.059	0.002					0.171 0.057

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
IT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
IT09U2	2085	0.019	-0.162	0.993	1.084	0.057			
IT09U2	2085					max	0.123	-0.061 0.131	
IT09U	2085								
IT09U Sig.									
IT10	2021-10-28–2022-04-26								
IT10U2	2133	0.030	0.038	0.940	0.960	0.058			
IT10U2	2133					max	0.290	0.135 0.167	
IT10U	2133								
IT10U Sig.									

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Lithuania									
LT05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
LT05U1	322	-0.350	0.346	0.896	0.873	-0.022			
LT05U1	322					max	-0.512	0.243	0.190
LT05U2	372	-0.354	0.122	1.178	0.948	-0.074			
LT05U2	372					max	-1.040	-0.263	0.131
LT05U3	457	-0.376	0.166	1.054	0.936	-0.192			
LT05U3	457					max	-0.553	0.341	0.165
		LT05U1		LT05U2		LT05U3			
LT05U	1151								
LT05U Sig.		<0.0005	0.250				<0.0005	0.483	
LT06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
LT06U1	353	-0.307	0.100	1.122	0.871	-0.249			
LT06U1	353					max	-0.569	0.114	0.185
LT06U1	353					sad	-3.153	2.998	0.006
LT06U2	487	0.008	-0.099	0.891	0.890	-0.124			
LT06U2	487					max	0.023	-0.182	0.226
LT06U2	487					sad	0.905	3.310	0.002
LT06U3	482	-0.165	0.552	1.106	0.888	-0.068			
LT06U3	482					max	0.073	0.643	0.183
		LT06U1		LT06U2		LT06U3			
LT06U	1322								
LT06U Sig.		<0.0005	0.033				<0.0005	<0.0005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>								
LT07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
LT07U1	412	0.325	0.252	1.052	0.762	-0.212		
LT07U1	412						sad	2.355 -2.708 0.000
LT07U1	412						min	0.614 -3.073 0.000
LT07U1	412						max	0.466 0.349 0.281
LT07U2	592	0.220	0.007	1.008	0.836	-0.031		
LT07U2	592						max	0.292 0.001 0.209
LT07U2	592						sad	0.569 3.282 0.003
LT07U3	521	-0.230	0.316	1.144	0.786	-0.040		
LT07U3	521						sad	1.192 -2.802 0.001
LT07U3	521						max	-0.581 0.337 0.189
LT07U3	521						sad	-1.835 3.594 0.001
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>LT07U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>LT07U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>LT07U3</p> </div> </div>								
LT07U	1525							
LT07U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	0.425
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>								
LT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
LT08U1	371	0.473	-0.308	0.957	1.030	-0.025		
LT08U1	371						max	0.795 -0.124 0.144
LT08U2	598	0.272	0.110	0.794	0.902	0.184		
LT08U2	598						sad	-1.219 -3.323 0.002
LT08U2	598						max	0.198 0.162 0.233
LT08U3	519	0.358	0.175	1.023	0.756	0.056		
LT08U3	519						sad	1.471 -2.800 0.001
LT08U3	519						max	0.700 0.202 0.265
LT08U3	519						min	0.412 3.970 0.000
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>LT08U1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>LT08U2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>LT08U3</p> </div> </div>								
LT08U	1488							
LT08U Sig.		0.004	<0.0005				0.002	<0.0005

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
LT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
LT09U1	270	0.426	0.010	0.814	1.005	-0.033			
LT09U1	270					sad	0.183	-3.610	0.008
LT09U1	270					max	0.786	0.131	0.214
LT09U1	270					sad	-2.412	-0.309	0.007
LT09U2	376	0.176	0.106	0.832	0.832	0.043			
LT09U2	376					sad	-0.148	-3.265	0.002
LT09U2	376					max	0.210	0.172	0.278
LT09U3	427	-0.320	0.383	1.129	1.122	-0.272			
LT09U3	427					max	-0.711	0.250	0.110

LT09U	1073								
LT09U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005	
LT10	2021-07-01–2021-12-15								

LT10U1	382	0.491	0.197	0.929	0.901	0.237			
LT10U1	382					max	0.748	0.325	0.239
LT10U1	382					sad	-2.426	-1.658	0.003
LT10U2	319	0.330	0.218	0.985	0.886	0.092			
LT10U2	319					sad	1.034	-2.788	0.002
LT10U2	319					max	0.454	0.284	0.193
LT10U2	319					sad	-1.322	3.113	0.002
LT10U3	456	0.005	0.008	0.983	0.997	-0.004			
LT10U3	456					max	0.129	0.111	0.155

LT10U	1157							
LT10U Sig.		<0.0005	0.002				<0.0005	0.005

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

LT11	2023-09-08–2023-12-29							
LT11U1	408	0.180	0.070	0.880	0.895	-0.011		
LT11U1	408						max	0.299 0.118 0.232
LT11U1	408						min	-3.584 -0.779 0.000
LT11U1	408						sad	-2.354 1.934 0.004
LT11U2	254	0.224	0.229	0.903	0.748	-0.015		
LT11U2	254						sad	0.503 -3.453 0.001
LT11U2	254						max	0.605 0.305 0.291
LT11U3	353	0.189	0.015	1.060	0.932	-0.005		
LT11U3	353						sad	2.270 -3.311 0.002
LT11U3	353						max	0.471 0.189 0.174
LT11U	1014							
LT11U Sig.		<0.0005	0.024					<0.0005 0.009

Latvia								
LV09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
LV09U1	128	-0.353	0.447	0.935	1.009	-0.230		
LV09U1	128						max	0.447 0.438 0.171
LV09U3	468	-0.174	0.289	1.057	0.974	-0.172		
LV09U3	468						max	0.262 0.206 0.155
LV09U	596							
LV09U Sig.		<0.0005	0.210					<0.0005 0.108

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Macedonia										
MK10	2021-10-25–2022-03-07									
MK10U1	668	-0.179	-0.468	1.105	1.133	0.064				
MK10U1	668					max	-0.806	-1.217	0.122	
MK10U3	458	-0.102	0.001	1.051	1.055	-0.176				
MK10U3	458					max	0.035	-0.186	0.155	
MK10U3	458					sad	-2.733	3.613	0.005	
MK10U	1126									
MK10U Sig.		<0.0005	0.045				<0.0005	<0.0005		
Netherlands										
NL05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
NL05U1	1187	0.471	0.012	0.760	0.683	-0.004				
NL05U1	1187					sad	1.054	-2.957	0.002	
NL05U1	1187					max	0.785	0.140	0.449	
NL05U2	234	0.500	0.060	0.653	0.699	-0.083				
NL05U2	234					max	0.823	0.252	0.410	
NL05U3	151	0.375	-0.114	0.759	0.697	0.126				
NL05U3	151					max	0.579	-0.002	0.371	
NL05U3	151					sad	-2.012	-0.806	0.005	
NL05U	1572									
NL05U Sig.		0.246	0.046				0.022	0.141		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
NL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
NL06U1	1194	0.433	0.078	0.811	0.671	0.119		
NL06U1	1194						max	0.851 0.242 0.441
NL06U2	257	0.444	0.039	0.749	0.657	0.027		
NL06U2	257						sad	1.784 -2.095 0.004
NL06U2	257						max	0.795 0.253 0.525
NL06U2	257						sad	-1.474 1.764 0.002
NL06U3	146	0.416	0.047	0.724	0.652	0.147		
NL06U3	146						sad	0.791 -2.809 0.001
NL06U3	146						min	-0.597 -2.782 0.000
NL06U3	146						max	0.626 0.099 0.484
NL06U3	146						sad	-2.228 -1.267 0.003
<hr/>								
NL06U1								
NL06U2								
NL06U3								
NL06U	1597							
NL06U Sig.		0.008	0.004				0.006	0.054
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NL07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
NL07U1	1168	0.371	-0.030	0.881	0.713	0.056		
NL07U1	1168						min	-0.288 -3.227 0.001
NL07U1	1168						max	0.757 0.085 0.382
NL07U2	251	0.452	-0.122	0.844	0.678	0.064		
NL07U2	251						max	0.926 -0.007 0.378
NL07U3	149	0.334	-0.103	0.806	0.626	0.145		
NL07U3	149						max	0.819 -0.090 0.457
<hr/>								
NL07U1								
NL07U2								
NL07U3								
NL07U	1569							
NL07U Sig.		0.322	0.106				0.337	0.191

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
NL08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
NL08U1	1049	0.448	-0.026	0.781	0.690	0.158		
NL08U1	1049						max	0.796 0.117 0.413
NL08U2	228	0.360	0.005	0.847	0.659	0.129		
NL08U2	228						sad	-1.340 -2.181 0.007
NL08U2	228						max	0.790 0.151 0.471
NL08U3	132	0.365	-0.033	0.803	0.574	0.057		
NL08U3	132						sad	0.441 -2.780 0.002
NL08U3	132						max	0.787 0.083 0.524
<hr/>								
NL08U	1408							
NL08U Sig.		0.005	0.320				0.183	0.737
<hr/>								
NL09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
NL09U1	1023	0.595	0.045	0.772	0.683	0.132		
NL09U1	1023						sad	0.211 -2.806 0.003
NL09U1	1023						max	0.941 0.187 0.445
NL09U2	240	0.598	-0.005	0.754	0.616	0.136		
NL09U2	240						max	0.945 0.028 0.524
NL09U2	240						sad	-1.171 -1.539 0.007
NL09U3	135	0.510	-0.027	0.793	0.604	0.131		
NL09U3	135						sad	0.200 -3.074 0.003
NL09U3	135						max	1.024 0.172 0.613
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NL09U	1398							
NL09U Sig.		0.221	0.589				0.872	0.973

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NL10	2021-10-02–2022-04-03							
NL10U1	865	0.561	0.192	0.811	0.659	0.060		
NL10U1	865						max	0.886 0.329 0.432
NL10U2	207	0.651	0.183	0.788	0.623	0.002		
NL10U2	207						sad	-0.849 -2.071 0.008
NL10U2	207						max	1.058 0.193 0.487
NL10U3	119	0.357	0.001	0.860	0.760	0.100		
NL10U3	119						max	0.979 0.070 0.357
NL10U	1191							
NL10U Sig.		0.007	0.013					0.057 0.098

NL11	2023-04-02–2023-11-07							
NL11U1	1026	0.495	0.128	0.853	0.695	0.111		
NL11U1	1026						max	0.883 0.232 0.399
NL11U2	235	0.556	0.154	0.829	0.626	0.180		
NL11U2	235						max	1.003 0.358 0.527
NL11U3	147	0.467	-0.046	0.872	0.766	0.116		
NL11U3	147						sad	1.446 -2.228 0.010
NL11U3	147						max	0.980 0.177 0.358
NL11U	1408							
NL11U Sig.		0.223	0.067					0.311 0.039

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Norway										
NO05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
NO05U1	301	0.578	0.200	0.743	0.726	-0.004				
NO05U1	301					sad	1.040	-2.830	0.003	
NO05U1	301					max	0.834	0.355	0.368	
NO05U2	512	0.507	-0.031	0.783	0.815	0.215				
NO05U2	512					max	0.719	0.220	0.276	
NO05U3	472	0.513	-0.069	0.832	0.760	0.102				
NO05U3	472					max	0.691	-0.072	0.312	
NO05U3	472					sad	-2.024	1.631	0.002	
NO05U	1285									
NO05U Sig.		0.426	<0.0005				0.336	<0.0005		
NO06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
NO06U1	331	0.582	0.204	0.712	0.818	0.047				
NO06U1	331						max	0.768	0.402	0.276
NO06U2	537	0.524	0.159	0.791	0.786	0.022				
NO06U2	537						max	0.709	0.284	0.298
NO06U3	534	0.499	0.001	0.751	0.791	0.087				
NO06U3	534						max	0.677	0.126	0.261
NO06U	1402									
NO06U Sig.		0.286	<0.0005				0.012	0.005		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NO07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
NO07U1	298	0.722	0.087	0.791	0.826	-0.050		
NO07U1	298						max	0.932 0.167 0.290
NO07U2	485	0.592	-0.025	0.833	0.804	0.121		
NO07U2	485						max	0.750 0.120 0.276
NO07U2	485						min	-3.579 -0.001 0.001
NO07U3	472	0.606	-0.123	0.789	0.837	0.133		
NO07U3	472						max	0.905 0.036 0.254
NO07U	1256							
NO07U Sig.		<0.0005	0.800					<0.0005 0.098

NO08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
NO08U1	308	0.823	0.174	0.753	0.862	-0.012		
NO08U1	308						max	1.131 0.416 0.301
NO08U2	502	0.661	-0.061	0.814	0.880	0.126		
NO08U2	502						max	0.981 0.188 0.254
NO08U3	486	0.702	-0.096	0.746	0.818	0.126		
NO08U3	486						max	0.964 0.205 0.278
NO08U	1296							
NO08U Sig.		<0.0005	0.994					<0.0005 0.612

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
NO09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
NO09U1	282	0.782	0.276	0.812	0.812	0.073			
NO09U1	282					max	1.145	0.619	0.328
NO09U2	435	0.759	0.128	0.799	0.753	0.120			
NO09U2	435					max	1.010	0.268	0.343
NO09U3	350	0.611	0.071	0.858	0.853	0.189			
NO09U3	350					max	1.036	0.114	0.230
NO09U	1067								
NO09U Sig.		0.008	<0.0005				0.001	0.009	
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NO10	2021-06-24–2022-04-27								
NO10U1	177	0.961	0.356	0.768	0.752	-0.014			
NO10U1	177					max	1.191	0.453	0.303
NO10U2	198	0.881	0.249	0.783	0.777	0.069			
NO10U2	198					max	1.138	0.453	0.287
NO10U2	198					sad	-2.196	1.014	0.004
NO10U3	735	0.780	0.208	0.851	0.825	0.227			
NO10U3	735					max	1.154	0.431	0.300
NO10U	1110								
NO10U Sig.		0.219	0.116				0.098	0.012	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

NO11	2023-04-20–2023-11-30								
NO11U1	378	0.870	0.413	0.859	0.801	0.092			
NO11U1	378					max	1.212	0.612	0.321
NO11U2	421	0.777	0.293	0.847	0.693	0.110			
NO11U2	421					max	1.069	0.358	0.367
NO11U3	340	0.843	0.305	0.867	0.763	0.198			
NO11U3	340					max	1.284	0.562	0.338
NO11U	1139								
NO11U Sig.		0.050	0.633				0.156	0.368	

Poland									
PL05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
PL05U1	146	-0.282	0.654	0.916	0.865	-0.110			
PL05U1	146					sad	2.470	-1.724	0.002
PL05U1	146					max	-0.151	0.829	0.255
PL05U1	146					sad	-3.070	3.154	0.003
PL05U2	326	-0.129	0.729	0.955	0.778	-0.110			
PL05U2	326					max	0.051	0.917	0.255
PL05U3	544	-0.243	0.540	0.953	0.797	-0.152			
PL05U3	544					sad	-0.099	-3.008	0.001
PL05U3	544					max	-0.535	0.555	0.226
PL05U3	544					sad	-1.796	4.030	0.001
PL05U	1016								
PL05U Sig.		0.147	0.003				0.330	0.002	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
PL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
PL06U1	176	-0.477	0.898	0.951	0.912	-0.273				
PL06U1	176					sad	3.300	-0.878	0.002	
PL06U1	176					max	-0.319	1.239	0.197	
PL06U1	176					sad	-4.041	2.736	0.002	
PL06U2	383	-0.288	0.814	0.898	0.872	-0.174				
PL06U2	383					max	-0.147	1.092	0.220	
PL06U3	553	-0.507	0.677	0.976	0.929	-0.147				
PL06U3	553					max	-0.772	0.798	0.173	
PL06U	1112									
PL06U Sig.		0.305	<0.0005				0.809	0.001		
PL07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
PL07U1	150	-0.618	0.562	0.973	0.850	-0.015				
PL07U1	150						max	-0.810	0.795	0.246
PL07U2	347	-0.537	0.498	0.922	0.864	-0.054				
PL07U2	347						max	-0.733	0.455	0.198
PL07U3	480	-0.601	0.415	0.987	0.861	-0.002				
PL07U3	480						sad	-1.886	-2.894	0.003
PL07U3	480						max	-0.860	0.448	0.202
PL07U	978									
PL07U Sig.		0.558	0.135				0.521	0.003		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
PL08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31									
PL08U1	138	-0.328	0.380	0.916	0.960	-0.280				
PL08U1	138					sad	-2.380	-1.429	0.006	
PL08U1	138					max	-0.426	0.942	0.221	
PL08U2	334	-0.327	0.441	0.931	0.956	-0.153				
PL08U2	334					max	-0.748	0.804	0.171	
PL08U3	478	-0.402	0.284	0.892	0.939	-0.228				
PL08U3	478					sad	0.538	-3.738	0.000	
PL08U3	478					max	-0.511	0.294	0.199	
PL08U3	478					sad	-0.374	3.797	0.002	
PL08U	950									
PL08U Sig.		0.453	0.065				0.432	0.027		
PL09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
PL09U1	123	0.116	0.194	0.873	1.088	-0.481				
PL09U1	123						max	0.307	0.500	0.185
PL09U2	310	-0.224	0.582	0.879	0.944	-0.054				
PL09U2	310						sad	0.789	-3.446	0.001
PL09U2	310						max	-0.137	0.607	0.205
PL09U2	310						sad	-4.348	0.766	0.001
PL09U3	438	-0.059	0.415	0.886	0.974	-0.132				
PL09U3	438						max	0.090	0.536	0.179
PL09U	871									
PL09U Sig.		0.947	0.008				0.658	0.528		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Portugal								
PT05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
PT05U1	426	-0.396	0.174	0.993	0.861	-0.153		
PT05U1	426						sad	-1.849 -2.972 0.001
PT05U1	426						max	-0.426 0.119 0.207
PT05U1	426						sad	-1.151 4.254 0.000
PT05U2	611	-0.272	0.060	0.874	0.716	-0.085		
PT05U2	611						max	-0.173 0.008 0.262
PT05U3	523	-0.384	0.035	1.013	0.705	-0.243		
PT05U3	523						sad	-1.440 -2.226 0.004
PT05U3	523						max	0.135 0.082 0.288
PT05U	1560							
PT05U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				0.074	0.078
PT06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
PT06U1	448	-0.587	0.068	0.921	0.977	-0.049		
PT06U1	448						max	-0.851 0.005 0.164
PT06U2	608	-0.504	-0.022	0.903	0.871	-0.172		
PT06U2	608						max	-0.737 -0.146 0.257
PT06U2	608						sad	-2.509 2.931 0.003
PT06U3	614	-0.307	-0.138	0.876	0.776	-0.111		
PT06U3	614						max	-0.124 -0.216 0.277
PT06U	1670							
PT06U Sig.		<0.0005	0.001				<0.0005	<0.0005

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

PT07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
PT07U1	310	-0.303	0.328	1.006	0.995	-0.100		
PT07U1	310						max	-0.363 0.353 0.145
PT07U2	398	-0.227	-0.013	0.971	0.880	-0.128		
PT07U2	398						sad	0.022 -2.937 0.003
PT07U2	398						max	-0.075 0.046 0.245
PT07U2	398						sad	-2.473 2.873 0.003
PT07U3	362	-0.411	0.098	1.067	0.943	-0.025		
PT07U3	362						max	-0.761 0.145 0.165

PT07U	1070							
PT07U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				0.009	0.007

PT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
PT08U1	329	-0.076	0.353	0.965	0.764	-0.160		
PT08U1	329						max	0.117 0.408 0.253
PT08U2	390	-0.115	0.299	1.002	0.825	-0.028		
PT08U2	390						sad	-1.525 -2.506 0.003
PT08U2	390						max	-0.010 0.227 0.224
PT08U2	390						sad	0.372 3.605 0.001
PT08U3	382	-0.356	0.247	1.041	0.851	-0.120		
PT08U3	382						max	-0.637 0.239 0.164

PT08U	1102							
PT08U Sig.		1.000	0.079				0.462	0.077

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

PT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
PT09U1	236	0.042	0.597	0.939	0.792	-0.068		
PT09U1	236						max	0.513 0.648 0.239
PT09U2	297	-0.075	0.346	0.993	0.798	-0.152		
PT09U2	297						sad	-1.416 -2.090 0.003
PT09U2	297						max	0.009 0.333 0.248
PT09U2	297						sad	1.423 2.775 0.003
PT09U3	292	-0.088	0.544	0.989	0.809	-0.015		
PT09U3	292						max	0.045 0.490 0.223
PT09U	826							
PT09U Sig.		0.258	0.001				0.216	0.070

PT10	2021-08-17–2022-03-04							
PT10U1	404	0.193	0.512	0.905	0.792	-0.103		
PT10U1	404						sad	0.436 -2.713 0.002
PT10U1	404						max	0.561 0.530 0.252
PT10U1	404						sad	-0.678 4.382 0.000
PT10U2	507	0.007	0.521	1.036	0.750	-0.130		
PT10U2	507						max	0.331 0.556 0.279
PT10U2	507						sad	-2.868 2.400 0.009
PT10U3	479	0.012	0.472	0.913	0.823	-0.001		
PT10U3	479						max	0.232 0.628 0.233
PT10U	1390							
PT10U Sig.		0.005	0.585				0.032	0.060

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Sweden								
SE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
SE05U1	602	0.550	0.446	0.803	0.865	0.023		
SE05U1	602						max	0.857 0.691 0.268
SE05U2	217	0.586	0.393	0.766	0.753	0.194		
SE05U2	217						max	0.970 0.825 0.291
SE05U3	312	0.536	0.324	0.831	0.823	0.100		
SE05U3	312						max	0.815 0.749 0.266
SE05U3	312						sad	-2.480 1.584 0.001
SE05U	1131							
SE05U Sig.		0.816	0.446					0.562 0.802
SE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
SE06U1	813	0.466	0.389	0.882	0.885	-0.053		
SE06U1	813						max	0.714 0.633 0.232
SE06U1	813						sad	-3.057 1.940 0.002
SE06U2	321	0.392	0.258	0.854	0.840	0.035		
SE06U2	321						max	0.739 0.457 0.237
SE06U3	410	0.369	0.315	0.890	0.839	0.028		
SE06U3	410						max	0.669 0.413 0.241
SE06U	1544							
SE06U Sig.		0.032	0.012					0.021 0.357

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
SE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
SE07U1	754	0.617	0.419	0.851	0.817	-0.004			
SE07U1	754						max	0.774 0.620 0.261	
SE07U1	754						sad	-2.399 -1.157 0.002	
SE07U1	754						min	-2.991 0.627 0.001	
SE07U1	754						sad	-2.286 2.163 0.002	
SE07U2	278	0.594	0.403	0.869	0.839	0.228			
SE07U2	278						max	1.078 0.705 0.313	
SE07U3	403	0.497	0.340	0.898	0.838	0.108			
SE07U3	403						max	0.958 0.866 0.233	
SE07U	1436								
SE07U Sig.		0.108	0.383					0.135 0.453	
SE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
SE08U1	663	0.507	0.368	0.812	0.866	0.182			
SE08U1	663						max	0.956 0.660 0.282	
SE08U2	153	0.619	0.450	0.748	0.811	0.134			
SE08U2	153						max	1.303 -0.132 0.206	
SE08U2	153						sad	1.125 0.337 0.193	
SE08U2	153						sad	0.224 -0.351 0.107	
SE08U2	153						max	-0.614 -0.970 0.174	
SE08U2	153						max	0.985 1.283 0.286	
SE08U3	427	0.483	0.229	0.843	0.902	0.241			
SE08U3	427						max	0.887 0.505 0.241	
SE08U	1242								
SE08U Sig.		0.204	0.007					0.261 0.005	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

SE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
SE09U1	498	0.587	0.381	0.821	0.893	0.096			
SE09U1	498					max	1.012	0.778	0.254
SE09U2	533	0.572	0.390	0.853	0.856	0.125			
SE09U2	533					max	1.010	0.734	0.271
SE09U3	262	0.584	0.264	0.770	0.830	0.135			
SE09U3	262					max	0.827	0.488	0.265
SE09U	1293								
SE09U Sig.		0.954	0.127				0.717	0.017	

Slovenia									
SI05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
SI05U1	241	-0.385	0.324	1.040	0.889	-0.021			
SI05U1	241					max	-0.718	0.366	0.180
SI05U3	789	-0.546	-0.116	0.988	0.876	-0.009			
SI05U3	789					max	-0.813	-0.186	0.182
SI05U	1030								
SI05U Sig.		0.452	0.159				0.357	0.152	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
SI06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
SI06U1	224	-0.631	0.406	0.948	0.833	-0.202			
SI06U1	224					max	-0.040	0.343	0.189
SI06U3	688	-0.389	0.164	0.995	0.921	-0.057			
SI06U3	688					max	-0.371	0.276	0.160
		SI06U1			SI06U3				
SI06U	912								
SI06U Sig.		<0.0005	0.980				0.006	0.368	
SI07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
SI07U1	251	-0.588	0.227	0.934	0.931	0.120			
SI07U1	251					max	-0.040	0.395	0.180
SI07U3	611	-0.514	0.026	0.913	0.849	0.051			
SI07U3	611					max	-0.906	0.015	0.212
		SI07U1			SI07U3				
SI07U	862								
SI07U Sig.		0.287	0.002				0.436	0.008	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>									
SI08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
SI08U1	268	-0.383	0.090	0.891	0.882	-0.073			
SI08U1	268					max	-0.486	0.125	0.188
SI08U3	831	-0.341	-0.206	0.971	0.939	0.010			
SI08U3	831					max	-0.433	-0.238	0.174
SI08U	1099								
SI08U Sig.		0.761	0.058				0.240	0.062	
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>									
SI09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
SI09U1	255	-0.418	0.053	0.986	0.887	0.058			
SI09U1	255					max	-0.103	0.372	0.171
SI09U3	764	-0.363	-0.250	1.022	0.972	0.011			
SI09U3	764					max	-0.446	-0.362	0.148
SI09U	1019								
SI09U Sig.		0.073	0.274				0.157	0.325	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
SI10	2020-09-18–2021-08-24								
SI10U1	264	-0.165	0.194	0.992	1.001	-0.151			
SI10U1	264						max	-0.022 0.313 0.148	
SI10U3	766	-0.258	-0.030	1.009	0.961	-0.054			
SI10U3	766						min	0.198 -4.604 0.000	
SI10U3	766						max	-0.206 -0.010 0.158	
SI10U	1030								
SI10U Sig.		0.161	0.205					0.464 0.201	
SI11	2023-03-21–2023-08-14								
SI11U1	202	-0.079	0.320	1.064	0.893	-0.049			
SI11U1	202						max	0.690 0.512 0.161	
SI11U3	737	0.001	0.018	1.015	0.895	0.039			
SI11U3	737						max	0.521 0.114 0.180	
SI11U	938								
SI11U Sig.		0.737	0.080					0.890 0.025	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Slovakia										
SK05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
SK05U1	184	-0.143	-0.067	0.947	0.931	-0.361				
SK05U1	184					sad	2.661	1.257	0.003	
SK05U1	184					max	-0.242	0.146	0.192	
SK05U1	184					sad	-2.500	-1.224	0.009	
SK05U3	1277	-0.135	0.046	1.012	0.869	-0.271				
SK05U3	1277					min	0.090	-4.027	0.000	
SK05U3	1277					max	-0.126	0.067	0.216	
SK05U	1460									
SK05U Sig.		0.922	0.104				0.537	0.138		
SK06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
SK06U1	214	-0.450	-0.246	1.056	1.061	-0.432				
SK06U1	214						max	-1.034	0.469	0.147
SK06U3	1289	-0.428	-0.067	1.054	0.948	-0.076				
SK06U3	1289						sad	-1.978	-3.266	0.004
SK06U3	1289						max	-0.763	0.015	0.187
SK06U	1503									
SK06U Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005		

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
SK09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
SK09U1	104	-0.085	-0.428	1.134	0.970	0.047			
SK09U1	104					sad	3.586	-0.482	0.009
SK09U1	104					max	-0.659	-1.281	0.327
SK09U1	104					sad	0.155	-0.002	0.073
SK09U1	104					max	0.410	0.681	0.090
SK09U1	104					sad	-2.225	2.648	0.012
SK09U3	822	0.095	-0.460	1.303	1.001	-0.315			
SK09U3	822					max	-0.191	-0.426	0.131
SK09U	926								
SK09U Sig.		0.409	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005	
SK10	2021-05-26–2021-10-31								
SK10U1	122	-0.212	0.254	0.944	1.045	0.039			
SK10U1	122					sad	2.016	-1.901	0.008
SK10U1	122					max	0.386	0.967	0.145
SK10U1	122					sad	-0.191	0.794	0.141
SK10U1	122					max	-0.737	0.551	0.145
SK10U3	927	-0.032	-0.390	1.121	0.976	0.083			
SK10U3	927					max	-0.565	-0.551	0.146
SK10U	1049								
SK10U Sig.		0.018	0.360				0.002	0.440	

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Table 2: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Urbanisation (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
SK11	2023-09-10–2023-12-11								
SK11U1	104	0.545	-0.627	0.917	0.868	0.019			
SK11U1	104					sad	3.552	-1.213	0.005
SK11U1	104					max	0.078	-1.341	0.268
SK11U1	104					sad	-2.307	0.379	0.002
SK11U1	104					sad	-0.438	2.488	0.004
SK11U1	104					min	-1.770	1.742	0.001
SK11U3	1036	0.206	-0.591	1.146	1.034	0.053			
SK11U3	1036					max	-0.267	-0.991	0.127

SK11U1

SK11U3

SK11U	1140						
SK11U Sig.		0.004	0.733			<0.0005	0.060

3 Results from the European Social Survey: Distributions of the Trust and Immigration Factors in Selected European Countries and Different Degrees of Regional Purchase Power

The first two characters of the region code code for the country, the next two for the ESS wave. Degrees of purchase power are coded in the last character of the region code. The purchase power in NUTS-3 regions were taken from [?], weighted with the NUTS-3 population and assigned to the regions used in the ESS. These were then recoded in three groups of approximately equal size within each country, such that group 1 contains the regions with the lowest purchase power (< 0.87 of the country mean) and group 3 contains the regions with the highest purchase power (≥ 1.09 of the country mean).

The diagrams show the estimated two-dimensional distributions of the two factors — truth in political institutions is the horizontal dimension, sympathy for immigrants is the vertical dimension. x_m and y_m are the coordinates of maxima or addles of the bimodal distributions. $f(x_m, y_m)$ is the value of the distribution function at such a point.

Table rows starting with P contain the significance level of the mean differences (in columns $\mu(x)$ and $\mu(y)$) and the significance yielded by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test between the one-dimensional distributions in purchase power classes 1 and 3 (in columns mode(x) and mode(y)). If the significance level is below 0.05, the entry is marked in yellow. The numbers of respondents (weighted countrywise) interviewed within the respective region groups can be found in the middle of these rows.

Table 3: Parameters of two-dimensional distributions of Trust and Immigration factors — Purchase Power

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Albania								
AL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
AL06P1	371	0.447	0.789	1.118	1.068	-0.102		
AL06P1	371						max	0.451 1.083 0.131
AL06P2	253	0.070	0.570	1.084	1.165	0.056		
AL06P2	253						max	0.299 1.340 0.100
AL06P3	248	0.066	0.926	1.052	0.973	0.056		
AL06P3	248						max	0.174 1.097 0.168
AL06P	871							
AL06P Sig.		0.004	0.369				0.001	0.138

AL06P1

AL06P2

AL06P3

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Austria									
AT07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
AT07P1	413	-0.041	-0.387	1.116	0.931	0.091			
AT07P1	413					max	0.088	-0.075	0.158
AT07P2	440	-0.026	-0.386	1.202	0.954	0.174			
AT07P2	440					max	0.460	-0.072	0.134
AT07P3	620	-0.051	0.057	1.077	0.926	0.099			
AT07P3	620					max	-0.221	0.034	0.177
AT07P	1473								
AT07P Sig.		0.132	0.002				0.476	0.005	
AT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
AT08P1	461	0.082	-0.602	0.960	0.953	0.298			
AT08P1	461					max	0.023	-0.568	0.175
AT08P2	505	0.004	-0.478	1.142	1.038	0.230			
AT08P2	505					max	-0.247	-0.639	0.128
AT08P3	715	0.026	-0.150	1.086	1.001	0.004			
AT08P3	715					max	-0.101	-0.050	0.155
AT08P	1681								
AT08P Sig.		<0.0005	0.139				0.001	0.047	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

AT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
AT09P1	459	0.326	-0.467	0.901	0.981	0.082		
AT09P1	459						max	0.446 -0.500 0.186
AT09P1	459						sad	-2.207 1.989 0.003
AT09P2	333	0.260	-0.322	1.077	1.056	0.076		
AT09P2	333						max	0.441 -0.097 0.131
AT09P3	1285	0.098	-0.121	0.992	1.086	0.105		
AT09P3	1285						max	0.477 0.308 0.138
AT09P	2077							
AT09P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005

AT11	2023-06-13–2023-12-03							
AT11P1	604	0.138	-0.276	1.051	0.778	0.124		
AT11P1	604						min	1.708 -2.904 0.000
AT11P1	604						sad	3.679 -0.823 0.004
AT11P1	604						sad	-1.322 -2.590 0.007
AT11P1	604						max	0.041 -0.224 0.321
AT11P1	604						min	0.636 2.980 0.000
AT11P1	604						sad	-2.332 1.802 0.001
AT11P2	598	0.031	-0.118	1.047	1.043	0.197		
AT11P2	598						max	0.229 0.057 0.127
AT11P3	802	0.185	0.083	1.067	0.950	0.099		
AT11P3	802						sad	2.611 -2.849 0.001
AT11P3	802						max	0.577 0.308 0.170
AT11P3	802						sad	-2.647 2.588 0.002
AT11P	2004							
AT11P Sig.		<0.0005	0.076				0.006	0.012

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Belgium										
BE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
BE05P1	451	0.038	-0.144	0.969	0.807	0.158				
BE05P1	451					max	0.302	0.016	0.261	
BE05P1	451					sad	-2.328	1.682	0.005	
BE05P2	381	-0.048	-0.104	0.965	0.760	0.085				
BE05P2	381					sad	1.074	-2.864	0.003	
BE05P2	381					max	0.556	0.266	0.306	
BE05P3	634	0.062	-0.069	0.973	0.798	0.034				
BE05P3	634					max	0.448	0.072	0.250	
BE05P	1467									
BE05P Sig.		0.207	0.307				0.515	0.201		
BE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
BE06P1	518	0.082	-0.253	1.023	0.890	0.051				
BE06P1	518					max	0.571	0.112	0.215	
BE06P1	518					sad	-2.313	2.302	0.003	
BE06P2	427	0.146	-0.134	0.924	0.706	0.121				
BE06P2	427					max	0.607	-0.017	0.322	
BE06P3	700	0.262	0.001	0.940	0.753	0.135				
BE06P3	700					max	0.682	0.227	0.321	
BE06P	1645									
BE06P Sig.		0.918	0.121				0.673	0.959		

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

BE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
BE07P1	499	-0.061	-0.283	1.026	0.903	0.132		
BE07P1	499						max	0.429 0.033 0.190
BE07P2	431	0.113	-0.227	1.036	0.788	0.122		
BE07P2	431						sad	0.361 -4.060 0.001
BE07P2	431						max	0.832 0.029 0.292
BE07P3	629	0.234	0.042	0.964	0.778	0.125		
BE07P3	629						max	0.580 0.286 0.280
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE07P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE07P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE07P3</p> </div> </div>								
BE07P	1558							
BE07P Sig.		0.001	<0.0005					0.006 <0.0005

BE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
BE08P1	480	-0.117	-0.062	0.976	0.846	0.089		
BE08P1	480						max	0.375 0.083 0.222
BE08P2	451	0.058	-0.168	1.000	0.784	0.134		
BE08P2	451						max	0.646 0.114 0.277
BE08P3	653	0.179	0.199	0.960	0.775	-0.005		
BE08P3	653						sad	-0.163 -3.751 0.001
BE08P3	653						max	0.725 0.343 0.323
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE08P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE08P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE08P3</p> </div> </div>								
BE08P	1585							
BE08P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					<0.0005 <0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

BE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
BE09P1	470	0.012	0.007	0.905	0.855	0.035		
BE09P1	470						sad	0.115 -3.432 0.002
BE09P1	470						max	0.259 0.114 0.258
BE09P1	470						sad	-3.101 -1.895 0.003
BE09P2	398	0.171	-0.029	0.944	0.775	0.207		
BE09P2	398						max	0.669 0.177 0.292
BE09P3	656	0.250	0.251	0.904	0.755	0.046		
BE09P3	656						sad	0.348 -3.198 0.001
BE09P3	656						max	0.787 0.426 0.372

BE09P	1525							
BE09P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005

BE10	2021-10-28–2022-09-02							
BE10P1	338	0.034	0.083	1.033	0.852	0.134		
BE10P1	338						max	0.695 0.353 0.211
BE10P1	338						sad	-2.629 2.245 0.003
BE10P2	302	0.126	0.128	0.958	0.749	0.169		
BE10P2	302						max	0.803 0.311 0.318
BE10P3	477	0.138	0.382	0.985	0.729	-0.011		
BE10P3	477						max	0.600 0.481 0.268

BE10P	1117							
BE10P Sig.		0.005	0.169				0.003	0.034

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N		$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Bulgaria										
BG05	2010-01-01-2011-12-31									
BG05P1	752	-0.260	0.636	1.102	1.014	-0.165				
BG05P1	752						max	-0.317	0.715	0.158
BG05P2	189	-0.138	0.427	1.036	1.041	-0.047				
BG05P2	189						max	0.211	0.561	0.164
BG05P2	189						sad	-3.435	2.446	0.004
BG05P3	377	-0.395	0.604	1.017	0.993	-0.185				
BG05P3	377						max	-0.743	0.630	0.164
BG05P	1318									
BG05P Sig.		0.224	0.213				0.251	0.158		
BG06	2012-01-01-2013-12-31									
BG06P1	708	-0.509	0.566	1.153	1.157	-0.105				
BG06P1	708						max	-0.838	0.580	0.117
BG06P2	165	-0.407	0.516	0.969	0.756	-0.029				
BG06P2	165						sad	-1.832	-2.087	0.006
BG06P2	165						max	-0.038	0.607	0.261
BG06P3	378	-0.256	0.254	0.889	0.842	-0.235				
BG06P3	378						max	0.047	0.046	0.246
BG06P3	378						sad	-1.943	-1.812	0.005
BG06P3	378						sad	0.244	3.222	0.003
BG06P	1251									
BG06P Sig.		0.175	0.011				0.004	0.026		

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

BG09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
BG09P1	627	-0.368	-0.004	1.183	1.108	-0.074		
BG09P1	627						max	-0.808 -0.274 0.130
BG09P2	125	-0.829	0.330	0.944	0.959	-0.257		
BG09P2	125						max	0.334 0.205 0.118
BG09P2	125						sad	-0.295 0.416 0.108
BG09P2	125						max	-1.609 0.536 0.209
BG09P3	272	-0.736	-0.455	0.826	1.039	-0.126		
BG09P3	272						sad	-0.425 -0.813 0.105
BG09P3	272						max	0.107 -0.133 0.137
BG09P3	272						max	-1.459 -1.444 0.218

BG09P1								
BG09P2								
BG09P3								
BG09P	1024							
BG09P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					<0.0005 <0.0005

BG10	2021-06-28–2021-09-30							
BG10P1	1513	-0.393	0.131	1.032	1.092	-0.019		
BG10P1	1513						max	-0.565 0.153 0.120
BG10P2	292	-0.699	0.401	0.754	0.815	-0.118		
BG10P2	292						sad	-0.243 -2.612 0.006
BG10P2	292						max	-0.990 0.719 0.288
BG10P3	333	-0.424	0.153	1.122	1.218	-0.047		
BG10P3	333						max	-0.911 -0.073 0.104

BG10P1								
BG10P2								
BG10P3								
BG10P	2138							
BG10P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					<0.0005 <0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Switzerland								
CH05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
CH05P2	786	0.245	0.090	0.918	0.831	-0.068		
CH05P2	786						max	0.530 0.203 0.242
CH05P3	347	0.342	0.054	0.858	0.789	-0.155		
CH05P3	347						sad	1.883 -3.015 0.002
CH05P3	347						max	0.610 0.119 0.278
CH05P3	347						sad	-0.602 3.637 0.000
CH05P	1133	"						
CH05P Sig.		0.020	0.100					
CH06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
CH06P2	816	0.349	0.013	0.852	0.807	-0.040		
CH06P2	816						max	0.714 0.124 0.272
CH06P3	352	0.346	-0.056	0.807	0.755	0.014		
CH06P3	352						max	0.583 0.009 0.296
CH06P	1168	"						
CH06P Sig.		0.099	0.080					

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
CH07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
CH07P2	863	0.322	0.002	0.854	0.783	0.007			
CH07P2	863					max	0.576	0.129	0.286
CH07P3	359	0.379	0.028	0.792	0.793	-0.046			
CH07P3	359					max	0.550	0.091	0.280
CH07P	1222								
CH07P Sig.		0.278	0.596						
CH08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
CH08P2	843	0.335	-0.020	0.872	0.809	0.015			
CH08P2	843					max	0.578	0.105	0.262
CH08P3	371	0.391	-0.089	0.860	0.883	-0.034			
CH08P3	371					max	0.582	0.075	0.239
CH08P3	371					sad	-2.184	2.219	0.002
CH08P	1214								
CH08P Sig.		0.017	0.071						

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

CH09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
CH09P2	755	0.419	0.011	0.862	0.765	<0.0005		
CH09P2	755						max	0.630 0.076 0.299
CH09P3	353	0.374	0.013	0.857	0.826	-0.021		
CH09P3	353						max	0.642 0.198 0.267
CH09P	1108							
CH09P Sig.		0.415	0.970					

CH10	2021-05-05–2022-05-02							
CH10P2	840	0.461	0.150	0.850	0.759	0.089		
CH10P2	840						sad	1.015 -3.167 0.001
CH10P2	840						max	0.744 0.282 0.314
CH10P3	352	0.443	0.104	0.905	0.853	-0.081		
CH10P3	352						max	0.773 0.270 0.253
CH10P	1192							
CH10P Sig.		0.170	0.091					

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
CH11	2023-03-11–2024-01-31								
CH11P2	753	0.473	0.146	0.817	0.785	0.085			
CH11P2	753						max	0.812 0.259 0.288	
CH11P3	287	0.459	0.069	0.825	0.719	0.139			
CH11P3	287						max	0.798 0.339 0.326	
CH11P	1040							" "	
CH11P Sig.		0.812	0.145						
Cyprus	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
CY05P2	728	0.087	-0.572	1.092	0.939	-0.195			
CY05P2	728						max	0.237 -0.873 0.171	
CY05P	728							" "	
CY05P Sig.									

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>								
CY06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
CY06P2	846	-0.280	-0.819	1.094	0.949	-0.072		
CY06P2	846						max	-0.619 -1.242 0.154
CY06P	846		" "					" "
CY06P Sig.								
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>								
CY09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
CY09P2	656	-0.182	-0.254	0.889	0.886	-0.109		
CY09P2	656						max	-0.011 -0.180 0.190
CY09P	656		" "					" "
CY09P Sig.								

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Czech Republic									
CZ05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
CZ05P1	958	-0.212	-0.257	1.027	0.919	-0.101			
CZ05P1	958					max	-0.440	-0.283	0.187
CZ05P2	707	-0.285	-0.292	1.004	0.877	-0.058			
CZ05P2	707					max	-0.546	-0.380	0.194
CZ05P3	231	-0.156	-0.326	0.995	0.875	-0.216			
CZ05P3	231					max	-0.724	0.014	0.159
			<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ05P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ05P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ05P3</p> </div> </div>						
CZ05P	1896								
CZ05P Sig.		0.162	0.510				0.163	0.351	
CZ06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
CZ06P1	646	-0.364	-0.210	1.094	0.928	-0.234			
CZ06P1	646					max	-0.827	-0.099	0.188
CZ06P2	543	-0.448	-0.227	1.139	0.962	-0.131			
CZ06P2	543					max	-0.893	-0.291	0.163
CZ06P3	200	0.152	-0.303	1.104	0.952	-0.260			
CZ06P3	200					max	-0.676	0.112	0.179
			<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ06P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ06P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CZ06P3</p> </div> </div>						
CZ06P	1389								
CZ06P Sig.		<0.0005	0.474				<0.0005	0.438	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
CZ07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
CZ07P1	752	-0.285	-0.473	1.050	0.779	-0.072			
CZ07P1	752					max	-0.452	-0.375	0.228
CZ07P2	571	-0.068	-0.468	1.056	0.817	-0.057			
CZ07P2	571					max	-0.133	-0.387	0.205
CZ07P3	158	0.121	-0.632	1.229	0.885	-0.252			
CZ07P3	158					max	1.102	-0.723	0.215
CZ07P3	158					sad	-1.961	-2.562	0.015
CZ07P3	158					sad	-0.392	-0.389	0.132
CZ07P3	158					max	-1.099	-0.338	0.142

CZ07P	1481							
CZ07P Sig.		<0.0005	0.058				<0.0005	0.017

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
CZ08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
CZ08P1	939	0.066	-0.544	1.051	0.826	-0.003			
CZ08P1	939					max	0.226	-0.386	0.193
CZ08P2	802	0.002	-0.609	1.071	0.883	0.031			
CZ08P2	802					max	0.292	-0.415	0.157
CZ08P3	239	-0.068	-0.747	1.097	0.915	0.018			
CZ08P3	239					max	-0.078	-0.877	0.151

CZ08P	1980							
CZ08P Sig.		0.166	0.004				0.045	0.002

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>								
CZ09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
CZ09P1	863	-0.041	-0.688	1.175	0.904	0.038		
CZ09P1	863						max	-0.444 -0.598 0.151
CZ09P2	757	0.064	-0.421	1.081	0.875	0.195		
CZ09P2	757						max	0.766 -0.075 0.203
CZ09P3	232	-0.105	-0.582	1.023	0.984	0.274		
CZ09P3	232						max	-0.337 -0.961 0.174
CZ09P	1852							
CZ09P Sig.	0.061	<0.0005					0.295	0.196
CZ10	<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/> 2021-07-07–2021-09-26							
CZ10P1	877	0.270	-0.359	1.175	0.956	0.136		
CZ10P1	877						max	0.969 0.209 0.152
CZ10P2	785	0.327	-0.323	1.183	1.013	0.193		
CZ10P2	785						max	1.175 0.304 0.163
CZ10P2	785						sad	-0.593 -0.874 0.079
CZ10P2	785						max	-0.921 -1.141 0.080
CZ10P3	271	0.050	-0.238	1.020	1.017	0.064		
CZ10P3	271						max	0.185 0.073 0.144
CZ10P	1932							
CZ10P Sig.	0.956	0.119					0.225	0.069

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Germany										
DE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
DE05P1	477	-0.201	-0.208	0.891	0.899	0.059				
DE05P1	477					max	-0.181	-0.129	0.197	
DE05P2	961	0.079	0.051	0.910	0.892	0.075				
DE05P2	961					max	0.134	0.181	0.213	
DE05P3	926	-0.085	0.051	0.896	0.870	0.063				
DE05P3	926					max	0.012	0.081	0.194	
DE05P	2364									
DE05P Sig.		0.001	0.002				0.006	0.005		
DE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
DE06P1	489	-0.043	-0.008	0.926	0.863	0.085				
DE06P1	489						max	0.128	0.022	0.197
DE06P2	1078	0.125	0.144	0.854	0.872	-0.015				
DE06P2	1078						max	0.259	0.213	0.233
DE06P3	984	0.042	0.150	0.850	0.807	0.108				
DE06P3	984						sad	0.610	-3.513	0.001
DE06P3	984						max	0.228	0.240	0.252
DE06P	2551									
DE06P Sig.		0.001	0.001				0.035	<0.0005		

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
DE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
DE07P1	516	-0.096	-0.138	1.024	0.932	0.095			
DE07P1	516						max 0.111	0.015 0.168	
DE07P2	1087	0.057	0.106	0.923	0.847	0.157			
DE07P2	1087						max 0.379	0.318 0.229	
DE07P3	1043	0.045	0.053	0.921	0.846	0.061			
DE07P3	1043						max 0.315	0.081 0.216	
DE07P	2646								
DE07P Sig.		0.006	<0.0005				0.005	<0.0005	
DE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
DE08P1	481	-0.042	-0.189	1.007	0.928	0.258			
DE08P1	481						max 0.337	0.049 0.154	
DE08P2	1047	0.113	0.030	0.946	0.863	0.056			
DE08P2	1047						max 0.467	0.199 0.215	
DE08P2	1047						sad -2.531	2.314 0.003	
DE08P3	1057	0.164	-0.025	0.857	0.866	0.092			
DE08P3	1057						max 0.424	0.104 0.211	
DE08P	2585								
DE08P Sig.		0.011	0.491				<0.0005	0.010	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		

DE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
DE09P1	397	-0.113	-0.113	0.950	0.905	0.169				
DE09P1	397						max	0.326	0.202	0.168
DE09P2	860	0.201	0.110	0.932	0.897	0.144				
DE09P2	860						max	0.477	0.291	0.199
DE09P3	824	0.092	0.049	0.935	0.940	0.154				
DE09P3	824						max	0.614	0.520	0.197
		DE09P1			DE09P2			DE09P3		
DE09P	2082									
DE09P Sig.		0.078	0.021					0.028	0.624	

DE11	2023-05-12–2023-12-17									
DE11P1	395	0.014	-0.129	1.034	0.874	0.253				
DE11P1	395						max	0.643	0.138	0.175
DE11P2	920	0.340	0.065	0.989	0.845	0.261				
DE11P2	920						max	0.781	0.295	0.235
DE11P2	920						sad	-2.121	2.028	0.003
DE11P3	855	0.326	0.089	0.959	0.871	0.235				
DE11P3	855						max	0.788	0.393	0.221
DE11P3	855						sad	-2.061	2.088	0.004
		DE11P1			DE11P2			DE11P3		
DE11P	2169									
DE11P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					<0.0005	<0.0005	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Denmark									
DK05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
DK05P1	323	0.557	-0.124	0.842	0.864	-0.106			
DK05P1	323						max 0.774	0.028	0.235
DK05P1	323						sad -2.223	0.940	0.005
DK05P2	573	0.529	-0.078	0.831	0.912	0.047			
DK05P2	573						max 0.752	0.113	0.218
DK05P3	386	0.528	0.266	0.866	0.899	-0.143			
DK05P3	386						max 0.944	0.393	0.237

DK05P 1282

DK05P Sig. <0.0005 0.078 <0.0005 0.091

DK06 2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
DK06P1	341	0.619	-0.109	0.805	0.992	0.113			
DK06P1	341						max 0.798	0.039	0.188
DK06P2	608	0.595	-0.060	0.841	0.897	0.161			
DK06P2	608						max 0.918	0.245	0.223
DK06P3	414	0.683	0.331	0.862	0.863	0.016			
DK06P3	414						max 0.924	0.582	0.273
DK06P3	414						sad -2.243	1.841	0.003

DK06P 1364

DK06P Sig. <0.0005 0.220 <0.0005 0.704

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
DK07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
DK07P1	328	0.438	-0.186	0.920	0.913	0.118		
DK07P1	328						max	0.931 -0.015 0.211
DK07P1	328						sad	-1.614 2.435 0.003
DK07P2	561	0.417	-0.288	0.879	0.946	0.172		
DK07P2	561						max	0.830 0.202 0.189
DK07P3	412	0.592	0.109	0.935	0.913	-0.004		
DK07P3	412						sad	3.033 -2.657 0.001
DK07P3	412						max	0.854 0.403 0.235
DK07P3	412						sad	-2.252 2.008 0.003
DK07P1								
DK07P2								
DK07P3								
DK07P	1301							
DK07P Sig.		<0.0005	0.850				<0.0005	0.914
<hr/>								
DK09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
DK09P1	322	0.522	-0.110	0.872	0.879	0.127		
DK09P1	322						max	0.935 0.047 0.232
DK09P2	548	0.597	0.009	0.820	0.951	-0.034		
DK09P2	548						max	0.975 0.371 0.227
DK09P3	393	0.644	-0.083	0.908	0.858	0.019		
DK09P3	393						sad	-1.661 -2.283 0.005
DK09P3	393						max	0.652 0.242 0.229
DK09P1								
DK09P2								
DK09P3								
DK09P	1263							
DK09P Sig.		0.166	0.119				0.087	0.263

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Estonia								
EE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
EE05P1	899	0.162	-0.196	0.969	0.816	-0.119		
EE05P1	899						max	0.345 -0.129 0.227
EE05P3	449	0.295	-0.043	0.894	0.882	-0.148		
EE05P3	449						max	0.432 0.050 0.228
EE05P3	449						sad	-3.108 1.231 0.002
EE05P	1348						" "	
EE05P Sig.		<0.0005	0.051					0.007 0.246
EE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
EE06P1	1137	0.106	0.075	0.969	0.892	-0.147		
EE06P1	1137						max	0.123 0.106 0.200
EE06P3	656	0.117	0.091	0.891	0.853	-0.174		
EE06P3	656						max	0.198 0.089 0.220
EE06P	1793						" "	
EE06P Sig.		0.820	0.706					0.725 0.475

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
EE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
EE07P1	898	0.078	0.015	1.003	0.859	-0.061		
EE07P1	898						sad	1.162 -3.588 0.001
EE07P1	898						max	0.194 0.098 0.216
EE07P3	743	0.046	0.044	0.952	0.840	-0.016		
EE07P3	743						min	0.307 -3.898 0.000
EE07P3	743						max	0.306 0.141 0.235
EE07P	1642						" "	
EE07P Sig.		0.499	0.484					0.678 0.837
EE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
EE08P1	956	0.111	-0.253	0.965	0.877	0.074		
EE08P1	956						max	0.438 -0.140 0.198
EE08P3	797	0.301	-0.232	0.900	0.896	0.014		
EE08P3	797						max	0.419 -0.089 0.210
EE08P	1754						" "	
EE08P Sig.		<0.0005	0.201					<0.0005 0.204

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

EE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
EE09P1	994	0.087	-0.307	0.971	0.854	0.142		
EE09P1	994						max	0.447 -0.123 0.216
EE09P3	723	0.355	-0.087	0.963	0.839	-0.043		
EE09P3	723						sad	1.763 -3.465 0.001
EE09P3	723						max	0.589 0.010 0.248
EE09P	1717							" "
EE09P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					<0.0005 <0.0005

EE10	2021-06-09–2021-12-31							
EE10P1	736	0.105	-0.189	1.015	0.947	0.018		
EE10P1	736						max	0.467 -0.020 0.175
EE10P3	632	0.359	0.062	0.909	0.853	0.056		
EE10P3	632						sad	1.043 -3.893 0.001
EE10P3	632						max	0.655 0.177 0.244
EE10P	1368							" "
EE10P Sig.		<0.0005	0.910					<0.0005 0.613

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Spain									
ES05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
ES05P1	560	-0.055	0.161	0.951	0.824	-0.018			
ES05P1	560					sad	1.389	-2.944	0.002
ES05P1	560					max	0.257	0.379	0.236
ES05P2	395	-0.095	0.177	0.971	0.838	0.010			
ES05P2	395					max	0.243	0.342	0.214
ES05P3	605	-0.213	0.323	0.960	0.853	-0.087			
ES05P3	605					max	0.048	0.456	0.216
ES05P	1560								
ES05P Sig.		0.015	0.002				0.020	<0.0005	
ES06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
ES06P1	502	-0.304	0.421	1.014	0.993	-0.118			
ES06P1	502					max	-0.436	0.566	0.150
ES06P2	414	-0.407	0.401	0.948	1.001	-0.174			
ES06P2	414					max	-0.273	0.524	0.176
ES06P3	707	-0.465	0.583	0.960	0.954	-0.103			
ES06P3	707					max	-0.548	0.817	0.167
ES06P	1623								
ES06P Sig.		0.018	0.002				0.029	0.002	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

ES07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
ES07P1	454	-0.120	0.248	1.030	0.953	-0.186			
ES07P1	454					max	-0.215	0.333	0.170
ES07P2	332	-0.236	0.406	1.050	0.886	-0.132			
ES07P2	332					max	-0.397	0.465	0.183
ES07P3	566	-0.350	0.399	0.987	0.982	-0.099			
ES07P3	566					max	-0.398	0.608	0.167
ES07P	1353								
ES07P Sig.		0.002	0.019				0.002	0.001	

ES08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
ES08P1	461	-0.226	0.388	1.019	0.855	0.006			
ES08P1	461					max	-0.132	0.475	0.173
ES08P2	366	-0.184	0.356	1.040	1.021	-0.226			
ES08P2	366					max	-0.117	0.653	0.145
ES08P3	582	-0.401	0.499	1.049	0.996	-0.075			
ES08P3	582					max	0.004	0.835	0.144
ES08P	1410								
ES08P Sig.		0.002	0.050				0.006	0.052	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

ES09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
ES09P1	391	-0.160	0.390	1.019	0.892	0.070		
ES09P1	391					max	-0.045	0.495 0.183
ES09P2	311	-0.163	0.519	0.962	0.964	-0.029		
ES09P2	311					max	-0.140	0.678 0.180
ES09P3	511	-0.271	0.614	1.007	0.935	-0.078		
ES09P3	511					max	-0.259	0.850 0.168
ES09P	1213							
ES09P Sig.	0.170	0.002					0.055	0.002
Finland								
FI05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
FI05P1	413	0.439	0.120	0.874	0.684	-0.018		
FI05P1	413						max	0.757 0.264 0.337
FI05P2	517	0.502	0.134	0.811	0.725	0.050		
FI05P2	517						max	0.790 0.325 0.327
FI05P3	422	0.457	0.293	0.815	0.784	0.017		
FI05P3	422						max	0.732 0.468 0.295
FI05P	1352							
FI05P Sig.	0.484	0.001					0.620	<0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
FI06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
FI06P1	698	0.527	0.152	0.829	0.674	0.109		
FI06P1	698						max 0.934	0.296 0.361
FI06P2	771	0.454	0.088	0.827	0.740	0.081	max	0.865 0.177 0.305
FI06P2	771						max	
FI06P3	589	0.631	0.324	0.818	0.741	0.068		
FI06P3	589						sad 0.980	-2.782 0.002
FI06P3	589						max 1.009	0.454 0.361
FI06P	2058							
FI06P Sig.		0.058	0.006				0.161	<0.0005
<hr/>								
FI07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
FI07P1	649	0.368	0.108	0.931	0.777	0.105		
FI07P1	649						max 0.764	0.324 0.281
FI07P2	697	0.360	0.118	0.892	0.805	0.070	max	0.887 0.241 0.261
FI07P2	697						max	
FI07P3	576	0.568	0.352	0.851	0.821	0.080		
FI07P3	576						max 1.051	0.593 0.285
FI07P	1922							
FI07P Sig.		0.442	0.718				0.227	0.539

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
FI08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
FI08P1	609	0.525	0.043	0.875	0.815	0.098		
FI08P1	609						max 0.972	0.361 0.307
FI08P2	659	0.474	0.104	0.944	0.753	0.147		
FI08P2	659						max 0.983	0.269 0.292
FI08P3	549	0.631	0.354	0.906	0.901	0.080		
FI08P3	549						max 1.082	0.552 0.268
FI08P3	549						sad -1.755	2.824 0.004
FI08P	1817							
FI08P Sig.		0.065	0.589				0.001	0.462
<hr/>								
FI09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
FI09P1	538	0.549	0.072	0.888	0.789	0.240		
FI09P1	538						max 1.090	0.387 0.338
FI09P2	592	0.520	0.084	0.845	0.833	0.208		
FI09P2	592						max 0.969	0.473 0.283
FI09P3	497	0.663	0.378	0.837	0.744	0.163		
FI09P3	497						max 1.112	0.598 0.429
FI09P	1626							
FI09P Sig.		0.007	0.230				0.003	0.223

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
FI10	2021-09-01–2022-01-14								
FI10P1	353	0.691	0.100	0.898	0.791	0.059			
FI10P1	353					max	1.186	0.454	0.340
FI10P2	548	0.795	0.148	0.813	0.806	0.161			
FI10P2	548					max	1.221	0.400	0.317
FI10P3	456	0.817	0.404	0.814	0.765	0.130			
FI10P3	456					max	1.286	0.692	0.364
FI10P	1357								
FI10P Sig.		0.002	0.953				0.029	0.226	
<hr/>									
FI11	2023-08-10–2024-01-25								
FI11P1	476	0.782	0.278	0.815	0.804	0.140			
FI11P1	476					max	1.089	0.556	0.302
FI11P2	535	0.748	0.324	0.821	0.809	0.216			
FI11P2	535					max	1.199	0.627	0.341
FI11P3	424	0.949	0.506	0.764	0.819	0.115			
FI11P3	424					max	1.212	0.828	0.328
FI11P3	424					sad	-1.872	1.493	0.004
FI11P	1435								
FI11P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				0.004	<0.0005	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
France								
FR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
FR05P1	699	-0.002	-0.263	0.930	1.002	-0.036		
FR05P1	699					max	0.283	-0.196 0.156
FR05P2	621	0.055	-0.108	0.893	1.003	-0.007		
FR05P2	621					max	0.223	-0.014 0.164
FR05P3	294	0.113	0.051	0.992	0.942	0.086		
FR05P3	294					sad	1.950	-3.272 0.001
FR05P3	294					max	0.352	0.256 0.190
FR05P3	294					sad	-1.863	2.407 0.007
FR05P	1614							
FR05P Sig.		0.029	0.288				0.004	0.204

FR06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
FR06P1	753	0.020	-0.303	0.923	0.966	0.160		
FR06P1	753						max	0.217 -0.195 0.178
FR06P2	778	-0.009	-0.122	0.911	0.950	0.050		
FR06P2	778						max	0.231 -0.035 0.174
FR06P3	329	0.172	0.282	0.933	0.856	-0.176		
FR06P3	329						max	0.523 0.378 0.212
FR06P	1860							
FR06P Sig.		<0.0005	0.052				<0.0005	0.005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
FR07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
FR07P1	775	-0.049	-0.168	0.920	0.949	0.070			
FR07P1	775					max	0.053	0.002	0.181
FR07P2	631	-0.141	-0.078	0.902	1.015	0.111			
FR07P2	631					max	0.111	0.120	0.162
FR07P3	320	0.159	0.372	0.943	0.966	-0.120			
FR07P3	320					max	0.443	0.463	0.185
FR07P	1726								
FR07P Sig.		0.317	0.172				0.002	0.498	
FR08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
FR08P1	783	-0.186	-0.164	0.927	1.009	0.127			
FR08P1	783					max	0.203	0.178	0.140
FR08P2	762	-0.068	-0.051	0.901	0.971	0.002			
FR08P2	762					max	0.228	0.116	0.184
FR08P3	357	0.024	0.336	0.927	0.918	0.008			
FR08P3	357					max	0.606	0.405	0.204
FR08P	1902								
FR08P Sig.		<0.0005	0.311				<0.0005	0.405	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x,y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>								
FR09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
FR09P1	680	-0.066	-0.134	0.947	1.007	0.099		
FR09P1	680					max	0.489	0.148 0.152
FR09P2	635	0.048	-0.023	0.860	0.931	0.028		
FR09P2	635					max	0.323	0.188 0.206
FR09P3	350	0.229	0.407	0.904	0.943	-0.059		
FR09P3	350					max	0.339	0.618 0.202
FR09P3	350					sad	-2.473	2.806 0.003
FR09P	1665							
FR09P Sig.	<0.0005	<0.0005					0.001	<0.0005
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>								
FR10	2021-01-01–2021-12-31							
FR10P1	624	0.063	-0.089	0.909	1.014	0.115		
FR10P1	624					max	0.377	0.069 0.163
FR10P2	676	0.116	0.084	0.907	0.998	0.031		
FR10P2	676					max	0.538	0.199 0.171
FR10P3	283	0.208	0.444	0.981	0.916	-0.137		
FR10P3	283					max	0.417	0.616 0.234
FR10P3	283					sad	-2.982	1.580 0.005
FR10P	1583							
FR10P Sig.	<0.0005	0.150					<0.0005	0.366

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Greece								
GR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
GR05P1	1129	-0.687	-0.750	1.005	0.887	-0.049		
GR05P1	1129					max	-1.276	-1.238 0.267
GR05P2	284	-0.738	-0.814	0.886	0.910	0.132		
GR05P2	284					max	-1.273	-1.643 0.336
GR05P3	900	-0.629	-0.580	0.915	0.975	-0.069		
GR05P3	900					max	-1.058	-1.124 0.204
GR05P	2312							
GR05P Sig.		0.707	0.881				0.016	0.446
GR10	2021-11-21–2022-04-19							
GR10P1	1097	0.162	-0.476	0.881	0.839	-0.020		
GR10P1	1097					max	0.360	-0.250 0.232
GR10P2	315	0.612	-0.104	0.787	0.872	-0.103		
GR10P2	315					max	0.712	0.158 0.212
GR10P3	950	0.278	-0.559	0.863	0.905	-0.206		
GR10P3	950					max	0.574	-0.542 0.188
GR10P	2363							
GR10P Sig.		<0.0005	0.001				<0.0005	<0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Croatia								
HR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
HR05P1	315	-0.531	0.023	1.073	1.073	-0.139		
HR05P1	315						sad	-0.349 -4.820 0.001
HR05P1	315						max	-0.855 0.120 0.145
HR05P2	354	-0.803	0.066	1.022	0.969	-0.055		
HR05P2	354						max	-1.271 -0.022 0.156
HR05P3	489	-0.868	0.374	0.913	1.037	-0.153		
HR05P3	489						max	-0.914 0.390 0.171
HR05P	1158							
HR05P Sig.		<0.0005	0.001					<0.0005 0.002
HR09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
HR09P1	172	-0.858	0.052	1.028	1.224	-0.078		
HR09P1	172						max	-1.353 -0.716 0.118
HR09P2	99	-0.654	0.008	1.160	1.478	-0.233		
HR09P2	99						max	-1.070 -1.640 0.128
HR09P2	99						sad	-1.219 0.263 0.045
HR09P2	99						max	-1.609 1.905 0.087
HR09P3	200	-0.763	0.181	0.901	1.077	-0.121		
HR09P3	200						sad	1.756 -2.868 0.003
HR09P3	200						max	-0.841 0.439 0.148
HR09P	472							
HR09P Sig.		<0.0005	0.010					0.014 <0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
HR10	2021-05-05–2021-11-13							
HR10P1	784	-0.527	0.292	1.111	1.166	-0.151		
HR10P1	784						max	-0.627
HR10P2	97	-0.761	-0.308	1.040	1.194	-0.198		0.517
HR10P2	97						max	-1.514
HR10P3	441	-0.464	0.364	0.974	1.134	-0.180		0.116
HR10P3	441						max	-0.581
								0.674
								0.128
HR10P	1322							
HR10P Sig.		0.172	0.165					0.049
								0.018
HR11	2023-06-24–2024-01-05							
HR11P1	729	-0.528	0.173	1.012	1.051	-0.074		
HR11P1	729						max	-0.593
HR11P2	111	-0.868	-0.071	1.123	1.119	-0.152		0.250
HR11P2	111						max	-1.467
HR11P3	469	-0.335	0.183	0.969	1.145	-0.147		-0.067
HR11P3	469						max	-0.425
								0.415
								0.116
HR11P	1309							
HR11P Sig.		0.188	0.686					0.086
								0.151

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Hungary								
HU05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
HU05P1	545	0.270	-0.300	1.076	0.887	-0.041		
HU05P1	545						max 0.235	-0.270 0.181
HU05P2	129	-0.056	-0.290	0.947	0.840	-0.316		
HU05P2	129						max 0.031	-0.357 0.228
HU05P2	129						sad -1.281	3.937 0.001
HU05P3	34	0.152	0.059	1.186	0.689	0.012		
HU05P3	34						max 1.943	0.001 0.562
HU05P3	34						sad 0.409	-0.504 0.165
HU05P3	34						max -0.738	-0.680 0.244
HU05P3	34						sad -1.071	-0.373 0.241
HU05P3	34						max -1.108	-0.328 0.241

HU05P 709
 HU05P Sig.

0.586 0.284

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
HU06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
HU06P1	744	0.070	-0.210	1.049	0.916	-0.213				
HU06P1	744						sad	1.574	-3.657	0.002
HU06P1	744						max	-0.134	-0.147	0.186
HU06P2	165	-0.174	-0.027	1.059	0.739	-0.081				
HU06P2	165						max	0.626	-0.123	0.176
HU06P2	165						sad	-0.257	0.238	0.168
HU06P2	165						max	-0.764	0.377	0.169
HU06P3	55	0.474	0.004	0.995	1.220	-0.270				
HU06P3	55						max	1.235	0.804	0.161
HU06P3	55						sad	-0.345	0.700	0.048
HU06P3	55						max	-1.045	0.673	0.055

HU06P1

HU06P2

HU06P3

HU06P	964								
HU06P Sig.		<0.0005	0.024						

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
HU07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
HU07P1	528	0.018	-0.321	0.970	0.905	-0.095		
HU07P1	528						max	-0.046 -0.309 0.197
HU07P1	528						sad	-1.764 3.298 0.001
HU07P2	111	0.349	-0.330	1.105	0.857	-0.356		
HU07P2	111						min	1.386 -4.429 0.000
HU07P2	111						max	1.001 -0.374 0.264
HU07P2	111						sad	-1.550 -1.829 0.012
HU07P2	111						sad	1.727 2.374 0.001
HU07P3	48	-0.188	-0.074	1.185	0.899	-0.352		
HU07P3	48						max	3.861 -2.750 0.002
HU07P3	48						sad	3.451 -1.221 0.000
HU07P3	48						sad	1.458 -2.461 0.000
HU07P3	48						min	1.690 -1.232 0.000
HU07P3	48						max	2.413 1.405 2.615
HU07P3	48						sad	0.397 0.759 0.001
HU07P3	48						max	-0.860 0.087 0.015

HU07P 687
 HU07P Sig. <0.0005 0.493

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HU08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
HU08P1	523	0.202	-0.636	0.990	0.878	0.008		
HU08P1	523						max	0.127 -0.504 0.185
HU08P2	141	-0.042	-0.941	1.185	0.859	0.400		
HU08P2	141						max	1.019 -0.848 0.183
HU08P2	141						sad	-0.092 -1.164 0.116
HU08P2	141						max	-1.660 -1.755 0.385

HU08P 664
 HU08P Sig. 0.003 0.414

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

HU09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
HU09P1	847	0.598	-0.640	0.933	0.961	-0.042		
HU09P1	847						max 0.777	-0.530 0.165
HU09P2	130	0.352	-0.641	1.197	0.910	0.394		
HU09P2	130						max 1.310	-0.044 0.195
HU09P2	130						sad -0.018	-0.926 0.103
HU09P2	130						max -1.127	-1.559 0.148
HU09P3	240	0.623	-0.587	0.896	0.987	-0.226		
HU09P3	240						sad 3.817	-2.008 0.003
HU09P3	240						max 0.642	-0.366 0.231
HU09P3	240						sad -2.086	-1.445 0.004

HU09P1								
HU09P2								
HU09P3								
HU09P	1217							
HU09P Sig.		0.061	0.019					

HU10	2021-06-10–2021-10-16							
HU10P1	903	0.452	-0.454	0.933	0.963	-0.181		
HU10P1	903						max 0.734	-0.317 0.171
HU10P2	105	0.618	-0.561	1.048	0.826	-0.094		
HU10P2	105						max 0.956	0.064 0.263
HU10P3	347	0.660	-0.366	0.815	0.986	-0.294		
HU10P3	347						max 0.591	0.275 0.260
HU10P3	347						sad -1.249	-1.936 0.005

HU10P1								
HU10P2								
HU10P3								
HU10P	1355							
HU10P Sig.		0.001	0.141					

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

HU11	2023-05-06–2023-11-07							
HU11P1	1084	0.448	-0.643	0.999	1.049	-0.025		
HU11P1	1084						max 0.593	-0.566 0.136
HU11P2	206	0.398	-0.588	0.875	0.936	0.018		
HU11P2	206						max 0.434	-0.554 0.187
HU11P3	408	0.661	-0.376	0.945	1.288	-0.244		
HU11P3	408						max 0.761	0.255 0.115
HU11P	1699							
HU11P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					

Ireland								
IE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
IE09P1	1036	0.198	0.387	0.967	0.898	0.015		
IE09P1	1036						max 0.568	0.573 0.197
IE09P3	707	0.246	0.733	1.053	0.889	0.015		
IE09P3	707						max 0.775	1.052 0.222
IE09P	1743							
IE09P Sig.		<0.0005	0.179	" "			<0.0005	0.008

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

IE10	2021-11-23–2022-08-26							
IE10P1	733	0.333	0.651	1.072	0.885	-0.060		
IE10P1	733						max 0.891	0.885 0.221
IE10P3	613	0.318	0.807	1.094	0.881	0.058		
IE10P3	613						max 1.026	1.065 0.241
IE10P	1346					" "		
IE10P Sig.		0.472	0.035				0.130	0.128

IE11	2023-06-27–2024-01-03							
IE11P1	948	0.296	0.278	1.099	1.114	0.027		
IE11P1	948						max 0.745	0.772 0.144
IE11P3	628	0.332	0.607	1.022	0.955	0.030		
IE11P3	628						max 0.725	1.135 0.226
IE11P	1576					" "		
IE11P Sig.		0.517	<0.0005				0.094	<0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Italy								
IT06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
IT06P1	235	-0.312	0.021	1.037	1.072	0.118		
IT06P1	235						max	-0.102 0.365 0.124
IT06P2	36	-0.323	-0.051	0.997	0.874	0.101		
IT06P2	36						sad	0.453 0.295 0.127
IT06P2	36						max	0.571 0.529 0.128
IT06P2	36						max	-1.542 -0.732 0.390
IT06P3	431	-0.104	0.267	1.017	1.076	-0.041		
IT06P3	431						sad	2.966 -2.397 0.002
IT06P3	431						max	-0.081 0.591 0.140
IT06P	703							
IT06P Sig.		0.032	0.008				0.057	0.001
IT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
IT08P1	699	-0.396	-0.393	1.029	1.001	0.025		
IT08P1	699						max	-1.095 -1.066 0.166
IT08P2	122	-0.458	-0.331	1.155	1.039	0.202		
IT08P2	122						max	0.881 0.092 0.166
IT08P2	122						sad	-0.337 -0.540 0.071
IT08P2	122						max	-1.564 -0.968 0.155
IT08P3	1158	-0.258	-0.157	0.998	1.042	0.140		
IT08P3	1158						max	-0.618 -0.439 0.136
IT08P	1979							
IT08P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				0.001	<0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

IT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
IT09P1	716	-0.098	-0.363	1.008	1.153	-0.016			
IT09P1	716					max	-0.204	-0.888	0.111
IT09P3	1369	0.080	-0.057	0.979	1.031	0.084			
IT09P3	1369					max	0.204	0.122	0.157
IT09P	2085								
IT09P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005	

IT10	2021-10-28–2022-04-26								
IT10P1	748	0.007	0.011	0.936	0.975	0.034			
IT10P1	748					max	0.332	0.251	0.159
IT10P3	1385	0.042	0.053	0.943	0.952	0.070			
IT10P3	1385					max	0.293	0.087	0.172
IT10P	2133								
IT10P Sig.		<0.0005	0.002				<0.0005	0.001	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Lithuania								
LT05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
LT05P1	457	-0.376	0.166	1.054	0.936	-0.192		
LT05P1	457					max	-0.553	0.341 0.165
LT05P2	372	-0.354	0.122	1.178	0.948	-0.074		
LT05P2	372					max	-1.040	-0.263 0.131
LT05P3	322	-0.350	0.346	0.896	0.873	-0.022		
LT05P3	322					max	-0.512	0.243 0.190
LT05P	1151							
LT05P Sig.		<0.0005	0.250				<0.0005	0.483
LT06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
LT06P1	482	-0.165	0.552	1.106	0.888	-0.068		
LT06P1	482					max	0.073	0.643 0.183
LT06P2	487	0.008	-0.099	0.891	0.890	-0.124		
LT06P2	487					max	0.023	-0.182 0.226
LT06P2	487					sad	0.905	3.310 0.002
LT06P3	353	-0.307	0.100	1.122	0.871	-0.249		
LT06P3	353					max	-0.569	0.114 0.185
LT06P3	353					sad	-3.153	2.998 0.006
LT06P	1322							
LT06P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				0.051	<0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

LT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
LT09P1	427	-0.320	0.383	1.129	1.122	-0.272		
LT09P1	427						max	-0.711 0.250 0.110
LT09P2	376	0.176	0.106	0.832	0.832	0.043		
LT09P2	376						sad	-0.148 -3.265 0.002
LT09P2	376						max	0.210 0.172 0.278
LT09P3	270	0.426	0.010	0.814	1.005	-0.033		
LT09P3	270						sad	0.183 -3.610 0.008
LT09P3	270						max	0.786 0.131 0.214
LT09P3	270						sad	-2.412 -0.309 0.007
LT09P	1073							
LT09P Sig.		0.004	0.783					0.013 0.086

LT10	2021-07-01–2021-12-15							
LT10P1	456	0.005	0.008	0.983	0.997	-0.004		
LT10P1	456						max	0.129 0.111 0.155
LT10P2	319	0.330	0.218	0.985	0.886	0.092		
LT10P2	319						sad	1.034 -2.788 0.002
LT10P2	319						max	0.454 0.284 0.193
LT10P2	319						sad	-1.322 3.113 0.002
LT10P3	382	0.491	0.197	0.929	0.901	0.237		
LT10P3	382						max	0.748 0.325 0.239
LT10P3	382						sad	-2.426 -1.658 0.003
LT10P	1157							
LT10P Sig.		<0.0005	0.003					<0.0005 0.151

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

LT11	2023-09-08–2023-12-29							
LT11P1	353	0.189	0.015	1.060	0.932	-0.005		
LT11P1	353						sad	2.270 -3.311 0.002
LT11P1	353						max	0.471 0.189 0.174
LT11P2	254	0.224	0.229	0.903	0.748	-0.015		
LT11P2	254						sad	0.503 -3.453 0.001
LT11P2	254						max	0.605 0.305 0.291
LT11P3	408	0.180	0.070	0.880	0.895	-0.011		
LT11P3	408						max	0.299 0.118 0.232
LT11P3	408						min	-3.584 -0.779 0.000
LT11P3	408						sad	-2.354 1.934 0.004

LT11P	1014							
LT11P Sig.		0.838	0.011				0.018	0.206

Latvia								
LV09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
LV09P1	468	-0.174	0.289	1.057	0.974	-0.172		
LV09P1	468						max	0.262 0.206 0.155
LV09P3	128	-0.353	0.447	0.935	1.009	-0.230		
LV09P3	128						max	0.447 0.438 0.171
LV09P	596							
LV09P Sig.		<0.0005	0.210			" "	<0.0005	0.108

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Makedonia								
MK10	2021-10-25–2022-03-07							
MK10P1	328	-0.083	-0.203	1.110	1.168	-0.061		
MK10P1	328						max	-0.264 -0.733 0.120
MK10P2	588	-0.095	-0.410	1.090	1.097	0.047		
MK10P2	588						max	-0.421 -0.904 0.110
MK10P3	210	-0.396	-0.019	0.988	1.084	-0.080		
MK10P3	210						max	0.582 0.051 0.133
MK10P3	210						sad	-0.446 -0.257 0.100
MK10P3	210						max	-1.243 -0.568 0.116
MK10P	1126							
MK10P Sig.		0.001	<0.0005				<0.0005	0.027
Netherlands								
NL05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
NL05P1	482	0.470	0.025	0.721	0.679	-0.011		
NL05P1	482						sad	0.934 -3.373 0.001
NL05P1	482						max	0.728 0.129 0.435
NL05P1	482						sad	-2.279 -0.956 0.003
NL05P2	713	0.455	-0.055	0.732	0.666	0.047		
NL05P2	713						max	0.766 0.174 0.452
NL05P3	378	0.484	0.100	0.801	0.727	-0.065		
NL05P3	378						sad	0.831 -3.488 0.001
NL05P3	378						max	0.824 0.163 0.419
NL05P3	378						sad	-2.226 -1.366 0.003
NL05P	1572							
NL05P Sig.		0.314	0.440				0.149	0.218

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
NL06P1	496	0.414	0.062	0.770	0.638	0.041		
NL06P1	496						sad	0.735 -2.948 0.001
NL06P1	496						max	0.712 0.169 0.476
NL06P2	720	0.390	0.029	0.805	0.668	0.104		
NL06P2	720						max	0.827 0.184 0.446
NL06P3	381	0.538	0.154	0.794	0.694	0.169		
NL06P3	381						max	0.925 0.360 0.461
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL06P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL06P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL06P3</p> </div> </div>								
NL06P	1597							
NL06P Sig.		0.006	0.814				0.001	0.487

NL07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
NL07P1	482	0.350	-0.118	0.830	0.699	0.109		
NL07P1	482						max	0.798 0.029 0.380
NL07P2	711	0.378	-0.035	0.915	0.707	0.038		
NL07P2	711						sad	1.185 -3.051 0.001
NL07P2	711						max	0.742 0.075 0.371
NL07P3	376	0.423	0.003	0.824	0.686	0.048		
NL07P3	376						min	0.204 -3.199 0.000
NL07P3	376						max	0.927 0.090 0.474
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL07P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL07P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL07P3</p> </div> </div>								
NL07P	1569							
NL07P Sig.		0.001	0.058				0.696	0.390

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NL08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
NL08P1	447	0.430	-0.059	0.797	0.664	0.136		
NL08P1	447						sad	0.051 -2.646 0.004
NL08P1	447						max	0.708 0.023 0.411
NL08P2	633	0.357	-0.051	0.827	0.691	0.100		
NL08P2	633						max	0.784 0.101 0.418
NL08P3	329	0.552	0.085	0.707	0.647	0.231		
NL08P3	329						max	0.950 0.317 0.523
NL08P	1408							
NL08P Sig.		0.001	0.183				<0.0005	0.127

NL09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
NL09P1	465	0.547	0.007	0.781	0.617	0.162		
NL09P1	465						max	0.961 0.049 0.555
NL09P1	465						sad	-1.576 -1.861 0.004
NL09P2	644	0.600	0.012	0.757	0.654	0.107		
NL09P2	644						max	0.958 0.162 0.458
NL09P3	289	0.624	0.104	0.783	0.754	0.138		
NL09P3	289						sad	0.349 -2.893 0.004
NL09P3	289						max	0.952 0.322 0.408
NL09P3	289						sad	-2.848 0.188 0.002
NL09P	1398							
NL09P Sig.		0.004	0.754				0.080	0.345

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
NL10	2021-10-02–2022-04-03								
NL10P1	418	0.546	0.116	0.817	0.681	0.035			
NL10P1	418					sad	-0.166	-2.749	0.002
NL10P1	418					max	0.981	0.226	0.433
NL10P2	498	0.494	0.155	0.810	0.661	0.114			
NL10P2	498					max	0.797	0.340	0.426
NL10P3	275	0.685	0.283	0.807	0.641	-0.020			
NL10P3	275					max	1.023	0.375	0.492
NL10P	1191								
NL10P Sig.		0.007	0.005				0.098	0.031	
NL11	2023-04-02–2023-11-07								
NL11P1	489	0.484	0.073	0.851	0.668	0.196			
NL11P1	489					sad	1.386	-2.283	0.004
NL11P1	489					max	0.931	0.270	0.464
NL11P2	582	0.504	0.060	0.842	0.681	0.142			
NL11P2	582					max	0.864	0.188	0.408
NL11P3	337	0.525	0.268	0.868	0.729	-0.004			
NL11P3	337					max	0.986	0.367	0.382
NL11P	1408								
NL11P Sig.		0.341	0.942				0.953	0.839	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Norway								
NO05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
NO05P1	984	0.510	-0.049	0.807	0.790	0.160		
NO05P1	984						max	0.688 0.066 0.290
NO05P1	984						sad	-2.099 1.481 0.002
NO05P3	301	0.578	0.200	0.743	0.726	-0.004		
NO05P3	301						sad	1.040 -2.830 0.003
NO05P3	301						max	0.834 0.355 0.368
NO05P	1285						" "	
NO05P Sig.		0.058	0.421					0.007 0.672
NO06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
NO06P1	1071	0.511	0.080	0.771	0.792	0.055		
NO06P1	1071						max	0.676 0.210 0.283
NO06P3	331	0.582	0.204	0.712	0.818	0.047		
NO06P3	331						max	0.768 0.402 0.276
NO06P	1402						" "	
NO06P Sig.		0.013	0.205					0.004 0.004

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NO07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
NO07P1	957	0.599	-0.074	0.812	0.822	0.126		
NO07P1	957						max 0.812	0.082 0.264
NO07P3	298	0.722	0.087	0.791	0.826	-0.050		
NO07P3	298						max 0.932	0.167 0.290
NO07P	1256						" "	
NO07P Sig.		0.022	0.003					0.025 0.080

NO08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
NO08P1	988	0.681	-0.078	0.782	0.850	0.126		
NO08P1	988						max 0.971	0.182 0.266
NO08P3	308	0.823	0.174	0.753	0.862	-0.012		
NO08P3	308						max 1.131	0.416 0.301
NO08P	1296						" "	
NO08P Sig.		<0.0005	0.932					<0.0005 0.673

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NO09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
NO09P1	786	0.693	0.103	0.829	0.799	0.156		
NO09P1	786						max 0.999	0.221 0.285
NO09P3	282	0.782	0.276	0.812	0.812	0.073		
NO09P3	282						max 1.145	0.619 0.328
NO09P	1067							
NO09P Sig.		0.003	<0.0005				0.005	0.001

NO10	2021-06-24–2022-04-27							
NO10P1	933	0.802	0.217	0.838	0.815	0.198		
NO10P1	933						max 1.143	0.434 0.296
NO10P2	177	0.961	0.356	0.768	0.752	-0.014		
NO10P2	177						max 1.191	0.453 0.303
NO10P	1110							
NO10P Sig.		0.019	0.035					

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NO11	2023-04-20–2023-11-30							
NO11P1	761	0.806	0.298	0.857	0.725	0.152		
NO11P1	761						max	1.171 0.453 0.347
NO11P2	378	0.870	0.413	0.859	0.801	0.092		
NO11P2	378						max	1.212 0.612 0.321
NO11P	1139							" "
NO11P Sig.		0.014	0.345					

Poland								
PL05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
PL05P1	435	-0.191	0.582	0.948	0.854	-0.157		
PL05P1	435						max	-0.218 0.744 0.187
PL05P2	375	-0.283	0.624	0.941	0.781	-0.058		
PL05P2	375						sad	-1.779 -2.310 0.002
PL05P2	375						max	-0.298 0.701 0.273
PL05P3	205	-0.126	0.679	0.963	0.739	-0.189		
PL05P3	205						max	-0.447 0.819 0.226
PL05P	1016							
PL05P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					0.123 0.001

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
<hr/>										
PL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
PL06P1	432	-0.473	0.757	0.985	0.913	-0.120				
PL06P1	432						max	-0.575 0.945 0.176		
PL06P2	474	-0.404	0.728	0.932	0.877	-0.269				
PL06P2	474						max	-0.296 0.882 0.202		
PL06P3	206	-0.382	0.836	0.917	0.980	-0.064				
PL06P3	206						sad	0.806 -3.457 0.001		
PL06P3	206						max	-0.239 1.181 0.178		
<hr/>										
PL06P	1112									
PL06P Sig.		0.417	0.367				0.477	0.418		
<hr/>										
PL07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
PL07P1	385	-0.564	0.429	1.016	0.850	0.012				
PL07P1	385						max	-0.809 0.432 0.191		
PL07P2	414	-0.567	0.459	0.925	0.811	-0.030				
PL07P2	414						sad	-1.008 -3.278 0.001		
PL07P2	414						max	-0.724 0.595 0.246		
PL07P3	179	-0.651	0.567	0.927	0.986	-0.061				
PL07P3	179						max	-0.964 0.539 0.161		
<hr/>										
PL07P	978									
PL07P Sig.		0.855	0.117				0.672	0.062		

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
PL08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
PL08P1	393	-0.404	0.348	0.943	0.974	-0.209			
PL08P1	393					max	-0.656	0.353	0.162
PL08P2	369	-0.327	0.324	0.865	0.886	-0.248			
PL08P2	369					max	-0.482	0.582	0.218
PL08P3	188	-0.358	0.422	0.922	1.019	-0.126			
PL08P3	188					max	-0.750	0.690	0.170
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PL08P1</p> </div> </div>									
PL08P	950								
PL08P Sig.		0.001	0.069				0.014	0.307	
<hr/>									
PL09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
PL09P1	295	-0.177	0.294	0.925	1.055	-0.173			
PL09P1	295					max	-0.115	0.279	0.152
PL09P2	398	-0.063	0.398	0.860	0.940	-0.296			
PL09P2	398					sad	1.338	-3.510	0.003
PL09P2	398					max	-0.009	0.498	0.236
PL09P2	398					sad	-2.996	0.173	0.005
PL09P3	178	-0.022	0.793	0.882	0.892	0.039			
PL09P3	178					max	0.546	1.083	0.232
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PL09P1</p> </div> </div>									
PL09P	871								
PL09P Sig.		0.121	<0.0005				0.421	<0.0005	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Portugal								
PT05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
PT05P1	611	-0.272	0.060	0.874	0.716	-0.085		
PT05P1	611						max	-0.173 0.008 0.262
PT05P2	490	-0.347	-0.001	1.024	0.700	-0.226		
PT05P2	490						sad	-1.296 -2.210 0.006
PT05P2	490						max	0.245 0.060 0.298
PT05P3	459	-0.434	0.202	0.980	0.849	-0.166		
PT05P3	459						sad	-1.803 -2.854 0.001
PT05P3	459						max	-0.539 0.181 0.215
PT05P3	459						min	0.273 3.853 0.000
PT05P3	459						sad	-1.168 4.290 0.000

PT05P	1560							
PT05P Sig.		<0.0005	0.022				<0.0005	0.037

Region N	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
PT06P1	608	-0.504	-0.022	0.903	0.871	-0.172		
PT06P1	608						max	-0.737 -0.146 0.257
PT06P1	608						sad	-2.509 2.931 0.003
PT06P2	549	-0.260	-0.102	0.860	0.751	-0.149		
PT06P2	549						sad	-1.816 -2.548 0.005
PT06P2	549						max	-0.071 -0.122 0.311
PT06P3	512	-0.602	0.004	0.920	0.984	-0.040		
PT06P3	512						max	-0.907 -0.220 0.155

PT06P	1670							
PT06P Sig.		<0.0005	0.117				0.018	0.007

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed #000;"/>									
PT07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
PT07P1	398	-0.227	-0.013	0.971	0.880	-0.128			
PT07P1	398					sad	0.022	-2.937	0.003
PT07P1	398					max	-0.075	0.046	0.245
PT07P1	398					sad	-2.473	2.873	0.003
PT07P2	318	-0.377	0.090	1.048	0.937	-0.041			
PT07P2	318					max	-0.667	0.179	0.164
PT07P3	354	-0.347	0.306	1.033	0.995	-0.067			
PT07P3	354					max	-0.604	0.235	0.145
PT07P3	354					sad	-2.842	3.657	0.002
PT07P	1070								
PT07P Sig.	0.105	<0.0005						0.004	<0.0005
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed #000;"/>									
PT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
PT08P1	390	-0.115	0.299	1.002	0.825	-0.028			
PT08P1	390					sad	-1.525	-2.506	0.003
PT08P1	390					max	-0.010	0.227	0.224
PT08P1	390					sad	0.372	3.605	0.001
PT08P2	335	-0.368	0.256	1.018	0.855	-0.167			
PT08P2	335					max	-0.513	0.256	0.173
PT08P3	377	-0.101	0.331	0.998	0.773	-0.100			
PT08P3	377					max	0.200	0.405	0.230
PT08P	1102								
PT08P Sig.	0.933	0.286						0.241	0.360

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

PT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
PT09P1	297	-0.075	0.346	0.993	0.798	-0.152		
PT09P1	297						sad	-1.416 -2.090 0.003
PT09P1	297						max	0.009 0.333 0.248
PT09P1	297						sad	1.423 2.775 0.003
PT09P2	248	-0.099	0.555	0.987	0.794	-0.006		
PT09P2	248						max	-0.071 0.465 0.227
PT09P3	281	0.031	0.578	0.948	0.809	-0.065		
PT09P3	281						max	0.529 0.634 0.238
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PT09P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PT09P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PT09P3</p> </div> </div>								
PT09P	826							
PT09P Sig.		0.672	0.062				0.369	0.159

PT10	2021-08-17–2022-03-04							
PT10P1	507	0.007	0.521	1.036	0.750	-0.130		
PT10P1	507						max	0.331 0.556 0.279
PT10P1	507						sad	-2.868 2.400 0.009
PT10P2	402	0.035	0.417	0.925	0.853	0.048		
PT10P2	402						max	0.279 0.545 0.216
PT10P3	481	0.146	0.552	0.901	0.765	-0.142		
PT10P3	481						sad	0.562 -2.520 0.003
PT10P3	481						max	0.465 0.579 0.263
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PT10P1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PT10P2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>PT10P3</p> </div> </div>								
PT10P	1390							
PT10P Sig.		0.060	0.032				0.110	0.389

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Sweden								
SE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
SE05P1	299	0.532	0.297	0.822	0.822	0.078		
SE05P1	299						max 0.844	0.726
SE05P1	299						sad -3.006	1.033
SE05P2	574	0.570	0.382	0.807	0.835	0.078		
SE05P2	574						max 0.845	0.638
SE05P3	258	0.539	0.568	0.776	0.824	0.059		
SE05P3	258						max 0.880	0.815
								0.305
SE05P	1131							
SE05P Sig.		0.410	0.533				0.362	0.774
SE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
SE06P1	423	0.320	0.328	0.884	0.848	-0.014		
SE06P1	423						max 0.585	0.461
SE06P1	423						sad -3.004	1.722
SE06P2	763	0.384	0.269	0.865	0.878	0.028		
SE06P2	763						max 0.705	0.397
SE06P3	358	0.634	0.516	0.870	0.834	-0.160		
SE06P3	358						max 0.895	0.749
								0.286
SE06P	1544							
SE06P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	0.033

SE05P1

SE05P2

SE05P3

SE06P1

SE06P2

SE06P3

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
SE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
SE07P1	393	0.549	0.395	0.943	0.828	0.077			
SE07P1	393					max	0.811	0.773	0.240
SE07P1	393					min	-3.803	-0.047	0.000
SE07P1	393					sad	-2.545	1.962	0.004
SE07P2	721	0.595	0.342	0.853	0.817	0.103			
SE07P2	721					max	0.950	0.603	0.272
SE07P3	322	0.580	0.508	0.809	0.841	0.020			
SE07P3	322					max	0.886	0.853	0.266
SE07P3	322					sad	-1.962	2.160	0.004
SE07P	1436								
SE07P Sig.		0.004	0.957				0.030	0.621	
<hr/>									
SE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
SE08P1	427	0.457	0.228	0.855	0.932	0.271			
SE08P1	427					max	0.902	0.590	0.226
SE08P2	518	0.495	0.337	0.811	0.823	0.144			
SE08P2	518					max	0.929	0.611	0.309
SE08P3	298	0.623	0.466	0.755	0.862	0.154			
SE08P3	298					max	1.026	0.725	0.296
SE08P	1242								
SE08P Sig.		<0.0005	0.002				<0.0005	0.100	

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

SE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
SE09P1	146	0.606	0.238	0.795	0.828	0.106		
SE09P1	146						max 0.923	0.571 0.278
SE09P2	833	0.571	0.360	0.837	0.854	0.146		
SE09P2	833						max 0.955	0.671 0.257
SE09P3	314	0.591	0.420	0.804	0.911	0.041		
SE09P3	314						max 1.033	0.821 0.267
SE09P	1293							
SE09P Sig.		0.004	0.015				0.107	0.038

Slovenia								
SI05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
SI05P1	361	-0.625	-0.234	0.936	0.829	0.048		
SI05P1	361						max -0.950	-0.319 0.201
SI05P2	428	-0.480	-0.017	1.024	0.902	-0.065		
SI05P2	428						max -0.647	-0.035 0.166
SI05P3	241	-0.385	0.324	1.040	0.889	-0.021		
SI05P3	241						max -0.718	0.366 0.180
SI05P	1030							
SI05P Sig.		0.023	0.119				0.011	0.146

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>										
SI06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
SI06P1	356	-0.327	0.219	0.990	0.887	-0.089				
SI06P1	356					max	-0.114	0.393	0.164	
SI06P2	332	-0.456	0.105	0.995	0.953	-0.034				
SI06P2	332					max	-0.502	0.123	0.152	
SI06P3	224	-0.631	0.406	0.948	0.833	-0.202				
SI06P3	224					max	-0.040	0.343	0.189	
SI06P	912									
SI06P Sig.		<0.0005	0.038				0.002	0.132		
<hr style="border-top: 1px dashed black;"/>										
SI07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
SI07P1	290	-0.448	0.015	0.938	0.840	0.106				
SI07P1	290					max	-0.987	-0.001	0.220	
SI07P2	321	-0.574	0.037	0.886	0.856	0.002				
SI07P2	321					max	-0.908	0.074	0.205	
SI07P3	251	-0.588	0.227	0.934	0.931	0.120				
SI07P3	251					max	-0.040	0.395	0.180	
SI07P	862									
SI07P Sig.		0.624	0.308				0.619	0.600		

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
SI08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
SI08P1	383	-0.373	-0.287	0.954	0.957	0.016		
SI08P1	383						max	-0.645 -0.417 0.168
SI08P2	448	-0.314	-0.137	0.985	0.918	<0.0005		
SI08P2	448						max	-0.295 -0.126 0.188
SI08P3	268	-0.383	0.090	0.891	0.882	-0.073		
SI08P3	268						max	-0.486 0.125 0.188
SI08P	1099							
SI08P Sig.		0.797	0.164					
							0.337	0.150
<hr/>								
SI09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
SI09P1	376	-0.363	-0.301	0.979	0.975	0.041		
SI09P1	376						max	-0.372 -0.382 0.147
SI09P2	388	-0.363	-0.200	1.062	0.967	-0.016		
SI09P2	388						max	-0.525 -0.314 0.148
SI09P3	255	-0.418	0.053	0.986	0.887	0.058		
SI09P3	255						max	-0.103 0.372 0.171
SI09P	1019							
SI09P Sig.		0.011	0.550					
							0.011	0.183

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
SI10	2020-09-18–2021-08-24							
SI10P1	362	-0.291	-0.022	1.015	0.984	-0.089		
SI10P1	362						max	-0.141 0.084 0.148
SI10P1	362						sad	-2.399 3.643 0.002
SI10P2	403	-0.228	-0.036	1.002	0.939	-0.020		
SI10P2	403						sad	-1.667 -3.157 0.004
SI10P2	403						max	-0.117 -0.023 0.167
SI10P2	403						sad	1.381 3.497 0.001
SI10P3	264	-0.165	0.194	0.992	1.001	-0.151		
SI10P3	264						max	-0.022 0.313 0.148
SI10P1								
SI10P2								
SI10P3								
SI10P	1030							
SI10P Sig.		0.140	0.267				0.797	0.576
SI11	2023-03-21–2023-08-14							
SI11P1	292	0.021	0.027	0.992	0.871	0.139		
SI11P1	292						max	0.615 0.154 0.197
SI11P2	445	-0.012	0.012	1.029	0.910	-0.021		
SI11P2	445						max	0.457 0.087 0.169
SI11P3	202	-0.079	0.320	1.064	0.893	-0.049		
SI11P3	202						max	0.690 0.512 0.161
SI11P1								
SI11P2								
SI11P3								
SI11P	938							
SI11P Sig.		0.943	0.063				0.727	0.297

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Slovakia								
SK05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
SK05P1	760	-0.134	0.113	1.030	0.804	-0.201		
SK05P1	760					max	-0.093	0.092 0.227
SK05P2	336	-0.093	-0.016	0.983	0.837	-0.430		
SK05P2	336					sad	2.347	-2.857 0.004
SK05P2	336					min	0.341	-3.341 0.001
SK05P2	336					max	0.045	0.122 0.242
SK05P3	364	-0.182	-0.096	0.967	1.031	-0.328		
SK05P3	364					max	-0.024	-0.301 0.168
SK05P3	364					sad	-3.164	-0.879 0.005

SK05P 1460

SK05P Sig. <0.0005 0.268

<0.0005 0.231

SK06 2012-01-01–2013-12-31

SK06P1	739	-0.408	0.065	1.066	0.890	-0.166		
SK06P1	739					sad	-1.623	-3.496 0.001
SK06P1	739					max	-0.782	0.127 0.195
SK06P2	409	-0.559	-0.376	0.978	1.010	0.086		
SK06P2	409					max	-0.994	-0.478 0.161
SK06P3	355	-0.332	-0.093	1.098	0.995	-0.352		
SK06P3	355					sad	-1.402	-3.128 0.002
SK06P3	355					max	-0.867	0.278 0.208
SK06P3	355					sad	1.511	2.463 0.002

SK06P 1503

SK06P Sig. <0.0005 <0.0005

<0.0005 <0.0005

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
SK09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
SK09P1	442	0.042	-0.428	1.350	0.988	-0.281			
SK09P1	442						max	-0.575	-0.346 0.135
SK09P2	267	0.196	-0.572	1.312	1.040	-0.349			
SK09P2	267						max	0.447	-1.015 0.116
SK09P3	218	-0.008	-0.370	1.096	0.949	-0.151			
SK09P3	218						sad	4.023	-0.538 0.006
SK09P3	218						max	-0.076	-0.679 0.155
SK09P3	218						sad	-5.592	0.003 0.000
SK09P	926								
SK09P Sig.		0.835	<0.0005					0.090	<0.0005
<hr/>									
SK10	2021-05-26–2021-10-31								
SK10P1	512	-0.042	-0.412	1.177	1.077	0.026			
SK10P1	512						max	-0.797	-0.803 0.125
SK10P2	296	0.118	-0.374	1.038	0.845	0.178			
SK10P2	296						max	0.548	0.048 0.194
SK10P3	241	-0.288	-0.035	0.971	0.977	0.141			
SK10P3	241						sad	2.648	-1.575 0.006
SK10P3	241						max	-0.735	-0.294 0.161
SK10P	1049								
SK10P Sig.		0.213	0.016					0.006	0.125

SK09P1

SK09P2

SK09P3

SK10P1

SK10P2

SK10P3

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Table 3: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Purchase Power (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
SK11	2023-09-10–2023-12-11								
SK11P1	496	0.202	-0.518	1.179	1.091	0.149			
SK11P1	496						max	-0.598 -1.387 0.135	
SK11P2	370	0.433	-0.618	1.211	1.067	-0.104			
SK11P2	370						max	0.813 -0.375 0.115	
SK11P3	273	0.035	-0.702	0.855	0.785	0.091			
SK11P3	273						sad	3.471 -1.202 0.001	
SK11P3	273						max	-0.155 -1.030 0.273	
SK11P3	273						sad	-2.659 0.481 0.003	

SK11P1

SK11P2

SK11P3

SK11P	1140			
SK11P Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005	<0.0005 0.004

4 Results from the European Social Survey: Distributions of the Trust and Immigration Factors in Selected European Countries and Different Degrees of Population Density

The first two characters of the region code code for the country, the next two for the ESS wave. Degrees of purchase power are coded in the last character of the region code. The purchase power in NUTS-3 regions were taken from [?], weighted with the NUTS-3 population and assigned to the regions used in the ESS. These were then recoded in three groups of approximately equal size within each country, such that group 1 contains the regions with the lowest purchase power (< 0.87 of the country mean) and group 3 contains the regions with the highest purchase power (≥ 1.09 of the country mean).

The diagrams show the estimated two-dimensional distributions of the two factors — truth in political institutions is the horizontal dimension, sympathy for immigrants is the vertical dimension. x_m and y_m are the coordinates of maxima or addles of the bimodal distributions. $f(x_m, y_m)$ is the value of the distribution function at such a point.

Table rows starting with P contain the significance level of the mean differences (in columns $\mu(x)$ and $\mu(y)$) and the significance yielded by the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test between the one-dimensional distributions in purchase power classes 1 and 3 (in columns mode(x) and mode(y)). If the significance level is below 0.05, the entry is marked in yellow. The numbers of respondents (weighted countrywise) interviewed within the respective region groups can be found in the middle of these rows.

Table 4: Parameters of two-dimensional distributions of Trust and Immigration factors — Population Density

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Albania								
AL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
AL06D1	526	0.346	0.678	1.103	1.094	-0.010		
AL06D1	526						max	0.391 1.038 0.124
AL06D2	97	0.016	0.822	1.164	1.205	-0.032		
AL06D2	97						max	-0.343 1.796 0.107
AL06D3	248	0.066	0.926	1.052	0.973	0.056		
AL06D3	248						max	0.174 1.097 0.168
AL06D	871							
AL06D Sig.		0.001	0.010				<0.0005	0.234

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Austria									
AT07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
AT07D1	850	-0.102	-0.296	1.036	0.923	0.117			
AT07D1	850					max	-0.046	-0.196	0.178
AT07D2	305	-0.052	-0.420	1.274	0.897	0.178			
AT07D2	305					max	0.908	0.057	0.145
AT07D2	305					max	-1.325	-1.264	0.140
AT07D2	305					sad	-0.441	-0.328	0.121
AT07D3	318	0.134	0.271	1.189	0.969	-0.012			
AT07D3	318					max	-0.129	0.415	0.140
AT07D	1473								
AT07D Sig.		0.006	<0.0005				0.274	<0.0005	
AT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
AT08D1	924	-0.037	-0.466	1.006	0.955	0.195			
AT08D1	924					sad	1.616	-3.692	0.001
AT08D1	924					max	0.028	-0.363	0.173
AT08D2	378	0.028	-0.495	1.098	1.000	0.260			
AT08D2	378					sad	2.528	-2.960	0.003
AT08D2	378					max	-0.366	-0.734	0.149
AT08D3	379	0.217	-0.022	1.172	1.108	-0.102			
AT08D3	379					max	-0.041	0.262	0.110
AT08D	1681								
AT08D Sig.		0.001	<0.0005				0.078	<0.0005	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

AT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
AT09D1	1181	0.159	-0.403	0.995	1.021	0.033			
AT09D1	1181					max	0.363	-0.325	0.161
AT09D2	359	0.138	-0.324	0.913	1.107	0.180			
AT09D2	359					max	-0.081	-0.140	0.128
AT09D3	537	0.234	0.213	1.032	1.019	0.095			
AT09D3	537					max	0.798	0.758	0.169
AT09D	2077								
AT09D Sig.		0.254	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005	

AT11	2023-06-13–2023-12-03								
AT11D1	1181	0.120	-0.150	1.059	0.905	0.110			
AT11D1	1181					sad	3.307	-2.072	0.002
AT11D1	1181					min	1.372	-3.616	0.000
AT11D1	1181					sad	-1.422	-3.291	0.004
AT11D1	1181					max	0.072	-0.110	0.206
AT11D1	1181					sad	1.172	3.497	0.001
AT11D1	1181					min	-0.968	3.406	0.000
AT11D2	397	0.059	-0.053	1.067	1.071	0.247			
AT11D2	397					max	0.808	0.466	0.119
AT11D2	397					sad	-0.425	-0.438	0.104
AT11D2	397					max	-0.543	-0.532	0.104
AT11D3	426	0.200	0.064	1.043	0.903	0.091			
AT11D3	426					max	0.431	0.222	0.195
AT11D3	426					sad	-2.535	2.174	0.003
AT11D	2004								
AT11D Sig.		0.001	<0.0005				0.006	0.012	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Belgium										
BE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
BE05D1	46	0.146	-0.136	0.944	0.809	0.108				
BE05D1	46					sad	-0.384	-1.331	0.058	
BE05D1	46					max	0.820	0.408	0.474	
BE05D1	46					max	-1.448	-1.255	0.098	
BE05D1	46					min	-0.772	-0.302	0.032	
BE05D1	46					sad	-1.438	-0.100	0.037	
BE05D2	76	0.151	-0.057	0.939	0.653	0.085				
BE05D2	76					sad	0.515	-3.165	0.001	
BE05D2	76					max	0.197	0.006	0.308	
BE05D2	76					sad	-1.779	1.959	0.007	
BE05D3	1345	0.015	-0.102	0.973	0.798	0.085				
BE05D3	1345					max	0.380	0.080	0.255	
BE05D3	1345					sad	-2.725	1.849	0.003	
BE05D	1467									
BE05D Sig.		0.343	0.850				0.515	0.201		
BE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
BE06D1	51	-0.067	-0.288	1.157	0.809	0.544				
BE06D1	51						max	0.917	0.050	0.388
BE06D1	51						sad	-0.761	-0.596	0.088
BE06D1	51						max	-1.956	-1.342	0.190
BE06D2	72	0.235	-0.297	0.986	0.828	-0.110				
BE06D2	72						max	0.248	-0.566	0.196
BE06D3	1522	0.180	-0.099	0.957	0.791	0.102				
BE06D3	1522						max	0.595	0.140	0.281
BE06D	1645									
BE06D Sig.		0.255	0.216				0.673	0.959		

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	

BE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
BE07D1	49	0.107	-0.185	1.005	0.855	0.189			
BE07D1	49					max	0.487	-0.098	0.221
BE07D2	71	-0.244	-0.321	0.984	1.061	0.064			
BE07D2	71					max	0.652	0.294	0.217
BE07D2	71					max	-1.464	-1.862	0.077
BE07D2	71					sad	-1.054	-0.884	0.056
BE07D3	1438	0.124	-0.126	1.010	0.821	0.144			
BE07D3	1438					max	0.602	0.154	0.244
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE07D1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE07D2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE07D3</p> </div> </div>									
BE07D	1558								
BE07D Sig.		0.141	0.559				0.006	<0.0005	

BE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
BE08D1	53	-0.328	-0.001	0.991	0.835	0.162			
BE08D1	53					max	0.373	0.324	0.312
BE08D2	98	-0.068	-0.048	0.911	0.777	0.117			
BE08D2	98					max	0.707	-0.306	0.284
BE08D2	98					sad	-0.275	0.340	0.147
BE08D2	98					max	-1.026	0.385	0.170
BE08D3	1433	0.077	0.021	0.985	0.817	0.074			
BE08D3	1433					max	0.638	0.228	0.272
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE08D1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE08D2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>BE08D3</p> </div> </div>									
BE08D	1585								
BE08D Sig.		0.006	0.715				<0.0005	<0.0005	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
BE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
BE09D1	38	-0.102	0.171	0.986	0.748	-0.003			
BE09D1	38					sad	1.212	-1.810	0.009
BE09D1	38					max	0.804	0.507	0.331
BE09D1	38					sad	-0.511	0.260	0.111
BE09D1	38					max	-1.562	-0.350	0.342
BE09D1	38					sad	-1.716	2.867	0.004
BE09D2	67	-0.086	0.185	0.929	0.908	-0.128			
BE09D2	67					sad	1.480	-2.724	0.001
BE09D2	67					max	0.734	0.372	0.235
BE09D2	67					sad	-0.325	0.490	0.188
BE09D2	67					max	-0.684	0.473	0.191
BE09D2	67					sad	-2.109	3.577	0.001
BE09D3	1420	0.174	0.097	0.916	0.799	0.114			
BE09D3	1420					sad	-0.091	-4.132	0.000
BE09D3	1420					max	0.606	0.251	0.298

BE09D1

BE09D2

BE09D3

BE09D	1525							
BE09D Sig.		0.017	0.594				<0.0005	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$			
<hr/>											
BE10	2021-10-28–2022-09-02										
BE10D1	31	-0.052	0.091	0.878	0.871	0.305					
BE10D1	31						max	0.853	-0.026	0.506	
BE10D1	31						sad	-0.313	-0.546	0.099	
BE10D1	31						max	-1.236	-0.983	0.235	
BE10D1	31						min	-0.231	0.555	0.057	
BE10D1	31						sad	0.022	0.995	0.060	
BE10D1	31						sad	-0.717	0.422	0.065	
BE10D1	31						max	-0.676	1.680	0.179	
BE10D2	57	0.178	0.213	0.880	0.759	0.015					
BE10D2	57						max	0.469	-0.190	0.249	
BE10D3	1029	0.104	0.227	1.002	0.784	0.086					
BE10D3	1029						max	0.631	0.416	0.258	
<hr/>											
BE10D	1117										
BE10D Sig.		0.584	0.631			0.005	<0.0005				
<hr/>											
Bulgaria											
BG05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31										
BG05D1	1018	-0.237	0.587	1.087	1.038	-0.147					
BG05D1	1018						max	-0.249	0.680	0.152	
BG05D3	300	-0.432	0.631	1.005	0.931	-0.186					
BG05D3	300						sad	1.364	-3.305	0.001	
BG05D3	300						max	-0.748	0.656	0.177	
<hr/>											
BG05D	1318										
BG05D Sig.		0.025	0.263			0.251	0.158				

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

BG06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
BG06D1	1026	-0.452	0.525	1.091	1.071	-0.109		
BG06D1	1026						max	-0.616 0.534 0.143
BG06D3	226	-0.272	0.195	0.906	0.784	-0.296		
BG06D3	226						max	0.239 -0.298 0.324
BG06D3	226						sad	-2.181 -1.725 0.003
BG06D3	226						sad	0.493 2.759 0.007
BG06D3	226						sad	-4.119 -0.082 0.001
BG06D	1251							
BG06D Sig.		0.021	<0.0005					<0.0005 <0.0005

BG09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
BG09D1	828	-0.499	-0.026	1.130	1.096	-0.071		
BG09D1	828						max	-0.956 -0.259 0.140
BG09D3	197	-0.617	-0.325	0.888	1.089	-0.204		
BG09D3	197						max	0.258 -0.190 0.176
BG09D3	197						sad	-0.493 -1.089 0.088
BG09D3	197						max	-1.578 -1.484 0.201
BG09D	1024							
BG09D Sig.		0.171	0.001					<0.0005 <0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

BG10	2021-06-28–2021-09-30							
BG10D1	1888	-0.437	0.169	1.005	1.054	-0.049		
BG10D1	1888						max	-0.672 0.281 0.138
BG10D3	250	-0.459	0.192	1.117	1.287	0.008		
BG10D3	250						max	-1.005 -0.546 0.092
BG10D	2138					" "		
BG10D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					<0.0005 <0.0005
Switzerland								
CH05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
CH05D1	150	0.175	0.065	0.848	0.711	-0.183		
CH05D1	150						max	0.515 0.001 0.323
CH05D1	150						sad	0.504 2.983 0.002
CH05D2	636	0.261	0.096	0.933	0.857	-0.048		
CH05D2	636						max	0.572 0.279 0.230
CH05D3	347	0.342	0.054	0.858	0.789	-0.155		
CH05D3	347						sad	1.883 -3.015 0.002
CH05D3	347						max	0.610 0.119 0.278
CH05D3	347						sad	-0.602 3.637 0.000
CH05D	1133							
CH05D Sig.		<0.0005	0.190					

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

CH06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
CH06D1	144	0.234	-0.067	0.766	0.713	-0.112		
CH06D1	144						sad	1.059 -2.875 0.003
CH06D1	144						max	0.660 -0.021 0.365
CH06D2	672	0.373	0.030	0.867	0.825	-0.031		
CH06D2	672						max	0.763 0.173 0.263
CH06D3	352	0.346	-0.056	0.807	0.755	0.014		
CH06D3	352						max	0.583 0.009 0.296
CH06D	1168							
CH06D Sig.		0.169	0.212					

CH07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
CH07D1	171	0.358	-0.066	0.839	0.634	0.099		
CH07D1	171						max	0.496 -0.099 0.342
CH07D2	692	0.313	0.019	0.858	0.815	-0.009		
CH07D2	692						max	0.574 0.185 0.273
CH07D3	359	0.379	0.028	0.792	0.793	-0.046		
CH07D3	359						max	0.550 0.091 0.280
CH07D	1222							
CH07D Sig.		0.437	0.038					

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
CH08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
CH08D1	159	0.394	-0.229	0.900	0.806	0.109		
CH08D1	159						max 0.844	-0.211 0.288
CH08D1	159						sad -2.663	-1.917 0.004
CH08D2	684	0.321	0.028	0.865	0.802	-0.002		
CH08D2	684						max 0.583	0.193 0.264
CH08D3	371	0.391	-0.089	0.860	0.883	-0.034		
CH08D3	371						max 0.582	0.075 0.239
CH08D3	371						sad -2.184	2.219 0.002
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CH08D1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CH08D2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CH08D3</p> </div> </div>								
CH08D	1214							
CH08D Sig.		0.011	0.023					
<hr/>								
CH09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
CH09D1	152	0.416	-0.069	0.785	0.803	-0.052		
CH09D1	152						sad 2.099	-2.811 0.001
CH09D1	152						max 0.528	-0.036 0.310
CH09D1	152						sad -2.667	-1.009 0.002
CH09D1	152						sad -1.025	2.790 0.001
CH09D2	603	0.420	0.031	0.881	0.754	0.012		
CH09D2	603						max 0.690	0.069 0.294
CH09D3	353	0.374	0.013	0.857	0.826	-0.021		
CH09D3	353						max 0.642	0.198 0.267
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: flex-start;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CH09D1</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CH09D2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>CH09D3</p> </div> </div>								
CH09D	1108							
CH09D Sig.		0.602	0.172					

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

CH10	2021-05-05–2022-05-02							
CH10D1	140	0.271	-0.129	0.788	0.665	0.113		
CH10D1	140						sad	2.868 -1.343 0.005
CH10D1	140						sad	0.424 -3.276 0.001
CH10D1	140						max	0.681 0.160 0.328
CH10D2	700	0.500	0.206	0.857	0.765	0.068		
CH10D2	700						sad	1.030 -3.145 0.001
CH10D2	700						max	0.794 0.342 0.321
CH10D3	352	0.443	0.104	0.905	0.853	-0.081		
CH10D3	352						max	0.773 0.270 0.253
CH10D	1192							
CH10D Sig.		0.264	0.143					

CH11	2023-03-11–2024-01-31							
CH11D1	126	0.439	-0.095	0.808	0.775	0.189		
CH11D1	126						max	1.023 -0.197 0.316
CH11D1	126						sad	-0.806 -0.788 0.072
CH11D1	126						max	-1.442 -1.193 0.078
CH11D2	627	0.479	0.195	0.819	0.778	0.063		
CH11D2	627						max	0.794 0.314 0.293
CH11D3	287	0.459	0.069	0.825	0.719	0.139		
CH11D3	287						max	0.798 0.339 0.326
CH11D	1040							
CH11D Sig.		0.856	<0.0005					

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Cyprus								
CY05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
CY05D1	728	0.087	-0.572	1.092	0.939	-0.195		
CY05D1	728						max 0.237	-0.873 0.171
CY05D	728					" "		" "
CY05D Sig.								
CY06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
CY06D1	846	-0.280	-0.819	1.094	0.949	-0.072		
CY06D1	846						max -0.619	-1.242 0.154
CY06D	846					" "		" "
CY06D Sig.								
CY09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
CY09D1	656	-0.182	-0.254	0.889	0.886	-0.109		
CY09D1	656						max -0.011	-0.180 0.190
CY09D	656					" "		" "
CY09D Sig.								

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
Czech Republic										
CZ05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
CZ05D1	567	-0.235	-0.332	1.005	0.887	-0.069				
CZ05D1	567						max	-0.409	-0.330	0.196
CZ05D2	1098	-0.247	-0.240	1.025	0.907	-0.089				
CZ05D2	1098						max	-0.524	-0.322	0.189
CZ05D3	231	-0.156	-0.326	0.995	0.875	-0.216				
CZ05D3	231						max	-0.724	0.014	0.159
		CZ05D1			CZ05D2			CZ05D3		
CZ05D	1896									
CZ05D Sig.		0.462	0.098					0.163	0.351	
CZ06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31									
CZ06D1	388	-0.219	-0.164	1.140	0.986	-0.354				
CZ06D1	388						max	-0.859	0.325	0.144
CZ06D2	801	-0.491	-0.244	1.093	0.921	-0.102				
CZ06D2	801						max	-0.918	-0.301	0.194
CZ06D3	200	0.152	-0.303	1.104	0.952	-0.260				
CZ06D3	200						max	-0.676	0.112	0.179
		CZ06D1			CZ06D2			CZ06D3		
CZ06D	1389									
CZ06D Sig.		<0.0005	0.193					<0.0005	0.438	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
<hr/>										
CZ07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31									
CZ07D1	451	-0.180	-0.450	1.146	0.764	-0.044				
CZ07D1	451						max	-0.428 -0.386 0.232		
CZ07D2	872	-0.197	-0.482	1.010	0.811	-0.077				
CZ07D2	872						max	-0.219 -0.392 0.202		
CZ07D3	158	0.121	-0.632	1.229	0.885	-0.252				
CZ07D3	158						max	1.102 -0.723 0.215		
CZ07D3	158						sad	-1.961 -2.562 0.015		
CZ07D3	158						sad	-0.392 -0.389 0.132		
CZ07D3	158						max	-1.099 -0.338 0.142		
<hr/>										
CZ07D	1481									
CZ07D Sig.		0.003	0.047				<0.0005	0.017		
<hr/>										
CZ08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31									
CZ08D1	564	-0.073	-0.492	1.090	0.784	-0.015				
CZ08D1	564						max	0.180 -0.315 0.205		
CZ08D2	1177	0.089	-0.614	1.042	0.882	0.035				
CZ08D2	1177						max	0.222 -0.499 0.163		
CZ08D3	239	-0.068	-0.747	1.097	0.915	0.018				
CZ08D3	239						max	-0.078 -0.877 0.151		
<hr/>										
CZ08D	1980									
CZ08D Sig.		0.004	<0.0005				0.045	0.002		

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

CZ09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
CZ09D1	484	-0.023	-0.491	1.176	0.798	0.104		
CZ09D1	484						max	0.641 -0.098 0.150
CZ09D1	484						sad	0.399 -0.167 0.149
CZ09D1	484						max	-0.818 -0.589 0.163
CZ09D2	1136	0.021	-0.594	1.114	0.939	0.118		
CZ09D2	1136						max	0.247 -0.326 0.154
CZ09D3	232	-0.105	-0.582	1.023	0.984	0.274		
CZ09D3	232						max	-0.337 -0.961 0.174
CZ09D	1852							
CZ09D Sig.		0.051	0.416				0.015	0.039

CZ10	2021-07-07–2021-09-26							
CZ10D1	551	0.224	-0.458	1.188	1.024	0.193		
CZ10D1	551						max	-1.146 -1.597 0.115
CZ10D1	551						sad	-0.150 -0.735 0.079
CZ10D1	551						max	0.997 0.386 0.151
CZ10D2	1110	0.333	-0.284	1.174	0.958	0.144		
CZ10D2	1110						max	1.132 0.197 0.165
CZ10D3	271	0.050	-0.238	1.020	1.017	0.064		
CZ10D3	271						max	0.185 0.073 0.144
CZ10D	1932							
CZ10D Sig.		0.389	0.090				0.225	0.069

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Germany									
DE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
DE05D1	208	-0.254	-0.349	0.892	0.931	0.096			
DE05D1	208					max	-0.348	-0.371	0.180
DE05D2	1005	-0.089	-0.019	0.883	0.851	0.025			
DE05D2	1005					max	-0.041	0.014	0.205
DE05D3	1152	0.038	0.077	0.922	0.901	0.091			
DE05D3	1152					max	0.119	0.208	0.207
DE05D	2364								
DE05D Sig.		0.001	0.026				0.006	0.005	
DE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
DE06D1	205	-0.003	-0.025	0.915	0.845	0.107			
DE06D1	205					max	0.225	-0.030	0.196
DE06D2	1044	-0.001	0.082	0.901	0.849	0.015			
DE06D2	1044					max	0.156	0.133	0.227
DE06D3	1302	0.120	0.168	0.831	0.843	0.071			
DE06D3	1302					sad	1.246	-2.962	0.002
DE06D3	1302					max	0.279	0.269	0.245
DE06D	2551								
DE06D Sig.		0.582	0.267				<0.0005	0.001	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
DE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
DE07D1	214	-0.213	-0.219	1.084	0.968	0.161		
DE07D1	214						max 0.571	0.130 0.132
DE07D1	214						sad -0.099	-0.089 0.128
DE07D1	214						max -1.038	-0.482 0.138
DE07D2	1069	-0.002	0.004	0.925	0.817	0.059		
DE07D2	1069						max 0.226	0.130 0.223
DE07D3	1363	0.078	0.104	0.930	0.882	0.126		
DE07D3	1363						max 0.343	0.259 0.213
DE07D	2646							
DE07D Sig.		0.485	0.700				0.249	0.065
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DE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
DE08D1	189	-0.039	-0.184	0.953	0.949	0.228		
DE08D1	189						max 0.579	0.167 0.183
DE08D2	1075	0.064	-0.123	0.955	0.869	0.162		
DE08D2	1075						max 0.329	0.001 0.192
DE08D3	1321	0.159	0.062	0.893	0.868	0.049		
DE08D3	1321						max 0.494	0.227 0.217
DE08D	2585							
DE08D Sig.		0.126	0.029				<0.0005	0.010

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
DE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
DE09D1	164	-0.166	-0.265	0.953	0.958	0.150		
DE09D1	164						max	0.527 0.275 0.157
DE09D2	872	0.014	0.002	0.950	0.929	0.113		
DE09D2	872						max	0.325 0.246 0.170
DE09D3	1045	0.209	0.126	0.920	0.892	0.182		
DE09D3	1045						max	0.567 0.418 0.213
DE09D	2082							
DE09D Sig.		0.021	0.152					0.028 0.624
<hr/>								
DE11	2023-05-12–2023-12-17							
DE11D1	167	-0.102	-0.200	0.982	0.845	0.207		
DE11D1	167						max	0.590 0.104 0.173
DE11D2	847	0.245	-0.012	0.980	0.845	0.277		
DE11D2	847						max	0.637 0.166 0.229
DE11D2	847						sad	-2.023 1.782 0.005
DE11D3	1155	0.351	0.111	0.991	0.872	0.234		
DE11D3	1155						max	0.887 0.445 0.223
DE11D	2169							
DE11D Sig.		0.271	0.064					0.008 0.095

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Denmark								
DK05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
DK05D1	896	0.539	-0.095	0.835	0.895	-0.007		
DK05D1	896						max 0.739	0.069 0.222
DK05D3	386	0.528	0.266	0.866	0.899	-0.143		
DK05D3	386						max 0.944	0.393 0.237
DK05D	1282						" "	
DK05D Sig.		0.833	<0.0005				0.656	<0.0005
DK06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
DK06D1	950	0.604	-0.078	0.828	0.933	0.142		
DK06D1	950						max 0.866	0.154 0.208
DK06D3	414	0.683	0.331	0.862	0.863	0.016		
DK06D3	414						max 0.924	0.582 0.273
DK06D3	414						sad -2.243	1.841 0.003
DK06D	1364						" "	
DK06D Sig.		<0.0005	0.083				<0.0005	0.704

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
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DK07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
DK07D1	889	0.425	-0.250	0.895	0.935	0.152		
DK07D1	889						max	0.860 0.076 0.192
DK07D3	412	0.592	0.109	0.935	0.913	-0.004		
DK07D3	412						sad	3.033 -2.657 0.001
DK07D3	412						max	0.854 0.403 0.235
DK07D3	412						sad	-2.252 2.008 0.003
DK07D	1301							
DK07D Sig.		<0.0005	0.919					<0.0005 0.914
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DK09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
DK09D1	870	0.569	-0.035	0.840	0.927	0.027		
DK09D1	870						max	0.959 0.265 0.226
DK09D3	393	0.644	-0.083	0.908	0.858	0.019		
DK09D3	393						sad	-1.661 -2.283 0.005
DK09D3	393						max	0.652 0.242 0.229
DK09D	1263							
DK09D Sig.		0.002	0.096					0.001 0.032

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Estonia								
EE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
EE05D1	899	0.162	-0.196	0.969	0.816	-0.119		
EE05D1	899						max 0.345	-0.129 0.227
EE05D2	449	0.295	-0.043	0.894	0.882	-0.148		
EE05D2	449						max 0.432	0.050 0.228
EE05D2	449						sad -3.108	1.231 0.002
EE05D	1348							" "
EE05D Sig.		0.015	0.002				0.003	0.005
EE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
EE06D1	1137	0.106	0.075	0.969	0.892	-0.147		
EE06D1	1137						max 0.123	0.106 0.200
EE06D2	656	0.117	0.091	0.891	0.853	-0.174		
EE06D2	656						max 0.198	0.089 0.220
EE06D	1793							" "
EE06D Sig.		<0.0005	0.011				<0.0005	0.014

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

EE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
EE07D1	898	0.078	0.015	1.003	0.859	-0.061		
EE07D1	898						sad	1.162 -3.588 0.001
EE07D1	898						max	0.194 0.098 0.216
EE07D2	743	0.046	0.044	0.952	0.840	-0.016		
EE07D2	743						min	0.307 -3.898 0.000
EE07D2	743						max	0.306 0.141 0.235
EE07D	1642							" "
EE07D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	0.005

EE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
EE08D1	956	0.111	-0.253	0.965	0.877	0.074		
EE08D1	956						max	0.438 -0.140 0.198
EE08D2	797	0.301	-0.232	0.900	0.896	0.014		
EE08D2	797						max	0.419 -0.089 0.210
EE08D	1754							" "
EE08D Sig.		<0.0005	0.201				<0.0005	0.204

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
EE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
EE09D1	994	0.087	-0.307	0.971	0.854	0.142			
EE09D1	994					max	0.447	-0.123 0.216	
EE09D2	723	0.355	-0.087	0.963	0.839	-0.043			
EE09D2	723					sad	1.763	-3.465 0.001	
EE09D2	723					max	0.589	0.010 0.248	
EE09D	1717							" "	
EE09D Sig.		<0.0005	0.219				<0.0005	0.006	
EE10	2021-06-09–2021-12-31								
EE10D1	736	0.105	-0.189	1.015	0.947	0.018			
EE10D1	736					max	0.467	-0.020 0.175	
EE10D2	632	0.359	0.062	0.909	0.853	0.056			
EE10D2	632					sad	1.043	-3.893 0.001	
EE10D2	632					max	0.655	0.177 0.244	
EE10D	1368							" "	
EE10D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Spain								
ES05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
ES05D1	722	-0.135	0.188	0.968	0.809	0.020		
ES05D1	722					max	0.050	0.311 0.233
ES05D2	449	-0.137	0.161	0.950	0.855	-0.091		
ES05D2	449					max	0.128	0.309 0.214
ES05D3	389	-0.099	0.379	0.963	0.869	-0.109		
ES05D3	389					max	0.426	0.612 0.226
ES05D	1560							
ES05D Sig.		0.806	<0.0005				0.020	<0.0005
ES06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
ES06D1	668	-0.377	0.442	0.974	0.971	-0.195		
ES06D1	668					max	-0.354	0.586 0.167
ES06D2	544	-0.407	0.514	0.976	0.985	-0.104		
ES06D2	544					max	-0.365	0.698 0.161
ES06D3	411	-0.430	0.523	0.980	0.993	-0.057		
ES06D3	411					max	-0.657	0.831 0.158
ES06D	1623							
ES06D Sig.		0.673	0.309				0.029	0.002

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
ES07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
ES07D1	596	-0.222	0.252	1.049	0.916	-0.170		
ES07D1	596					max	-0.377	0.320 0.173
ES07D2	417	-0.262	0.362	0.980	0.959	-0.094		
ES07D2	417					max	-0.382	0.522 0.166
ES07D3	340	-0.264	0.508	1.023	0.984	-0.147		
ES07D3	340					max	-0.296	0.682 0.175
ES07D	1353							
ES07D Sig.		0.760	<0.0005				0.002	0.001
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ES08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
ES08D1	590	-0.212	0.370	1.029	0.938	-0.118		
ES08D1	590					max	-0.036	0.595 0.157
ES08D2	481	-0.376	0.410	1.057	0.995	-0.093		
ES08D2	481					max	-0.421	0.725 0.142
ES08D3	338	-0.296	0.543	1.030	0.940	-0.071		
ES08D3	338					max	0.314	0.718 0.158
ES08D	1410							
ES08D Sig.		0.037	0.028				0.006	0.052

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
ES09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
ES09D1	517	-0.233	0.456	0.965	0.936	0.013				
ES09D1	517					max	-0.093	0.661	0.179	
ES09D2	414	-0.204	0.515	1.020	0.940	-0.084				
ES09D2	414					max	-0.380	0.545	0.173	
ES09D3	282	-0.167	0.634	1.037	0.911	-0.004				
ES09D3	282					max	0.097	0.973	0.189	
ES09D	1213									
ES09D Sig.		0.671	0.036				0.055	0.002		
Finland										
FI05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31									
FI05D1	958	0.469	0.128	0.835	0.715	0.024				
FI05D1	958						max	0.757	0.291	0.330
FI05D2	394	0.468	0.303	0.825	0.770	0.003				
FI05D2	394						max	0.757	0.471	0.299
FI05D	1352									
FI05D Sig.		0.002	0.111				0.171	0.173		

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
FI06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
FI06D1	2058	0.529	0.177	0.828	0.725	0.096		
FI06D1	2058						max 0.930	0.301 0.335
FI06D	2058						" "	" "
FI06D Sig.	0.004							
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FI07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
FI07D1	1922	0.425	0.185	0.898	0.808	0.098		
FI07D1	1922						max 0.860	0.375 0.267
FI07D	1922						" "	" "
FI07D Sig.							0.227	0.539
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FI08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
FI08D1	1817	0.538	0.159	0.912	0.831	0.117		
FI08D1	1817						max 1.000	0.354 0.278
FI08D	1817						" "	" "
FI08D Sig.							0.001	0.462

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

FI09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
FI09D1	1626	0.573	0.170	0.860	0.804	0.214		
FI09D1	1626						max 1.066	0.483 0.331
FI09D	1626					" "		" "
FI09D Sig.	0.143							

FI10	2021-09-01–2022-01-14							
FI10D1	1357	0.776	0.222	0.838	0.799	0.127		
FI10D1	1357						max 1.216	0.494 0.330
FI10D	1357					" "		" "
FI10D Sig.							0.029	0.226

FI11	2023-08-10–2024-01-25							
FI11D1	1435	0.819	0.362	0.807	0.816	0.171		
FI11D1	1435						max 1.164	0.656 0.318
FI11D	1435					" "		" "
FI11D Sig.							0.016	0.142

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
France								
FR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
FR05D1	761	0.047	-0.215	0.890	1.016	-0.017		
FR05D1	761					max	0.252	-0.127 0.153
FR05D2	456	0.048	-0.117	0.934	0.993	-0.026		
FR05D2	456					max	0.226	-0.059 0.161
FR05D3	398	0.022	-0.047	0.993	0.960	0.073		
FR05D3	398					max	0.225	0.133 0.183
FR05D3	398					sad	-2.027	2.592 0.005
FR05D	1614							
FR05D Sig.	0.073	0.852		0.004				0.204
FR06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
FR06D1	834	0.015	-0.298	0.879	0.953	0.159		
FR06D1	834						max	0.168 -0.166 0.183
FR06D2	570	-0.017	-0.046	0.968	0.968	0.051		
FR06D2	570						max	0.367 0.041 0.160
FR06D3	456	0.136	0.096	0.933	0.916	-0.087		
FR06D3	456						max	0.418 0.240 0.193
FR06D	1860							
FR06D Sig.	<0.0005	0.012		<0.0005				0.005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

FR07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
FR07D1	797	-0.071	-0.145	0.924	0.957	0.100		
FR07D1	797						max 0.065	0.050 0.182
FR07D1	797						sad -2.451	2.364 0.003
FR07D2	511	-0.120	-0.094	0.911	1.023	0.120		
FR07D2	511						max 0.185	0.040 0.153
FR07D3	419	0.101	0.246	0.923	0.985	-0.113		
FR07D3	419						max 0.214	0.370 0.175
FR07D	1726							
FR07D Sig.		0.001	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005

FR08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
FR08D1	1009	-0.162	-0.138	0.910	0.981	0.080		
FR08D1	1009						max 0.071	0.079 0.157
FR08D2	423	-0.073	-0.036	0.914	0.994	0.017		
FR08D2	423						max 0.269	0.139 0.175
FR08D3	470	0.011	0.227	0.935	0.976	0.052		
FR08D3	470						max 0.644	0.460 0.204
FR08D	1902							
FR08D Sig.		0.003	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
FR09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
FR09D1	749	-0.063	-0.065	0.936	0.985	0.101				
FR09D1	749						max	0.545	0.230	0.160
FR09D2	472	0.039	-0.067	0.874	0.948	0.017				
FR09D2	472						max	0.310	0.150	0.199
FR09D3	444	0.213	0.263	0.886	0.989	-0.010				
FR09D3	444						max	0.327	0.456	0.192
FR09D	1665									
FR09D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					0.001	<0.0005	
FR10	2021-01-01–2021-12-31									
FR10D1	759	0.068	-0.057	0.899	1.029	0.093				
FR10D1	759						max	0.408	0.145	0.156
FR10D2	450	0.130	0.134	0.923	0.971	-0.005				
FR10D2	450						max	0.588	0.135	0.190
FR10D3	374	0.176	0.296	0.965	0.963	-0.022				
FR10D3	374						max	0.413	0.520	0.206
FR10D3	374						sad	-2.927	1.890	0.004
FR10D	1583									
FR10D Sig.		<0.0005	0.331					<0.0005	0.366	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Greece								
GR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
GR05D1	1479	-0.688	-0.741	0.986	0.901	-0.009		
GR05D1	1479						max	-1.258 -1.311 0.265
GR05D3	833	-0.640	-0.604	0.904	0.972	-0.079		
GR05D3	833						max	-1.067 -1.132 0.210
		GR05D1				GR05D3		
GR05D	2312						" "	
GR05D Sig.		0.986	0.242				0.016	0.446
GR10	2021-11-21–2022-04-19							
GR10D1	1496	0.260	-0.370	0.877	0.869	-0.030		
GR10D1	1496						sad	2.577 -3.012 0.003
GR10D1	1496						max	0.434 -0.216 0.222
GR10D3	867	0.284	-0.615	0.868	0.883	-0.172		
GR10D3	867						max	0.551 -0.582 0.181
		GR10D1				GR10D3		
GR10D	2363						" "	
GR10D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Croatia								
HR05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
HR05D1	669	-0.675	0.045	1.055	1.020	-0.099		
HR05D1	669						max	-1.030 0.032 0.160
HR05D2	489	-0.868	0.374	0.913	1.037	-0.153		
HR05D2	489						max	-0.914 0.390 0.171
HR05D	1158							" "
HR05D Sig.		<0.0005	0.279				<0.0005	0.002
HR09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
HR09D1	472	-0.775	0.097	1.010	1.227	-0.138		
HR09D1	472						max	-1.156 0.050 0.108
HR09D	472							" "
HR09D Sig.							0.014	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
HR10	2021-05-05–2021-11-13							
HR10D1	988	-0.534	0.312	1.080	1.133	-0.159		
HR10D1	988						max	-0.623 0.510 0.121
HR10D2	113	-0.663	-0.037	1.054	1.265	-0.097		
HR10D2	113						max	-1.497 -0.759 0.104
HR10D3	221	-0.404	0.253	0.985	1.253	-0.170		
HR10D3	221						max	-0.534 0.928 0.110
HR10D	1322							
HR10D Sig.		0.023	0.085				0.049	0.018
<hr/>								
HR11	2023-06-24–2024-01-05							
HR11D1	926	-0.535	0.198	1.028	1.059	-0.080		
HR11D1	926						max	-0.651 0.293 0.138
HR11D2	109	-0.686	-0.270	1.000	0.930	-0.082		
HR11D2	109						max	0.255 -0.490 0.139
HR11D2	109						sad	-0.863 -0.321 0.111
HR11D2	109						max	-1.674 0.344 0.123
HR11D3	274	-0.249	0.181	0.944	1.224	-0.200		
HR11D3	274						max	-0.301 0.608 0.102
HR11D	1309							
HR11D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				0.004	0.501

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Hungary								
HU05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
HU05D1	648	0.242	-0.282	1.076	0.877	-0.064		
HU05D1	648					max	0.184	-0.264 0.183
HU05D2	61	-0.196	-0.275	0.874	0.835	-0.339		
HU05D2	61					max	0.409	-0.213 0.223
HU05D	709							
HU05D Sig.		0.731	0.979					" "
HU06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
HU06D1	898	0.068	-0.177	1.052	0.917	-0.199		
HU06D1	898					sad	1.767	-3.626 0.002
HU06D1	898					max	-0.128	-0.096 0.181
HU06D2	66	-0.187	-0.027	1.091	0.833	-0.126		
HU06D2	66					max	0.943	-0.456 0.194
HU06D2	66					sad	-0.381	0.066 0.101
HU06D2	66					max	-1.455	0.729 0.173
HU06D	964							" "
HU06D Sig.		0.624	0.038					

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

HU07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
HU07D1	652	0.077	-0.315	1.000	0.893	-0.169		
HU07D1	652						sad	2.483
HU07D1	652						min	-0.396
HU07D1	652						max	-0.088
HU07D2	35	-0.314	-0.134	1.268	0.998	-0.042		
HU07D2	35						max	1.440
HU07D2	35						sad	0.158
HU07D2	35						sad	0.909
HU07D2	35						min	0.053
HU07D2	35						max	-1.469
HU07D2	35						sad	-0.104
HU07D2	35						max	1.492
HU07D2	35						sad	-1.562
HU07D2	35						max	-1.901

HU07D	687							
HU07D Sig.		0.024	0.334					" "

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

HU08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
HU08D1	632	0.212	-0.664	0.999	0.867	0.034		
HU08D1	632						max	0.255
HU08D2	32	-1.080	-1.435	1.070	0.870	0.705		
HU08D2	32						sad	1.756
HU08D2	32						min	0.572
HU08D2	32						max	-1.814
HU08D2	32						max	0.734
HU08D2	32						sad	-0.967

HU08D	664							" "
HU08D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					" "

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
HU09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
HU09D1	828	0.580	-0.583	0.911	0.918	0.068		
HU09D1	828						max	0.901 -0.417 0.186
HU09D2	169	0.458	-0.863	1.213	1.119	-0.116		
HU09D2	169						max	0.498 -1.252 0.093
HU09D3	219	0.653	-0.627	0.915	0.964	-0.252		
HU09D3	219						sad	3.865 -1.924 0.003
HU09D3	219						max	0.693 -0.392 0.223
HU09D3	219						sad	-2.027 -1.480 0.004
<hr/>								
HU09D	1217							
HU09D Sig.		<0.0005	0.126					
<hr/>								
HU10	2021-06-10–2021-10-16							
HU10D1	858	0.491	-0.465	0.886	0.937	-0.143		
HU10D1	858						max	0.687 -0.365 0.195
HU10D2	213	0.442	-0.488	1.150	0.960	-0.321		
HU10D2	213						max	1.458 -0.588 0.140
HU10D2	213						sad	1.075 -0.157 0.139
HU10D2	213						max	0.393 0.323 0.142
HU10D3	284	0.657	-0.326	0.798	1.020	-0.269		
HU10D3	284						max	0.569 0.433 0.252
HU10D3	284						sad	-1.441 -1.993 0.006
<hr/>								
HU10D	1355							
HU10D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
HU11	2023-05-06–2023-11-07							
HU11D1	1108	0.380	-0.596	0.961	0.941	-0.068		
HU11D1	1108						max	0.478 -0.558 0.175
HU11D2	245	0.569	-0.732	1.089	1.335	0.076		
HU11D2	245						sad	0.028 -1.771 0.054
HU11D2	245						max	1.337 0.370 0.083
HU11D2	245						max	-0.590 -1.720 0.055
HU11D3	346	0.800	-0.384	0.863	1.355	-0.268		
HU11D3	346						max	0.826 0.413 0.110
HU11D	1699							
HU11D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005					
<hr/>								
Ireland								
IE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
IE09D1	1248	0.211	0.422	0.987	0.892	0.018		
IE09D1	1248						max	0.572 0.608 0.200
IE09D3	495	0.236	0.794	1.042	0.901	0.016		
IE09D3	495						max	0.826 1.172 0.236
IE09D	1743							
IE09D Sig.		<0.0005	0.007					<0.0005 0.008

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
IE10	2021-11-23–2022-08-26								
IE10D1	938	0.361	0.650	1.068	0.877	-0.047			
IE10D1	938						max 0.938	0.865	0.231
IE10D3	408	0.244	0.888	1.110	0.885	0.100			
IE10D3	408						max 1.059	1.123	0.242
IE10D	1346								
IE10D Sig.		0.068	<0.0005					0.733	0.004
<hr/>									
IE11	2023-06-27–2024-01-03								
IE11D1	1178	0.315	0.303	1.087	1.080	0.026			
IE11D1	1178						max 0.760	0.780	0.154
IE11D3	397	0.297	0.723	1.012	0.954	0.052			
IE11D3	397						max 0.644	1.273	0.243
IE11D	1576								
IE11D Sig.		<0.0005	0.084					<0.0005	0.020

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Italy								
IT06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
IT06D1	82	-0.429	-0.064	0.998	1.190	0.044		
IT06D1	82						max 0.591	0.718 0.093
IT06D1	82						max -1.311	-1.437 0.146
IT06D1	82						sad -0.417	0.194 0.055
IT06D2	416	-0.248	0.211	0.990	1.000	0.076		
IT06D2	416						max -0.180	0.391 0.157
IT06D3	204	0.040	0.174	1.074	1.150	-0.062		
IT06D3	204						max 0.141	0.855 0.116

IT06D	703							
IT06D Sig.		<0.0005	0.105				0.057	0.001

IT08 2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
IT08D1	194	-0.466	-0.191	1.109	1.098	-0.010		
IT08D1	194						max -1.371	-1.209 0.184
IT08D2	1136	-0.339	-0.305	0.987	1.017	0.153		
IT08D2	1136						max -0.917	-0.889 0.149
IT08D3	649	-0.239	-0.174	1.049	1.038	0.081		
IT08D3	649						max -0.712	-0.562 0.133

IT08D	1979							
IT08D Sig.		0.015	0.025				0.014	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

IT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
IT09D2	1546	0.042	-0.171	0.954	1.087	0.038		
IT09D2	1546						max	0.199 -0.084 0.137
IT09D3	539	-0.047	-0.138	1.093	1.076	0.109		
IT09D3	539						sad	2.898 -2.621 0.005
IT09D3	539						max	-0.359 -0.284 0.118
IT09D	2085		" "					
IT09D Sig.		0.722	0.002					<0.0005 <0.0005

IT10	2021-10-28–2022-04-26							
IT10D2	1598	0.012	0.006	0.952	0.985	0.086		
IT10D2	1598						max	0.414 0.298 0.152
IT10D3	535	0.083	0.135	0.903	0.874	-0.053		
IT10D3	535						max	0.306 -0.055 0.223
IT10D3	535						sad	-2.965 -1.707 0.003
IT10D	2133		" "					
IT10D Sig.		0.201	0.013					<0.0005 0.001

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Lithuania								
LT05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
LT05D1	1151	-0.361	0.202	1.056	0.927	-0.108		
LT05D1	1151					max	-0.505	0.313 0.164
LT05D	1151					" "		" "
LT05D Sig.	0.004							
LT06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
LT06D1	1322	-0.139	0.192	1.044	0.929	-0.145		
LT06D1	1322					max	-0.066	0.167 0.179
LT06D	1322					" "		" "
LT06D Sig.							<0.0005	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
LT07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31								
LT07D1	1525	0.095	0.179	1.094	0.812	-0.098			
LT07D1	1525					sad	2.080	-3.044	0.001
LT07D1	1525					min	1.435	-3.131	0.001
LT07D1	1525					sad	-0.966	-3.023	0.001
LT07D1	1525					max	0.217	0.229	0.210
LT07D1	1525					sad	-1.659	3.576	0.000
LT07D	1525					" "		" "	
LT07D Sig.							0.072	0.015	
<hr/>									
LT08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31								
LT08D1	1488	0.352	0.029	0.924	0.911	0.059			
LT08D1	1488					sad	1.089	-3.147	0.003
LT08D1	1488					max	0.469	0.130	0.212
LT08D	1488					" "		" "	
LT08D Sig.							<0.0005	<0.0005	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

LT09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
LT09D1	1073	0.042	0.192	1.006	1.011	-0.180		
LT09D1	1073						sad	0.122 -4.130 0.001
LT09D1	1073						max	0.357 0.216 0.174
LT09D1	1073						sad	-2.285 3.379 0.003
LT09D	1073					" "		" "
LT09D Sig.	0							

LT10	2021-07-01–2021-12-15							
LT10D1	1157	0.255	0.128	0.989	0.941	0.113		
LT10D1	1157						sad	1.331 -3.534 0.001
LT10D1	1157						max	0.471 0.209 0.187
LT10D	1157					" "		" "
LT10D Sig.	0							

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

LT11	2023-09-08–2023-12-29							
LT11D1	1014	0.194	0.091	0.952	0.878	-0.008		
LT11D1	1014						sad	1.538 -3.436 0.001
LT11D1	1014						max	0.398 0.206 0.220
LT11D	1014					" "		" "
LT11D Sig.	0.018							

Latvia								
LV09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
LV09D1	468	-0.174	0.289	1.057	0.974	-0.172		
LV09D1	468						max	0.262 0.206 0.155
LV09D3	128	-0.353	0.447	0.935	1.009	-0.230		
LV09D3	128						max	0.447 0.438 0.171
LV09D	596					" "		" "
LV09D Sig.		<0.0005	0.210					<0.0005 0.108

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Makedonia								
MK10	2021-10-25–2022-03-07							
MK10D1	1039	-0.117	-0.292	1.088	1.124	-0.027		
MK10D1	1039						max	-0.200 -0.615 0.118
MK10D3	88	-0.516	-0.102	0.960	1.141	0.151		
MK10D3	88						max	0.346 0.422 0.098
MK10D3	88						sad	-0.201 -0.019 0.092
MK10D3	88						max	-1.366 -1.006 0.149
MK10D3	88						sad	-2.338 3.033 0.006
MK10D	1126							
MK10D Sig.		0.190	0.016					0.096 <0.0005
Netherlands								
NL05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
NL05D2	202	0.431	-0.098	0.733	0.699	0.158		
NL05D2	202						max	0.649 0.135 0.383
NL05D2	202						sad	-2.129 -0.828 0.004
NL05D3	1371	0.472	0.022	0.747	0.685	-0.024		
NL05D3	1371						sad	1.096 -3.070 0.002
NL05D3	1371						max	0.775 0.150 0.444
NL05D	1572							
NL05D Sig.		0.255	0.763					0.149 0.218

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NL06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
NL06D2	203	0.414	0.037	0.752	0.663	0.182		
NL06D2	203						max	0.705 0.151 0.460
NL06D3	1394	0.436	0.073	0.799	0.668	0.097		
NL06D3	1394						max	0.833 0.233 0.448
NL06D	1597		" "					
NL06D Sig.		0.722	0.469				<0.0005	0.007

NL07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
NL07D2	204	0.379	-0.083	0.854	0.612	0.182		
NL07D2	204						max	0.946 -0.087 0.466
NL07D3	1365	0.380	-0.047	0.871	0.713	0.048		
NL07D3	1365						sad	1.338 -3.061 0.001
NL07D3	1365						min	-0.009 -3.337 0.001
NL07D3	1365						max	0.759 0.069 0.377
NL07D	1569		" "					
NL07D Sig.		0.981	0.489				0.162	0.036

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
NL08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
NL08D2	184	0.339	0.025	0.812	0.581	0.016		
NL08D2	184						sad	-0.955 -2.093 0.002
NL08D2	184						max	0.690 0.098 0.518
NL08D2	184						sad	1.171 2.707 0.001
NL08D3	1225	0.439	-0.029	0.791	0.688	0.162		
NL08D3	1225						max	0.802 0.120 0.417
NL08D	1408		" "					
NL08D Sig.		0.113	0.318				0.004	0.023
<hr/>								
NL09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
NL09D2	190	0.523	-0.011	0.805	0.604	0.031		
NL09D2	190						max	1.003 0.132 0.568
NL09D3	1208	0.597	0.036	0.765	0.674	0.147		
NL09D3	1208						sad	0.099 -2.858 0.002
NL09D3	1208						max	0.924 0.152 0.451
NL09D	1398		" "					
NL09D Sig.		0.014	0.818				0.080	0.345

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NL10	2021-10-02–2022-04-03							
NL10D2	157	0.424	0.010	0.831	0.730	0.152		
NL10D2	157						sad	-0.582 -3.105 0.004
NL10D2	157						max	0.982 0.132 0.430
NL10D3	1034	0.577	0.196	0.811	0.653	0.040		
NL10D3	1034						max	0.912 0.318 0.436
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL10D2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL10D3</p> </div> </div>								
NL10D	1191		" "					
NL10D Sig.		0.008	0.151				<0.0005	0.197

NL11	2023-04-02–2023-11-07							
NL11D2	182	0.491	-0.008	0.881	0.758	0.115		
NL11D2	182						sad	1.382 -2.330 0.009
NL11D2	182						max	1.045 0.229 0.359
NL11D3	1226	0.504	0.132	0.847	0.682	0.124		
NL11D3	1226						max	0.894 0.243 0.421
<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-around; align-items: center;"> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL11D2</p> </div> <div style="text-align: center;"> <p>NL11D3</p> </div> </div>								
NL11D	1408		" "					
NL11D Sig.		0.848	0.011				0.447	0.002

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Norway								
NO05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
NO05D1	984	0.510	-0.049	0.807	0.790	0.160		
NO05D1	984						max 0.688	0.066 0.290
NO05D1	984						sad -2.099	1.481 0.002
NO05D2	301	0.578	0.200	0.743	0.726	-0.004		
NO05D2	301						sad 1.040	-2.830 0.003
NO05D2	301						max 0.834	0.355 0.368
NO05D	1285							" "
NO05D Sig.		0.193	<0.0005				0.111	<0.0005
NO06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
NO06D1	1071	0.511	0.080	0.771	0.792	0.055		
NO06D1	1071						max 0.676	0.210 0.283
NO06D2	331	0.582	0.204	0.712	0.818	0.047		
NO06D2	331						max 0.768	0.402 0.276
NO06D	1402							" "
NO06D Sig.		0.013	0.205				0.004	0.004

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

NO07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
NO07D1	957	0.599	-0.074	0.812	0.822	0.126		
NO07D1	957						max 0.812	0.082 0.264
NO07D2	298	0.722	0.087	0.791	0.826	-0.050		
NO07D2	298						max 0.932	0.167 0.290
NO07D	1256							" "
NO07D Sig.		0.001	0.618				0.002	0.247

NO08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
NO08D1	988	0.681	-0.078	0.782	0.850	0.126		
NO08D1	988						max 0.971	0.182 0.266
NO08D2	308	0.823	0.174	0.753	0.862	-0.012		
NO08D2	308						max 1.131	0.416 0.301
NO08D	1296							" "
NO08D Sig.		0.005	<0.0005				0.001	0.002

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$		
NO09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31									
NO09D1	786	0.693	0.103	0.829	0.799	0.156				
NO09D1	786						max	0.999	0.221	0.285
NO09D2	282	0.782	0.276	0.812	0.812	0.073				
NO09D2	282						max	1.145	0.619	0.328
NO09D	1067									" "
NO09D Sig.		0.003	<0.0005					0.005	0.001	
NO10	2021-06-24–2022-04-27									
NO10D1	1110	0.827	0.239	0.829	0.807	0.172				
NO10D1	1110						max	1.151	0.435	0.297
NO10D	1110									" "
NO10D Sig.										" "

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
NO11	2023-04-20–2023-11-30								
NO11D1	1139	0.827	0.336	0.858	0.753	0.133			
NO11D1	1139						max	1.186 0.503 0.334	
NO11D	1139								
NO11D Sig.									
Poland									
PL05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
PL05D1	547	-0.184	0.573	0.949	0.831	-0.174			
PL05D1	547						sad	0.686 -3.594 0.000	
PL05D1	547						max	-0.396 0.651 0.202	
PL05D2	324	-0.228	0.676	0.966	0.727	-0.042			
PL05D2	324						max	-0.242 0.749 0.258	
PL05D3	146	-0.282	0.654	0.916	0.865	-0.110			
PL05D3	146						sad	2.470 -1.724 0.002	
PL05D3	146						max	-0.151 0.829 0.255	
PL05D3	146						sad	-3.070 3.154 0.003	
PL05D	1016								
PL05D Sig.		<0.0005	0.125					0.123 0.001	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
Sweden									
SE05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
SE05D1	729	0.552	0.360	0.800	0.838	0.070			
SE05D1	729					max	0.836	0.674	0.269
SE05D2	145	0.581	0.320	0.873	0.799	0.123			
SE05D2	145					max	0.903	0.510	0.255
SE05D3	258	0.539	0.568	0.776	0.824	0.059			
SE05D3	258					max	0.880	0.815	0.305
SE05D	1131								
SE05D Sig.		0.366	0.273				0.362	0.774	
SE06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31								
SE06D1	994	0.370	0.315	0.882	0.854	0.006			
SE06D1	994					max	0.672	0.479	0.234
SE06D2	192	0.314	0.160	0.820	0.923	0.036			
SE06D2	192					max	0.526	0.036	0.217
SE06D3	358	0.634	0.516	0.870	0.834	-0.160			
SE06D3	358					max	0.895	0.749	0.286
SE06D	1544								
SE06D Sig.		<0.0005	0.001				<0.0005	0.033	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

SE07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
SE07D1	922	0.576	0.367	0.901	0.842	0.101		
SE07D1	922						max 0.870	0.676 0.247
SE07D1	922						sad -3.527	0.025 0.001
SE07D2	192	0.591	0.333	0.809	0.713	0.040		
SE07D2	192						max 0.882	0.631 0.341
SE07D3	322	0.580	0.508	0.809	0.841	0.020		
SE07D3	322						max 0.886	0.853 0.266
SE07D3	322						sad -1.962	2.160 0.004
SE07D	1436							
SE07D Sig.		0.978	0.016				0.110	0.248

SE08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
SE08D1	789	0.489	0.290	0.820	0.882	0.234		
SE08D1	789						max 0.864	0.602 0.261
SE08D2	156	0.419	0.273	0.885	0.841	0.079		
SE08D2	156						max 1.035	0.531 0.321
SE08D3	298	0.623	0.466	0.755	0.862	0.154		
SE08D3	298						max 1.026	0.725 0.296
SE08D	1242							
SE08D Sig.		0.017	0.009				0.001	0.001

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
<hr/>									
SE09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31								
SE09D1	979	0.577	0.342	0.831	0.851	0.140			
SE09D1	979					max	0.946	0.654	0.259
SE09D3	314	0.591	0.420	0.804	0.911	0.041			
SE09D3	314					max	1.033	0.821	0.267
SE09D	1293					" "			
SE09D Sig.		0.001	0.025				0.107	0.038	
<hr/>									
Slovenia									
SI05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31								
SI05D1	583	-0.495	-0.029	1.022	0.900	-0.073			
SI05D1	583					max	-0.686	0.017	0.168
SI05D2	447	-0.526	0.007	0.976	0.896	0.107			
SI05D2	447					max	-0.891	-0.171	0.195
SI05D	1030					" "			
SI05D Sig.		0.425	0.005				0.011	0.146	

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

SI06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
SI06D1	501	-0.460	0.102	0.990	0.960	-0.036		
SI06D1	501					max	-0.459	0.194 0.154
SI06D2	411	-0.435	0.372	0.988	0.812	-0.200		
SI06D2	411					max	0.011	0.363 0.178
SI06D	912							" "
SI06D Sig.		0.703	<0.0005				0.007	0.109

SI07	2014-01-01–2015-12-31							
SI07D1	501	-0.539	0.023	0.893	0.853	0.036		
SI07D1	501					max	-0.924	0.018 0.210
SI07D2	360	-0.531	0.171	0.957	0.905	0.108		
SI07D2	360					max	-0.402	0.255 0.179
SI07D	862							" "
SI07D Sig.		0.691	0.542				0.619	0.600

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
<hr/>								
SI08	2016-01-01–2017-12-31							
SI08D1	674	-0.330	-0.200	0.963	0.931	0.018		
SI08D1	674					max	-0.379	-0.217 0.179
SI08D2	425	-0.385	-0.029	0.933	0.930	-0.052		
SI08D2	425					max	-0.602	0.002 0.174
SI08D	1099							" "
SI08D Sig.		0.058	0.106				0.337	0.150
<hr/>								
SI09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
SI09D1	593	-0.380	-0.276	1.021	0.973	0.025		
SI09D1	593					max	-0.509	-0.437 0.148
SI09D2	425	-0.371	-0.032	1.004	0.924	0.007		
SI09D2	425					max	-0.479	0.001 0.159
SI09D	1019							" "
SI09D Sig.		0.888	<0.0005				0.523	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

SI10	2020-09-18–2021-08-24							
SI10D1	594	-0.246	-0.071	1.013	0.944	-0.030		
SI10D1	594						sad	-1.165 -3.709 0.002
SI10D1	594						max	-0.179 -0.038 0.163
SI10D1	594						min	-0.095 4.366 0.000
SI10D2	436	-0.217	0.163	0.993	1.003	-0.138		
SI10D2	436						max	-0.042 0.246 0.145
SI10D	1030							" "
SI10D Sig.		0.637	<0.0005				0.028	0.001

SI11	2023-03-21–2023-08-14							
SI11D1	590	-0.024	-0.007	1.031	0.908	0.034		
SI11D1	590						max	0.435 0.055 0.173
SI11D2	348	-0.003	0.235	1.018	0.874	-0.021		
SI11D2	348						max	0.751 0.398 0.184
SI11D	938							" "
SI11D Sig.		0.708	0.238				0.727	0.297

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$
Slovakia								
SK05	2010-01-01–2011-12-31							
SK05D1	929	-0.078	0.026	1.001	0.790	-0.239		
SK05D1	929						sad	2.203 -3.057 0.002
SK05D1	929						max	-0.217 0.109 0.239
SK05D2	348	-0.288	0.097	1.024	1.049	-0.335		
SK05D2	348						max	-0.129 -0.014 0.156
SK05D2	348						sad	-4.676 0.943 0.001
SK05D3	184	-0.143	-0.067	0.947	0.931	-0.361		
SK05D3	184						sad	2.661 1.257 0.003
SK05D3	184						max	-0.242 0.146 0.192
SK05D3	184						sad	-2.500 -1.224 0.009
SK05D	1460							
SK05D Sig.		<0.0005	0.283				<0.0005	0.231
SK06	2012-01-01–2013-12-31							
SK06D1	1016	-0.462	-0.138	1.047	0.962	-0.040		
SK06D1	1016						max	-0.778 -0.100 0.174
SK06D2	273	-0.304	0.197	1.068	0.843	-0.279		
SK06D2	273						sad	0.232 -2.606 0.003
SK06D2	273						max	-0.874 0.284 0.286
SK06D2	273						sad	0.762 2.702 0.003
SK06D3	214	-0.450	-0.246	1.056	1.061	-0.432		
SK06D3	214						max	-1.034 0.469 0.147
SK06D	1503							
SK06D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	<0.0005

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Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$

SK09	2018-01-01–2020-12-31							
SK09D1	630	0.050	-0.462	1.328	1.001	-0.287		
SK09D1	630						max	-0.255 -0.570 0.127
SK09D2	192	0.241	-0.450	1.205	0.998	-0.421		
SK09D2	192						max	-0.270 -0.096 0.142
SK09D3	104	-0.085	-0.428	1.134	0.970	0.047		
SK09D3	104						sad	3.586 -0.482 0.009
SK09D3	104						max	-0.659 -1.281 0.327
SK09D3	104						sad	0.155 -0.002 0.073
SK09D3	104						max	0.410 0.681 0.090
SK09D3	104						sad	-2.225 2.648 0.012

SK09D1								
SK09D2								
SK09D3								
SK09D	926							
SK09D Sig.		0.429	<0.0005					0.090 <0.0005

SK10	2021-05-26–2021-10-31							
SK10D1	710	-0.035	-0.379	1.135	0.997	0.083		
SK10D1	710						max	-0.639 -0.601 0.140
SK10D2	217	-0.025	-0.426	1.077	0.902	0.082		
SK10D2	217						sad	1.839 -3.132 0.003
SK10D2	217						max	-0.349 -0.443 0.175
SK10D3	122	-0.212	0.254	0.944	1.045	0.039		
SK10D3	122						sad	2.016 -1.901 0.008
SK10D3	122						max	0.386 0.967 0.145
SK10D3	122						sad	-0.191 0.794 0.141
SK10D3	122						max	-0.737 0.551 0.145

SK10D1								
SK10D2								
SK10D3								
SK10D	1049							
SK10D Sig.		0.238	<0.0005					<0.0005 <0.0005

... continued on next page

Table 4: Parameters ... Trust and Immigration — Population Density (continued)

Region N	$\mu(x)$	$\mu(y)$	$\sigma(x)$	$\sigma(y)$	$\rho(x, y)$	FPT x_m	y_m	$f(x_m, y_m)$	
SK11	2023-09-10–2023-12-11								
SK11D1	719	0.242	-0.556	1.191	1.074	-0.013			
SK11D1	719						max	-0.073 -0.785 0.108	
SK11D2	317	0.125	-0.670	1.032	0.933	0.241			
SK11D2	317						sad	2.824 -2.353 0.003	
SK11D2	317						max	-0.344 -1.165 0.212	
SK11D3	104	0.545	-0.627	0.917	0.868	0.019			
SK11D3	104						sad	3.552 -1.213 0.005	
SK11D3	104						max	0.078 -1.341 0.268	
SK11D3	104						sad	-2.307 0.379 0.002	
SK11D3	104						sad	-0.438 2.488 0.004	
SK11D3	104						min	-1.770 1.742 0.001	

SK11D1

SK11D2

SK11D3

SK11D	1140							
SK11D Sig.		<0.0005	<0.0005				<0.0005	0.004

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